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Abstract

This Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan provides a framework that guides the daily activities within the GraspOS project. It outlines how these activities contribute to the visibility and uptake of project results, and ensures engagement with external stakeholders and ongoing initiatives in Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment. The Plan has guided the daily operations of the project, and is monitored continuously, to support both the current activities of the project and post-project sustainability.

The document reports on activities carried out since the start of the project, including the use of digital platforms, events, publications, and community engagement, and assesses their effectiveness through key performance indicators. It also describes updates made to the original plan to optimise outreach and alignment with related initiatives. In addition, the DECP sets out the final exploitation strategy, including the identification of key exploitable results, value propositions, sustainability pathways, and alignment with European Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment initiatives.

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Abbreviation List

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BIP! NDR	BIP! NoDoiRefs dataset
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoP	Community of Practice
CRIS	Current Research Information System
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D&E&C	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DBLP	Digital Bibliography & Library Project
DECP	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
DORI	Declaration on Open Research Information
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
N/A	Not Applicable

OA	Open Access
OI4RRA	Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
ORE	Open Research Europe
OS	Open Science
OSAF	Open Science Assessment Framework
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RIs	Research Infrastructures
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RP	Reporting Period
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan (DECP) has guided the dissemination, exploitation, and communication (D&E&C) activities of the GraspOS project, ensuring they are carried out in the most efficient way so as to maximise the uptake and impact of project results. The DECP aims to promote, raise awareness, and enhance the visibility of the project, ensuring that key stakeholders are effectively engaged in order to successfully exploit project outcomes. It also sets out targeted actions to promote GraspOS's mission to foster Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). It identifies clear stakeholder groups and aligns its communication channels to reach these audiences effectively. A KPI framework allows for monitoring progress and adjusting strategies when necessary.

The DECP is structured as follows:

Section 1. Introduction provides an overview of the GraspOS project objectives and expected impacts.

Section 2. Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy reports the objectives of the DECP, and outlines the strategy to manage C&D activities in the project so as to maximise engagement with stakeholders and to ensure the uptake of project outcomes. The C&D Key performance indicators are also included there.

Section 3. Report on C&D activities provides information on the measures taken to reach the objectives of the DECP for all GraspOS channels.

Section 4. Alignment with the communication of GraspOS partners and collaborations with related projects and initiatives highlights activities related to engagement with external stakeholders within the project.

Section 5. Final Exploitation Plan of the GraspOS project and outlines the concrete measures undertaken to ensure the long-term sustainability, adoption, and valorisation of the project outcomes.

Methodology

Not applicable.

1. Introduction

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DECP) is a framework which guides the dissemination, exploitation, and communication (D&E&C) activities of the Horizon Europe project GraspOS¹ (Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science, Grant Agreement n.101095129).

The task is managed by CNR within Work Package 6 and the current document provides a final update of the first DECP (Deliverable 6.1, DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077)) delivered in June 2023 (M6).

1.1 GraspOS overview

GraspOS is a research project focused on creating an open research assessment infrastructure² providing data, tools, services and guidance to support and enable policy reforms for Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) at various levels including researchers, institutions, organisations and countries.

The project was launched on 1st January 2023, and will come to an end on 31st December 2025. The overall objective of GraspOS is to enable a rewards and recognition system based on a new generation of qualitative and quantitative metrics and indicators, leading to a culture and system change that increases the quality and impact, the creativity and the transparency of and trust in science, and to establish a system of qualitative information

¹ <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/>

² We follow the Data Spaces Support Centre's definition of data space as defined in the DSSC Glossary: "An infrastructure that enables data transactions between different data ecosystem parties based on the governance framework of that data space. Data space should be generic enough to support the implementation of multiple use cases".

<https://dssc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DSSC-Data-Spaces-Glossary-v1.0.pdf>

based on community-led curation and annotations of research outcomes that feeds into a revamped rewards and recognition system.

The objectives and expected impacts of the project are summarised below³.

Project objectives

1. Deliver the **SCOPE+i Framework** as a toolkit to assist RFOs and RPOs in tailoring and implementing new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
2. Develop and deliver a set of **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-integrated, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven metadata enrichment tools and services** for enhancing missing attributes and novel indicator values on research outputs to support the implementation of new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
3. Build an **EOSC-integrated, open research assessment dataspace** providing data, tools, and services to support the implementation of new generation, Open Science-aware RRA approaches.
4. Empower and bring together different stakeholder communities to co-design, showcase, validate, and evaluate Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools, services, and infrastructure in **real-world pilots**.

Expected impacts

- Improve transparency, creativity, and trust in research assessment.
- Reform the way research funders, organisations, and communities perform research assessment.
- Generate new data and develop new tools enabling qualitative research assessment.
- Contribute to EOSC Core and provide EOSC native services for research assessment on Open Science.

³ For additional details on GraspOS objectives and expected impacts, please see section 1.2 of GraspOS Deliverable 6.1. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077).

2. C&D strategy

The C&D strategy was tailored to promote, raise awareness, and enhance the visibility of the project so as to maximise the exploitation of project results. This section presents the main elements of the strategy, as defined in M6 (2.1)⁴, changes brought to the initial plan (2.2), Open Science practices (2.3), and the C&D KPIs (2.4).

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⁴ For an extensive description of stakeholder groups, please refer to section 2.1 of the Deliverable 6.1. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077).

2.1 Objectives of the DECP and target audiences

The main objectives of the DECP are recalled below, along with the key results to be addressed by the D&E&C measures, and the main stakeholder categories targeted by these measures.

The objectives of the DECP are as follows:

- Build awareness about the project;
- Lay down the foundations for effective communication of the project's concept and potential benefits to interested stakeholders;
- Communicate research findings so as to stimulate ongoing interest in the work of the project;
- Build the foundations for future partnerships among the engaged stakeholders;
- Maximise the project's impact;
- Maximise exploitation opportunities of the project throughout and beyond its development.

The key results addressed by the D&E&C measures are the following:

1. [SCOPE+i Framework](#): The project has developed a tailored infrastructure that works together with the existing SCOPE framework, which is known as the (GraspOS) SCOPE+i Framework. This assessment infrastructure consists of two main components: assessment process resources and digital services. The assessment process resources offer guidance for implementing key elements of RRA while the assessment digital services enable collaborative collection and sharing of assessment plans and documentation throughout the entire assessment process.
2. [Enrichment Services](#): Tools and services to enhance missing attributes on research outputs, enrich research output links with semantics, enrich research outputs with novel metrics capturing scientific impact or usage of Open Science from different perspectives.
3. [Monitoring Services](#): (a) an Open Science Institutional Dashboard, a tailor-made Open Science Profile for research performing organisations; (b) an Open Science Researcher Dashboard, a tailor-made Open Science Profile for researchers, offering Open Science metrics and functions for manual annotations and narratives.
4. [Open and Federated Research Assessment Infrastructure](#): A federated infrastructure that extends the EOSC Interoperability Framework with the appropriate metadata standards, protocols, components and APIs to support AI-driven annotation/enrichment and to implement an EOSC Core Metrics service based on the integration of key GraspOS components.
5. [Pilots](#): Piloting activities to co-design, showcase, validate, and evaluate GraspOS's key results considering domain-specific aspects and different levels of Open Science-aware RRA.

6. [Community of Practice](#): An open space where a diverse community of RRA experts and practitioners from relevant networks can exchange experiences and reflect on current developments related to Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools, and services.
7. [Training material](#): A set of six trainings and six webinars developed to support capacity-building and stakeholder engagement. To ensure sustainability and ongoing public engagement, presentations are openly available on Zenodo, and session recordings are hosted on OpenAIRE's YouTube channel⁵. An interactive online course is being created on OpenPlato⁶ using Articulate⁷, enhancing the accessibility and reusability of the content.

Target audiences

The target audiences of the project are illustrated in the Figure below. During the project's duration, these groups were targeted in community consultations, in specific events and collaborations, and in the general communication activities of the project which are detailed in section 3. Further details are provided on each target group in section 2.1 of the Deliverable 6.1 (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077)).

⁵ Playlist "Training and Webinars of GraspOS"

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL0c4IRNUxuKf73fGnsfSMO9DKCFT-YZR1>

⁶ <https://openplato.eu/>

⁷ <https://id.articulate.com/>

Figure 1. GraspOS target audiences

C&D channels

The C&D channels used in the project include a variety of platforms and activities to reach the diverse audiences represented in Figure 1.

These channels consist of the project website⁸, social media (LinkedIn⁹, Mastodon¹⁰, X¹¹), a monthly newsletter¹², and stakeholder consultations through the Community of Practice¹³ and Pilots¹⁴. Outreach activities also include GraspOS-led webinars, training tutorials and events, as well as participation in external events by project partners. In addition, scientific publications authored by project partners contribute to the dissemination of project results. The nine pilot's success stories, and a Final brief will be produced towards the end of the project to serve as a legacy, showcasing key achievements, lessons learnt, and policy insights.

⁸ <https://graspos.eu/>

⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9303131/>

¹⁰ <https://mastodon.social/@graspos@scicomm.xyz>

¹¹ https://x.com/GraspOS_project

¹² <https://graspos.eu/newsletters>

¹³ <https://graspos.eu/community-of-practice-on-open-science-and-responsible-research-assessment>

¹⁴ <https://graspos.eu/case-studies>

The activities carried out across the various C&D channels of the project are detailed in section 3. of the DECP.

C&D workflow

A clear C&D workflow was established at the outset of the project and has been consistently followed to ensure alignment with and successful delivery of the DECP objectives. Figure 2 below outlines how information flows from internal sources to external communication and dissemination channels in the GraspOS project.

Figure 2. GraspOS C&D workflow

The process begins with several key sources which provide content for communication and dissemination. These sources mainly include WP Leaders (WPL) and WPs meeting minutes, the events list of the project, input provided by project partners for the monthly GraspOS newsletter, and project emails. These sources of information provide the foundation for identifying what should be communicated.

From these, a set of topics is identified for regular communication. These topics represent both internal developments related to the project and external initiatives and activities, such as GraspOS technical developments and GraspOS-led events, External conferences and webinars, Information about external initiatives like the EOSC, the Coalition for Advancing

Research Assessment (CoARA), and the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), Exploitation of project results, and joint activities with other projects and initiatives.

Once topics are defined, they are translated into content for communication and dissemination on a daily or weekly basis, depending on the nature of the information. Daily communication was prioritised for time-sensitive activities such as events and community consultations, while consistent weekly engagement was maintained throughout the project to ensure ongoing visibility and interaction. Content is shared through a variety of channels, which are designed to reach the different target audiences of the project.

2.2 Updates to the strategy

The implementation of the C&D strategy followed closely the strategy laid out in the Deliverable 6.1 DECP delivered at the beginning of the project (M6), relying on a set of organisational tools to facilitate the management of C&D activities across the project¹⁵.

Following the assessment of the C&D strategy in the first reporting period of the project, a series of changes were brought; these adjustments are detailed below.

Website

It was suggested that the visibility of the project's outcomes could be improved to ensure that relevant stakeholders have a clearer understanding of the impact and benefits of GraspOS. In response, several updates were made to the website. A series of short, accessible news pieces written in non-technical language were published to communicate project developments, deliverables, and interim results. Additionally, the "Methodology" section of the website was revised and expanded, including the integration of a new visual diagram that illustrates the architecture of the project in a more comprehensive and intuitive way¹⁶.

Cross-projects collaboration plans

Recommendations were made to improve the planning and articulation of GraspOS collaborations with other projects, particularly in terms of clarifying the mutual benefits and the strategic value of these collaborations. To address this, the responsibilities for managing these collaborations were clearly defined: ARC, within WP1, was tasked with the coordination of collaborative inputs from all partners, while CNR, under WP6, ensured the proper communication of these activities through updated website content and dissemination materials. A new section was added to the project website¹⁷, containing information on the collaboration activities that GraspOS carries out with other projects and initiatives. For each collaboration, a web page provides information on the rationale, focus areas, expected outcomes, and mutual benefits of the collaboration. Furthermore, a promotional campaign

¹⁵ These organisational tools are provided in the Deliverable 6.1, Annex 2, 3, 4, and 5. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077)

¹⁶ <https://graspos.eu/methodology>

¹⁷ <https://graspos.eu/collaborations>

titled “Connecting the Dots: Cross-project Conversations”¹⁸ was launched in September 2024. This initiative features representatives of projects and initiatives with whom GraspOS has collaborated in the form of discussion-like interviews, to be published on the project website and promoted across the various social media and online channels.

Community of Practice

It was noted that user engagement within the Community of Practice (CoP) could benefit from closer monitoring. In response, the CoP section of the website was revised to provide a more detailed description of its objectives. An internal planning document was also introduced for CoP organisers to support the coordination of meetings and monitor user engagement across the series. To foster more active engagement, the format of the final four sessions was revised: instead of using the CoP as an outlet to present the different pilots, it was decided to focus on topics of interest for the wider community where external colleagues and GraspOS colleagues reflected on these issues.

Training and webinars

The need to better track user engagement and participation in training and webinar activities was also highlighted. To improve outreach, partners were encouraged to promote GraspOS training events more actively through their own networks. At the same time, systematic tracking of participant numbers was introduced, along with post-event surveys to collect feedback on the level of satisfaction of participants.

Exploitation Plan

Finally, it was advised that the long-term sustainability of project outcomes should be more clearly addressed, particularly with regard to those results with potential for market uptake. To respond to this, a detailed characterisation of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) was carried out. This included identifying target users, defining value propositions, assessing technology maturity, and outlining preliminary exploitation paths. This work contributed directly to the refinement of the Exploitation Plan. In parallel, the project applied for support from the Horizon Results Booster (HRB). The service launch took place in January 2025, focusing on the Go-to-Market service which provided valuable support in refining the value propositions of the KERs, identifying relevant market segments and stakeholders, shaping a preliminary sustainability and business strategy, and designing a coherent and actionable exploitation roadmap.

¹⁸ <https://graspos.eu/connecting-the-dots-cross-project-conversations>

2.3 Open Science practices

In alignment with the project's strong commitment to support and enable Open Science practices, all project outputs are made available in Open Access (OA), following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles ([Wilkinson et al, 2016](#)).

Peer reviewed scientific publications funded under the Grant are available in OA, and a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version is deposited in a trusted repository, using a CC BY license or equivalent.

The trusted OA repository Zenodo¹⁹ was selected to deposit all GraspOS outputs for several reasons.

- Trusted and certified repository ensuring long-term accessibility and integrity of research outputs.
- Assignment of DOIs to deposited objects, facilitating citation and discoverability
- Carefully curated metadata with open metadata under a CC BY license, enhancing visibility and reuse.
- Long-term archiving to guarantee accessibility.
- Support for various file formats and large datasets, making it suitable for a wide range of research outputs.

Given the diversity of outputs produced within the project, a total of five Zenodo communities were created.

The **GraspOS** community²⁰ gathers all the outputs produced within the project, including: Reports, deliverables, and policy briefs; Presentations of the GraspOS Community of Practice meetings; Presentations of the GraspOS Training and Webinar events; Datasets; Posters; The Data Management Plan.

The **GraspOS Tools** community²¹ serves as a GraspOS tools catalogue. It lists all stand-alone GraspOS enrichment and monitoring tools and facilitates their discovery and exploration.

The **GraspOS Datasets** community²² serves as a GraspOS datasets. It enables users to explore and understand data and metadata within the GraspOS federated infrastructure, and serves as an inventory of data sources and assets.

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/>

²⁰ https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos_project/

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-tools/>

²² <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-datasets/>

The GraspOS **Templates & Guidelines** community²³ will serve as a metadata catalogue for GraspOS research assessment templates, guidelines, checklists, and toolboxes, facilitating their discovery and exploration.

All four communities were added to the EU Open Research Repository²⁴, a Zenodo community managed by CERN on behalf of the EC which facilitates compliance with Open Science requirements and complements the Open Research Europe (ORE) publishing platform and by providing a space for all the other research outputs including data sets, software, posters, and presentations that are out of scope for ORE²⁵. This choice provides greater visibility and easier discoverability of GraspOS outputs by relevant stakeholders.

Lastly, the **Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment community**²⁶ collects all the presentations given by project partners at external conferences, meetings and relevant events in which they present the project advancements and results. This community welcomes external contributions with the aim to provide a space for researchers interested in research assessment reform, research assessment experts and relevant initiatives and frameworks working on the reform.

2.4 Key performance indicators (KPIs)

The effectiveness of the overall strategy was assessed through a regular monitoring of the C&D KPIs, reported in Table 1 below. The following KPIs served as a baseline to quantify positive evolutions or needs for improvement in the C&D strategy. They are reported below with the state of progress at M6 and M31.

Table 1. Communication and Dissemination (C&D) KPIs

Channel	Activity	KPI	Measure	M6	M31
Project website	main source for outputs and news	# visitors	>200 unique monthly visitors	A usage tracking tool was set up in M12.	496 unique visitors
Social Media (X, LinkedIn, Mastodon)	project specific social media profiles for dissemination and communication purposes, including video tutorials	# followers	> 500 X followers	258 X followers	693 X followers 257 LinkedIn members 268 Mastodon followers

²³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources/>

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/>

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/about>

²⁶ https://zenodo.org/communities/open_science_rra/

Newsletter	Disseminating project-specific content and news to subscribers	# newsletters	monthly newsletter	Activity starts at M6	26 Newsletters 348 subscribers
Training tutorials	Training and co-design workshops organised by the project	# events	6 training tutorials, engaging overall 300 participants	Activity started in M12	5 training tutorials 220 participants
GraspOS webinars	2 webinars per year organised by the project	# events	6 webinars targeting 240 participants	2 events	5 webinars 386 participants
GraspOS final conference	1 final F2F conference	# participants	Minimum 100 participants	N/A	The conference will take place in M35
Participation in external events	promoting project outputs at external events	# of events with contributions from project partners	> 30 events	5 events completed, 4 in preparation	65 events completed, 6 in preparation
Scientific publications	OA journals and platforms	# publications	4 research outputs	1 publication	11 publications

The KPIs for communication and dissemination have been successfully reached, and are well on track regarding GraspOS training tutorials and webinars. The project website, which serves as the main hub for the project's communication, saw 496 unique visitors in M31, well above the KPI of 200 unique monthly users. Social media engagement exceeded targets with 693 followers on X, 257 members in the LinkedIn group, and 268 followers on Mastodon. The monthly newsletter, launched as planned in M6 and delivered monthly, currently reaches 348 subscribers, with 26 newsletters published. Participation in external events has been especially strong, with contributions to 65 events, significantly exceeding the goal of 30. Finally, 12 scientific publications have been published, tripling the initial target of 4.

Training and co-design workshops began in M12 and have already delivered 5 tutorials to 220 participants, closely approaching the target of 6 events and 300 participants. The same applies to GraspOS webinars with 5 events reaching 386 participants, against a goal of 6 webinars and 240 attendees.

The delay in the delivery of the training tutorials and webinars is justified by our commitment to delivering a more complete and user-friendly training offer. Specifically:

- Additional components of high relevance were identified during the initial roll-out. For example, the upcoming session "GraspOS Infrastructure – A Walkthrough" will offer users a practical guide to navigate the tools and services of the project.

- We have one final webinar requested by SSH/OPERAS and one more training event with OPUS Framework, and we are also preparing a session dedicated to the launch of the MyResearchFolio. This is a new service developed in response to the needs expressed by the pilots and, although not originally planned in the training activities, we believe it is worth presenting and discussing with a broader community.
- We are also considering including posters and pilot case reports from the final event in November. These will provide practical examples of how to use GraspOS resources, further supporting end users.
- Content harmonisation required additional coordination, especially due to updates such as the renaming of OSAF to SCOPE+i. We are progressively correcting all references across the sessions.
- Metadata curation and user experience improvements in OpenPlato introduced additional overhead but are crucial for ensuring accessibility, findability, and long-term usability of the training content.

These improvements aim not only to complete the course as initially planned but also to significantly enhance its clarity, coherence, and practical value for future users.

3. Report on Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities

In the initial phase (M1-M12) of the project, the activities focused on communicating about GraspOS objectives and promoting project activities through various channels. From the second year of the project onwards, efforts focused on disseminating technical project developments, outcomes and strengthening collaborations with external stakeholders. For each of the strategies outlined above, this section reports on the C&D activities carried out from the beginning of the project until M31.

3.1 Website

Website Strategy

The GraspOS project website (<https://graspos.eu/>) is hosted by ATHENA RC, Greece and administered by CNR, Italy. It was delivered in M3, and has been the main channel to communicate and disseminate the outcomes of the project to key stakeholders.

The idea was to create a digital ecosystem that boosts the online presence of the project and reaches out to key stakeholders effectively. The digital ecosystem, represented below in

Figure 3, highlights the central role of the project website in the communication and dissemination strategy and outlines the information flow with target networks.

Figure 3. GraspOS digital ecosystem

Information is shared from the website towards external channels which act as amplifiers by re-sharing the information to other networks of stakeholders. Some of the external channels are managed by GraspOS and represent GraspOS communities on different social media platforms (X, Mastodon, LinkedIn). To circulate information, the project also relied on project partners' networks, and on impactful stakeholders such as the EOSC Association²⁷ (also through the EOSC Forum²⁸) and CoARA²⁹. This strategy had the double advantage of considering the project website as the source of communication and dissemination activities while also bringing traffic to the website. The News section of the website served as the main point to communicate on project updates and share relevant news. Content was shared on a regular basis of 2 articles per month, including communication campaigns (interviews, stakeholder consultations), short reports on project activities and results, and news from relevant initiatives.

The architecture of the website is represented in Figure 4. below.

²⁷ <https://eosc.eu/>

²⁸ <https://forum.eosc.eu/>

²⁹ <https://coara.eu/>

Figure 4. GraspOS website architecture

Updates to the Strategy

As the project progressed, several improvements were required to optimise website navigation.

A **slideshow** was added on the homepage of the website to feature important information, next events, new results, or consultations. Typically, it features announcements on upcoming webinars or public consultations organised by GraspOS, Community of Practice meetings, and summaries of technical deliverables.

The former **'Activities&Results'** menu tab was divided in two to facilitate users' navigation on the website, and in particular to give more visibility to the Community of Practice (CoP), and the Training and webinars series. The **Activities** menu tab gathers information on ongoing activities in the project. Dedicated pages were created as sub-tabs for the following activities: Community of Practice; Training and Webinar Series; Collaborations; Interviews. The **Outputs** menu tab is dedicated to project results and provides access to the GraspOS Deliverables and Publications, and information on the Key Results of the project.

A significant part of the work in GraspOS consists in alignment with other projects and initiatives to collectively foster and build an Open Science-aware research assessment system.

To highlight these collaborative efforts, a dedicated page of the website, **'Collaborations'**, was created and regularly updated to provide information on the projects and initiatives GraspOS collaborates with. For each bi-directional collaboration, an individual page details the main characteristics of the collaboration, mutual benefits and joint activities. The collaboration activity was supported by the communication campaign "Connecting the Dots: Cross-project conversations", a series of collective interviews featuring project representatives discussing their joint efforts to advance Open Science and RRA.

Finally, following the renaming of the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) to the SCOPE+i Framework, the website was updated accordingly. All pages were revised to reflect the new name, and references to the former name were removed.

Results

The GraspOS website registered an average 443 unique monthly users since the beginning of the traffic monitoring using Google analytics in M12. For detailed monitoring of website traffic, please go to Annex 1. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS website traffic (M12-M31).

As of 31 July 2025, a total of 57 articles were published in the News section³⁰ of the GraspOS website. As reported in Table 2. below, these articles are grouped into four content categories.

Table 2. Articles published in the news section of the website

News and updates about GraspOS and external initiatives	32 articles
Inside stories from the Pilot studies	9 stories
GraspOS Chats	12 interviews
Connecting the Dots	4 discussions
Total	57 articles

A total of 32 news articles were published between M3 and M31 to raise awareness about the project and promote its activities, including relevant external initiatives and projects. The articles mainly focused on topics related to GraspOS activities and results (summaries of technical deliverables, presentation of GraspOS results, calls for community consultations, and training and workshop takeaways), and updates from external initiatives of high relevance to the project (CoARA WGs and National Chapters, EOSC-related news, EC-related news in the field of Open Science and RRA).

³⁰ <https://graspos.eu/news>

In addition, three communication campaigns were launched to raise awareness about the project and beyond.

- Pilot studies: *Inside stories from the Pilot studies*³¹, a series of 9 interviews conducted between M7 and M21 which focused on informing stakeholders about the aims and ongoing activities of the nine Pilots. These interviews served as a basis to create the Pilot's Success Stories (see section 3.8) which will be delivered towards the end of the project.
- Project members: *GraspOS Chats*,³² a series of 12 interviews conducted between M6 and M30 to present GraspOS team members, their role in the project, and their views on the need for an Open Science-aware RRA System.
- Cross-project conversations: *Connecting the Dots*³³, a shorter series of 4 conversations planned between M21 and M29 with representatives from relevant projects and initiatives to discuss joint efforts to advance Open Science and responsible research assessment. These conversations are longer than the aforementioned interviews and served as a means to highlight specific collaborations and to disseminate the GraspOS community of practice events which were of wider interest to the Open Science and RRA community.

The content listed above was published on the website, and was subsequently shared in the monthly newsletter and promoted across social media channels to maximise outreach, for which specific visuals were created. Examples of visuals are available in the figures below.

The full list of articles published in the News section of the website can be found in Annex 2. List of articles published on the GraspOS website. A selection of visuals created to accompany the promotion of articles published on the website is provided below (Figures 5-9).

³¹ <https://graspos.eu/inside-stories-from-the-pilot-studies>

³² <https://graspos.eu/graspos-chats>

³³ <https://graspos.eu/connecting-the-dots-cross-project-conversations>

Figure 5. Inside story visual for website

Figure 6. Inside story visual for social media

Figure 7. GraspOS Chats visual for website

Figure 8. GraspOS Chats visual for social media

Figure 9. Connecting the Dots visual for website

3.2 Social media

3.2.1 Strategy

GraspOS social media accounts were set up to reach and address various groups of stakeholders with different needs and interests across the European research landscape. Social media presence allowed us to reach broader audiences than through traditional dissemination activities and to achieve the objectives listed below. All social media channels are administered and maintained by CNR, Italy.

- **Raise awareness about the project's concept and main goals.** In the initial stages of the project, the objective is to inform about the project and to increase and broaden the project's audience.
- **Build a community.** GraspOS will maximise community outreach and engagement through its social media channels. Social media will also be used to promote collaborations through the exchange of information, ideas and opinions.
- **Increase visibility and generate traffic to the GraspOS website.**
- **Promote and inform about GraspOS activities and events.** The project's social media channels are used to share project surveys, workshops and events.
- **Analyse the effectiveness and impact of our social media communication activities.** GraspOS will verify the impact of its social media presence by periodically reporting on engagement metrics using the tools provided by each social media platform.
- **Promote the EC and the EOSC.**

3.2.2 Results

GraspOS social media communication and dissemination measures have been implemented in accordance to the objectives and target audiences detailed in section 3.3 of the Deliverable 6.1³⁴. Activities have been carried out through the project's social media accounts on X, LinkedIn, and Mastodon. All social media channels were administered and maintained by CNR, Italy. The project also made use of OpenAIRE Youtube channel reach to disseminate GraspOS training activities and video tutorials.

The main topics of social media posts focus on raising awareness on the project's activities and results; fostering engagement and participation in project training and webinars, Community of Practice meetings, stakeholder consultations, and events involving GraspOS partners; and informing stakeholders about relevant events and initiatives in the world of Open Science and RRA. GraspOS also regularly shares (through reposts) content from project partner institutions and external, related research infrastructures, projects and initiatives.

To maximise outreach and to ensure the development of a community around the GraspOS project, high impact accounts such as project partner institutions and external initiatives (including but not limited to CoARA, DORA, Barcelona Declaration, EOSC Association) were regularly tagged and frequently used hashtags in the field (#ResearchAssessment, #ReformingRA, #OpenScience, #CoARA) were consistently included in the social media posts.

The subsections below provide information on each social media channel.

X ACCOUNT

Creation: January 2023

URL: https://x.com/GraspOS_project

User name: @GraspOS_project

Display name: GraspOS

The GraspOS profile on X was created in January 2023 and officially started posting in February 2023. As of 31 July 2025, 616 posts had been published or reposted from the GraspOS project account. It should be noted that free access to the profile's analytics were discontinued in June 2024. From then onwards, monthly impressions and engagement data, which were used to measure the visibility of posts (number of times content was displayed) and the level of user interaction (likes, shares, comments, clicks), were not freely available anymore. We therefore focused on manually monitoring the number of monthly original posts, likes, shares and followers. As of 31 July 2025, the GraspOS profile on X has gathered 692 followers and published 225 original posts, for a total of 892 shares and 1815 likes.

³⁴ Deliverable 6.1. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8087077](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8087077)

It should be noted that the acquisition of Twitter in late 2022 (rebranded as X since then) was followed by significant policy shifts, which led users to migrate to alternative platforms such as Mastodon and Bluesky. This migration contributed to a decline in user engagement on this social media platform. The table below reports the overall engagement figures as of 31 July 2025. The extended monthly monitoring table, in which the decline in user engagement is more visible, is available in Annex 3. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS X account (M2-M31).

Table 3. Overall engagement metrics X account (M31)

Original posts	Followers	Shares	Likes
225	693	892	1815

LINKEDIN GROUP

Creation: January 2023

URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9303131/>

Name: GraspOS

The GraspOS profile on LinkedIn was created in January 2023 and officially started posting in February 2023. The profile was first created as a private group to favour the development of a small community which would leave more space for interactions. This strategy was however revised with the migration of X users towards other platforms including LinkedIn, and the group became public on 6 July 2023.

As of 31 July 2025, the LinkedIn group gathered 257 members, with 116 original posts published, and 58787 impressions³⁵. The table below reports the overall engagement figures as of 31 July 2025. The extended monthly monitoring table is available in Annex 4. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS LinkedIn account (M2-M31).

Table 4. Overall engagement metrics LinkedIn group (M31)

Original posts	Members	Impressions
116	257	58787

³⁵ Impressions refer to the number of times a post was shown on LinkedIn.

MASTODON

Creation: May 2023

URL: <https://scicomm.xyz/@graspos>

User name: @GraspOS

Display name: GraspOS

The GraspOS profile on Mastodon was created in May 2023 as a response to the user migration from X to other alternative platforms. The main objective was to stay in touch with the active community of former X users, especially researchers, who moved towards Mastodon, a decentralised and open source network. The outreach was not as high as expected, as the user base never reached that of X, but we chose to keep the profile active and mostly to relay the same content on Mastodon that we posted on the other two social media.

A monitoring tool is available for Mastodon (MastoMetrics³⁶) but it only retrieves overall engagement figures (total number of followers and total number of posts, including reposted content). Additionally, this tool suffers from regular maintenance issues which limits access to analytics. The number of monthly original posts and the growth of the follower base was therefore reported manually on a periodical basis.

As of 31 July 2025, the account totalled 257 followers, with 295 posts published or reposted from the GraspOS project account, and 160 original posts. The extended monthly monitoring table is available in Annex 5. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS Mastodon account (M2-M31).

Table 5. Overall engagement metrics Mastodon account (M31)

Original posts	Followers
160	257

³⁶ <https://mastometrics.com/>

3.3 Newsletter

To inform GraspOS stakeholders on the advancements and results of the project, a monthly newsletter has been shared with subscribers starting from June 2023. Each edition is also hosted in the News section of the project website³⁷ and shared on social media and with the EOSC community through the Communication and Engagement WG monthly meeting.

The newsletter focuses on promoting GraspOS activities, progress and results, and also includes news on relevant initiatives and a calendar of upcoming events in the Open Science and RRA ecosystem. The table below links all the monthly newsletters published up to July 2025. As of 31 July 2025, the GraspOS newsletter counted 348 subscribers and 26 editions had been published.

Table 6. GraspOS monthly newsletters

2023	2024	2025
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • June • July • August • September • October • November • December 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • January • February • March • April • May • June • July • August • September • October • November • December 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • January • February • March • April • May • June • July

3.4 Events

Within the project, we distinguish between two types of events: GraspOS-led events, and Participation to external events. The former includes Conferences and internal workshops organised by the project (CoP meetings, trainings, and webinars are treated separately, see sections 3.6 and 3.7), while the latter includes external events attended by project partners including conferences, workshops and organisation meetings related to research careers and incentives, research assessment and Open Science and EOSC-related events to present the results of the project and to understand how the landscape is developing.

³⁷ <https://graspos.eu/newsletters>

3.4.1 GraspOS-led events

The table below reports information on the GraspOS-led events since the beginning of the project. By the end of the project, a total of 7 events (6 in person, and 1 online) will have been organised by the project, including the Final Conference. The events listed below were promoted to stakeholders through social media, and for the internal workshops, summaries were produced in lay language and published on the project website as news items.

Table 7. GraspOS-led events

Event #1	
Event type	Joint Workshop at a Conference
Name	Open Science Fair 2023
Date	25 September 2023
Venue	Madrid, Spain
Title	Monitoring Open Science in the context of incentives and rewards for Open Science
Speakers	Natalia Manola, Giulia Malaguarnera (OpenAIRE)
Audience	EOSC Ecosystem
Outreach	163 participants
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10000921
Additional information	Joint workshop between GraspOS, OPUS, and PathOS projects at the Open Science FAIR 2023
Event #2	
Event type	Conference, Special Session
Name	STI 2023
Date	28 September 2023
Venue	Leiden, Netherlands
Title	Research(er) evaluation at the interface of open science and responsible research assessment
Speakers	Thanasis Vergoulis (Athena Research Centre), Ludo Waltman (CWTS), Anestis Amanatidis (CWTS), Andrea Mannocci (CNR)

Audience	Research communities
Outreach	350 (total conference attendees)
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8424590
Additional information	GraspOS special session at STI 2023 Conference on the OSAF and the Open Metrics Infrastructure
Event #3	
Event type	Internal workshop
Name	GraspOS Pilots Internal Workshop
Date	3 October 2023
Venue	Online
Title	Stakeholder mapping exercise
Speakers	N/A
Audience	GraspOS Pilot representatives
Outreach	N/A
Materials	https://graspos.eu/report-from-the-graspos-pilot-workshops (summary news piece reporting on the three internal workshops Event #3, #4 and #5)
Additional information	A workshop exercise in which pilot representatives identified the various groups of stakeholders they aimed at including in their piloting activities, using guidance from the OSAF and the SCOPE Framework.
Event #4	
Event type	Internal workshop
Name	GraspOS Pilots Internal Workshop
Date	22 November 2023
Venue	Espoo, Finland
Title	OSAF Method - Values Statement
Speakers	N/A
Audience	GraspOS Pilot Representatives

Outreach	N/A
Materials	https://graspos.eu/report-from-the-graspos-pilot-workshops (summary news piece reporting on the three internal workshops Event #3, #4 and #5)
Additional information	This workshop focused on integrating SCOPE principles into the OSAF. A central element of the preparatory work for the workshop was the development of a values statement by each pilot representative.
Event #5	
Event type	Internal workshop
Name	GraspOS Pilots Internal Workshop
Date	31 January 2024
Venue	Leiden, Netherlands
Title	Tools and Services Exploration
Speakers	N/A
Audience	GraspOS Pilot Representatives
Outreach	N/A
Materials	https://graspos.eu/report-from-the-graspos-pilot-workshops (summary news item reporting on the three internal workshops Event #3, #4 and #5)
Additional information	A workshop centred on the development and use of GraspOS tools and services for the pilots.
Event #6	
Event type	Internal Workshop
Name	GraspOS Pilots Internal Workshop
Date	29-30 May 2024
Venue	Athens, Greece
Title	Roadmaps for GraspOS pilots: pathways for service inclusion
Speakers	N/A
Audience	GraspOS Pilot and Services teams

Outreach	N/A
Materials	https://graspos.eu/building-roadmaps-for-the-graspos-pilots-identifying-paths-for-service-inclusion (news item summarising the workshop)
Additional information	A workshop for pilot representatives to present their progress and use case scenarios, and for the services team to identify how to respond to these needs.
Event #7	
Event type	Conference
Name	GraspOS Final Conference
Date	12-13 November 2025
Venue	Pisa, Italy
Title	Opening Research Assessment
Speakers	N/A
Audience	GraspOS project stakeholders
Outreach	N/A
Materials	N/A
Additional information	The Final Conference will be held in the last months of the project, therefore no reporting information is available yet. Information regarding the organisation of this final event is provided below.

The Final Conference of the project is organised and hosted by CNR and will take place at the CNR Area della Ricerca, in Pisa, Italy from 12-13 November 2025.

To prepare this final event, a dedicated website page was created in M28 to host all the information about the conference³⁸, including the programme, the call for poster contributions, the registration link, the location and the scientific committee. Following the digital strategy established within the project, such information was shared across all social media channels in a regular communication effort.

To maximise outreach, project partners contributed to sharing ready made information from WP6 towards their networks and mailing lists, ensuring that the main announcements (Save the date, Call for Posters, Programme, Registration open, Keynote speakers) also reached

³⁸ <https://graspos.eu/graspos-conference-2025>

wider audiences. To help coordinate and track these efforts, a shared spreadsheet was used to record dissemination activities carried out by project partners.

A promotion campaign was also set up, with a dedicated visual identity for the Conference designed to align with GraspOS branding. Examples of visuals declined for various platforms are provided in the figures below.

Figure 10. Save the date banner for the Opening Research Assessment Conference website

Figure 11. Save the date visual for the opening Research Assessment Conference social media post

Figure 12. Call for posters visual for the Opening Research Assessment Conference

Figure 13. Registration is open visual for the Opening Research Assessment Conference

Figure 14. Keynote speaker announcement 1 for the Opening Research Assessment Conference

Figure 15. Keynote speaker announcement 2 for the Opening Research Assessment Conference

3.4.2 Participation to external events

Project partners attended external events, including conferences and workshops addressing topics related to research careers and incentives, research assessment of Open Science and EOSC related events. To facilitate reporting, these events were classified into four types: Virtual event, International event, National/local event, Organisation meeting.

The table below provides summarised information about participation to external events for each reporting period (RP), with the estimated outreach (provided by the partners attending the events). Information about the specific events attended since the beginning of the project is provided in Annex 6. Participation in external events.

Table 8. GraspOS Participation in external events

	RP1	RP2	RP3 (only M25-M31)	RP1-RP3
Virtual events	3	4	1	8
International events	11	18	5	34
National/local events	4	4	2	10
Organisation meetings	4	5	3	12
Total number of events	22	31	11	64
Overall estimated outreach	1280	2353	2489	6122

3.5 Publications

The project initially aimed to publish at least four research outputs such as scientific articles, and conference proceedings published in OA journals and platforms and/or stored in OA repositories, with the aim to ensure wide dissemination, long-term availability and preservation of GraspOS outputs.

11 peer-reviewed publications have been published since the beginning of the project. They are all available from the Publications section³⁹ of the GraspOS website.

1. Kallipoliti M., Chatzopoulos S., Baglioni M., Adamidi E., Koloveas P., Vergoulis T. (2025). **From raw affiliations to organization identifiers**. In: Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2025). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.07577> (preprint, to be presented at TPDL 2025 in September)

³⁹ <https://graspos.eu/publications>

2. Koloveas P., Chatzopoulos S., Vergoulis T., Tryfonopoulos C. (2025). **Can LLMs Predict Citation Intent? An Experimental Analysis of In-context Learning and Fine-tuning on Open LLMs.** In: Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2025). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.14561> (preprint - to be presented at TPDL 2025 in September)
3. Provost L., Xenou Z. (2025). **Reframing Research Assessment: towards a comprehensive framework for Researcher Profiles.** In: fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation 57, e1, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2025.693>
4. Ivan Heibi, I., Moretti, A., Peroni, S., Soricetti, M. (2024). **The OpenCitations Index: description of a database providing open citation data.** In: Scientometrics 129, 7923–7942. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11192-024-05160-7>
5. Corcho, O., Ekaputra, F. J., Heibi, I., Jonquet, C., Micsik, A., Peroni, S., & Storti, E. (2024). **A maturity model for catalogues of semantic artefacts.** In: Sci Data 11, 479. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4>. Also available in Open Access at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.06746>
6. Rizzetto, E., Peroni, S. (2024). **Mapping bibliographic metadata collections: the case of OpenCitations Meta and OpenAlex.** In: CEUR Wokshop Proceedings, vol 3643, 20th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science (IRCDL 2024), Bressanone, Italy. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3643/paper15.pdf>. Also available in Open Access at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.16523>.
7. Massari, A., Mariani, F., Heibi, I., Peroni, S., Shotton, D. (2024). **OpenCitations Meta.** In : Quantitative Science Studies 1-26. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292. Also available in Open Access at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.16191>.
8. Moretti, A., Soricetti, M., Heibi, I., Massari, A., Peroni, S., & Rizzetto, E. (2024). **The Integration of the Japan Link Center's Bibliographic Data into OpenCitations - The production of bibliographic and citation data structured according to the OpenCitations Data Model, originating from an Anglo-Japanese dataset.** In: Journal of Open Humanities Data, 10(1), p. 21. <https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/articles/10.5334/johd.178>
9. Koloveas, P., Chatzopoulos, S., Tryfonopoulos, C., Vergoulis, T. (2023). **BIP! NDR (NoDoiRefs): A Dataset of Citations from Papers Without DOIs in Computer Science Conferences and Workshops.** In: Alonso, O., Cousijn, H., Silvello, G., Marrero, M., Teixeira Lopes, C., Marchesin, S. (eds) Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries. TPDL 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14241. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43849-3_9. Also available in Open Access at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.12794>.
10. Chatzopoulos, S., Vichos, K., Kanellos, I., Vergoulis, T. (2023). **Piloting Topic-Aware Research Impact Assessment Features in BIP! Services.** In: Pesquita, C., et al. The Semantic Web: ESWC 2023 Satellite Events. ESWC 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 13998. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43458-7_15. Also available in Open Access at <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.06047>.

11. Santos, E.A.d., Peroni, S. and Mucheroni, M.L. (2023). **An analysis of citing and referencing habits across all scholarly disciplines: approaches and trends in bibliographic referencing and citing practices.** In: Journal of Documentation, Vol. 79 No. 7, pp. 196-224. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-10-2022-0234>. Also available in Open Access at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.08469>.

Blog posts and media articles written by GraspOS partners were also made available on the website, in the section 'Publications'. They are listed below:

1. [Scientific papers are not just the number of papers and citations](#), Đorđević, A., Savić, S., Pozitron - 32. University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry, 32, 18-18, March 2024 (In Serbian)
2. [Toward open research information - Introducing the Information & Openness focal area at CWTS](#), Anli, Z., Tatum, C., Waltman, L., [Leiden Madtrics](#), January 2024.
3. [Don't forget the social dimension of research evaluation](#), Amanatidis, A., Provost, L., Research Europe (print edition), January 2024.
4. [Community discussion on Research Assessment Reform in Social Sciences and Humanities](#), Delmazo C., [OPERAS blog](#), December 2023.
5. [Engaging with research communities to advance research assessment](#), Provost, L., [Italian Open Science Portal](#), December 2023 (in Italian).
6. [Research\(er\) assessment that considers Open Science](#), Amanatidis, A., [Leiden Madtrics](#), September 2023.
7. [GraspOS: Responsible assessment of scientific research and Open Science](#), Djordjevic, A., [Pozitron](#) (pages 60-61), August 2023 (in Serbian).

3.6 Community of Practice

A GraspOS Community of practice (CoP) was set up in M6 and officially kicked off in M9. The CoP sought to bring together actors involved in Open Science practices and in developing new recognition and reward systems. Diverse groups of actors involved in the design, development, testing and validation of the infrastructure were invited to participate in it. A total of 10 CoP sessions were held until summer 2025; a final CoP session with DORA representatives is planned in November 2025 to invite participants to continue their exchanges at the DORA CoP (see Table 9 below).

Initially, the CoP intended to focus on discussing the challenges and opportunities the 9 pilot studies being carried out encountered when co-designing, validating and evaluating Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools, and services. In its initial setup, one of the aims was to collect requirements for GraspOS tools and services for evaluation of Open Science and insights from the different communities engaged in RRA.

The first session was an introduction to the project and its aims. The following five sessions focused on specific pilots, to reflect on how research assessments can consider open science in a responsible way through engagement of different epistemic communities. The RP1 review (M16-18) noted the setup of the CoP seemed fragile and called for revisiting the strategy. Following this, the CoP strategy was updated (M19-21): a new organiser was appointed and the number of participants of past sessions was made available on the website. Further, the original aims of collecting requirements and insights were pursued through internal workshops as these allowed for a more targeted discussion around specific challenges encountered by the pilots.

In late 2024, following discussions with the team, the format of the CoP was changed. Rather than focusing on a particular pilot, the CoP sessions sought to focus on current developments related to Open Science-aware RRA indicators, tools, and services. This change allowed us to present panels and discussions that included external as well as internal speakers who shared their insights on the challenges and opportunities of assessing Open Science. The sessions served as community-building events that allowed RRA and OS practitioners to exchange experiences, and generated Q&As between the speakers and the audience.

The sessions were advertised through GraspOS' newsletter, website, and social media channels. The slides and community notes from each session have been made available in the Zenodo community "GraspOS" and are linked on the dedicated page of the project website.

Table 9. Community of Practice events

CoP #1	
Date	18 October 2023
Speaker	Ludo Waltman (CWTS)
Why	Kick off of the GraspOS CoP, conceptual issues of the project were presented.
Audience	45
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10276720
CoP #2	
Date	17 January 2024
Speaker	Fotis Mystakopoulos (OPERAS)
Why	Open Science and research assessment in Social Sciences and Humanities.
Audience	48
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10562682

CoP #3	
Date	20 March 2024
Speaker	Laurent Romary (Inria)
Why	Open Science and research assessment in Computer Science.
Audience	29
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11047836
CoP #4	
Date	15 May 2024
Speaker	Anestis Amanatidis (Utrecht University)
Why	Assessing Open Science values at Utrecht University
Audience	39
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11236219
CoP #5	
Date	10 July 2024
Speaker	Odile Hologne (INRAE)
Why	Open Science and responsible research assessment at INRAE
Audience	12
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12705979
CoP #6	
Date	11 September 2024
Speakers	Ioana Spanache (UEFISCDI), Alina Irimia (UEFISCDI)
Why	The viability of the openness researcher profile: insights from the pilot study at UEFISCDI
Audience	30
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13798738
CoP #7	

Date	13 November 2024
Speakers	Bianca Kramer (Barcelona Declaration), Thanasis Vergoulis (Athena Research Center), Janne Pölönen (CoARA)
Why	The Barcelona Declaration and openness of research information as a prerequisite for research assessment reform
Audience	71
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14218174
CoP #8	
Date	22 January 2025
Speakers	Rita Morais (European University Association), Biljana Kosanović (University of Belgrade), Ana Đorđević (University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry), and Nicolas Fressengeas (University of Lorraine)
Why	Monitoring Open Science at university level for research assessment
Audience	90
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14745700
CoP #9	
Date	12 March 2025
Speakers	Clifford Tatum, chair (CWTS / GraspOS) Laura Himanen (CSC / GraspOS) Panelists: Karen Stroobants (CoARA) Gareth O'Neill (Technopolis Group / OPUS) James Morris (Science Europe) Sarah de Rijcke (Leiden University)
Why	Exploring the Context dimension of Responsible Research Assessment
Audience	42
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15058162
CoP #10	
Date	11 June 2025
Speakers	Elizabeth Gadd (INORMS, CoARA) & Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE)

Why	Assessing open science: opportunities & challenges
Audience	49
Materials	DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15729828
CoP #11	
Date	19 November 2025
Speaker	Giovanna Lima (DORA)
Why	Connections between Responsible Research Assessment and the scholarly publishing reform
Audience	N/A
Materials	N/A

3.7 Training and Webinars

To support pilot participants and external stakeholders in effectively engaging with the tools and services developed in the project, a series of twelve events are being produced. So far, five webinars and five training sessions have already taken place, with one additional webinar and one more training session scheduled for September. All training materials are available on the OpenAIRE YouTube channel and are actively disseminated through GraspOS online channels to ensure broad accessibility.

In parallel, a dedicated course is currently being developed using Articulate and will be hosted on the OpenPlato platform. The course is designed to offer a comprehensive introduction and practical guidance, and it is planned for release at the end of the project.

More details on these activities can be found in Deliverable 6.3 Report on C/D/E, community engagement, and training activities ([10.5281/zenodo.10475613](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10475613)).

The GraspOS training and webinars strategy is being updated, carried out by OpenAIRE in this document: [W Strategy for planning, promotion and dissemination of events.docx](#). In particular, the improved strategy includes stronger involvement from Consortium members in sharing invitations to GraspOS trainings and webinars to the networks they informed in the [Dissemination Channels spreadsheet](#). This procedure should enable task leaders to measure the estimated outreach of dissemination activities in this task.

As part of our training and capacity-building efforts, we have successfully organized five training sessions to date, reaching a total of 216 participants. These sessions have been

delivered online to reduce logistical costs and enhance accessibility for participants across various regions. Led by subject-matter experts, the training provided practical insights and hands-on guidance. A sixth and final training session is currently being planned and will be delivered before the end of the project, further advancing stakeholder competence and collaboration.

Table 10. GraspOS Training events

Title	Date	Speaker, Moderator	Description	Audience	Link to materials
GraspOS training BIP! Scholar	2 November 2023	Thanasis Vergoulis (Athena Research Center), Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE) (moderator)	This training event aims to introduce the audience to the main functionalities of BIP! Scholar, a service that offers researchers the opportunity to set up academic profiles that summarize their research careers.	50 participants, 70 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material
GraspOS training Indicators for Institutions	19 December 2023	Leonidas Pispiringas (Athena Research Center). Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE) (moderator)	This training event equips participants with the skills to navigate the institutional dashboard, interpret OA metrics, and identify collaboration patterns to assess their institution's research landscape. Attendees will learn to apply these insights for strategic decision-making and evaluating the impact of institutional research.	35 participants, 78 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material
GraspOS training Citations and their meaning - or why we cite	23 July 2024	Silvio Peroni (University of Bologna), Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE) (moderator)	This training session shed light on the various dynamics behind citations. Ontological models for the characterisation of citations were presented, along with the fundamentals for using a tool to infer citation characterisation.	40 participants, 100 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material

<p>GraspOS training Leveraging OPERAS Metrics: showing the impact of OA books</p>	<p>26 November 2024</p>	<p>Fotis Mystakopoulos (OPERAS), Carol Delmazo (OPERAS), Maxim Kupreyev (OPERAS), Rowan Hatherley (Ubiquity Press), Cristian Garcia (Ubiquity Press), Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE) (moderator)</p>	<p>The training session provided an overview of the key features of OPERAS Metrics and its role in research assessment, emphasizing its alignment with the open science practices of the GraspOS project.</p>	<p>54 participants, 117 registrations</p>	<p>https://graspOS.eu/training-material</p>
<p>Achieving Metadata Excellence, from compliance to FAIRness: The OpenAIRE Metadata Validator</p>	<p>1 July 2025</p>	<p>Leonidas Pispingas (OpenAIRE), Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE) (moderator)</p>	<p>The training session focused on the OpenAIRE Metadata Validator and how it can help improve the metadata quality, openness, FAIRness and interoperability.</p>	<p>37 participants, 67 registrations</p>	<p>https://graspOS.eu/training-material</p>

In the framework of our outreach and skill-development efforts, we have successfully conducted five webinars to date, as detailed in the table below, with a total of 386 participants. These webinars have been delivered in an online format to reduce costs and enable broader participation across regions. Renowned experts from the field have been invited to lead the sessions, ensuring high-quality content and valuable insights for attendees. They also inform participants about a wide range of tools and capabilities related to research assessment trends and promote approaches for fair and transparent evaluation. We are preparing to hold one more webinar before the end of the project to continue strengthening stakeholder engagement and knowledge sharing.

Table 11. GraspOS Webinars

Title	Date	Speaker, Moderator	Description	Audience	Link to materials
GraspOS webinar Open Science Assessment Framework	7 March 2024	Clifford Tatum (CWTS), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Lottie Provost (CNR) (moderator)	This webinar focused on the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) developed in GraspOS. The OSAF is one of the main outcomes of the project. It aims to assist research funding and performing organisations in tailoring and implementing new generation, Open Science aware Responsible Research Assessment approaches.	76 participants, 141 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material
GraspOS webinar Assessing OA Books: Shedding Light on Peer Review with PRISM	14 May 2024	Carol Delmazo (OPERAS), Fotis Mystakopoulos (OPERAS), Ronald Snijder (OAPEN Foundation), Lottie Provost (CNR) (moderator)	The webinar presented the Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM) and discussed how it can be used in research assessment.	69 participants, 134 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material
PEP-CV- Peer Mentoring and Narrative CVs: A New Paradigm in Academic Recognition	11 February 2025	Sean Sapcariu (PEP-CV), Pooja Khurana (PEP-CV), Angeliki Tzouganatou (OpenAIRE) moderator	This webinar focused on the growing importance of narrative CVs in reshaping research culture and presented the Peer Exchange Platform for Narrative-style CVs (PEP-CV), an innovative peer mentoring platform designed to tackle	95 participants 164 registrations	https://graspos.eu/training-material

			challenges in current assessment systems.		
OpenAIRE Graph New APIs	29 April 2025	Thanasis Vergoulis (Athena Research Center) Alane Brunschweiler (OpenAIRE) moderator	Explore the enhanced OpenAIRE Graph API! Designed to support bibliometric analyses, research discovery, and Open Science monitoring, the new API offers streamlined access to OpenAIRE's rich research data ecosystem.	66 participants 144 registrations	OpenAIRE Graph - Training Resources
Research Assessment in Transition: Open Infrastructures, Policy, and Diamond OA	22 May 2025	Janne Pölönen (GraspOS), Thanasis Vergoulis (GraspOS), Leonidas Pispiringas (CRAFT-OA), Iryna Kuchma (DIAMAS), Milica Ševkušić (DIAMAS) Fotis Mystakopoulos (OPERAS), Zenia Xenou (OpenAIRE)	The session focused on how Diamond OA publishing and open infrastructures interact with ongoing reform efforts in research evaluation, highlighting both the opportunities and challenges of aligning non-profit publishing with emerging assessment models.	80 participants 145 registrants	https://graspOS.eu/training-material

All webinar sessions were recorded and uploaded to the OpenAIRE YouTube channel on a dedicated playlist for GraspOS training and webinars. You can find all the recordings at the following link:

<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL0c4IRNUxuKf73fGnsfSMO9DKCFT-YZR1&si=YJzpNctLCLt5ZYgB>

In addition, all presentation materials from both the webinars and training sessions have been made openly available to the community via Zenodo. These resources ensure continued access to the content for those who could not attend live and support ongoing learning and reference. You can find all the materials at the following link: [Search GraspOS](#)

3.8 Success stories

Each pilot is expected to produce a “success” story to promote the results of the pilot, and to share relevant experience learnt from the piloting activity. The stories will be used to inform and encourage new stakeholders with similar needs who are aiming to reform their research assessment practices. The success stories will be published on the GraspOS website and disseminated through the GraspOS online channels by M35. These will be written in the style of the Research and Innovation Projects Success stories page of the European Commission⁴⁰ and published as a collection of stories from the GraspOS Pilots.

As of 31 July, all the pilots have already provided the draft content for their story, and an example story has been set up based on the CSC pilot, it is provided in Annex 7. CSC Pilot story.

The objective is to create a short, narrative, story for each Pilot to account for the work carried out in the 2.5 past years. The stories will be included in a Booklet to be published towards the end of the project, and will feature for each pilot: an overview of the pilot, issues addressed by the pilot and specific outcomes that can be useful to stakeholders with similar needs.

3.9 Final Brief

A final brief will be produced by the project at M34 with guidelines and lessons learnt to be left as legacy to future initiatives and also to relevant stakeholders. The document will be shared in the form of a concise report and disseminated through all of GraspOS channels as a final output.

The final brief will provide a comprehensive overview of GraspOS, and of the community needs addressed by the project, such as reforming research assessment practices, enabling qualitative assessment through new data and interoperable tools, fostering trust in open data and services, and improving discoverability of resources to facilitate Open Science-aware RRA practices.

Key results will be presented, including the SCOPE+i Framework, the Open and Federated Infrastructure, and the training series to support adoption of RRA best practices, which will be available via the Open Plato platform. The report will also address community engagement, focusing on the main activities of the GraspOS Community of Practice and the nine Pilot studies, in order to shed light on a set of lessons that will serve as a legacy for the project.

Finally, the final brief will include policy recommendations that are aligned with the EOSC policy narrative ([EOSC Tripartite Governance, 2025](#)), and which draw from CoARA Working Groups and related projects’ outputs (including but not limited to PathOS, OPUS, and Scilake), offering guidance for advancing Open Science and RRA adoption in the European Research Area.

⁴⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories>

4. Communication and collaboration with GraspOS partners and related initiatives

Throughout the project, GraspOS actively aligned its communication and engagement activities with those of its partners, related infrastructures, and ongoing initiatives in the broader research assessment and Open Science landscape. This alignment has been carried out through a coordinated online and social media strategy, based on mutual collaboration and the reciprocal sharing of relevant updates, tools, events, and results.

Since January 2023, members of Work Package 6 (WP6) have participated in the EOSC Association Working Group on Communication and Engagement for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects (EOSC-A C&E WG). This involvement has supported the alignment of communication strategies, enables knowledge exchange, and fostered collaborative opportunities across projects with overlapping goals.

GraspOS has also established meaningful collaborations with a number of key initiatives, ensuring both strategic alignment and targeted dissemination of complementary work. In particular, 6 areas of mutual relevance were identified: Infrastructure, Policy, Datasets, Theoretical Framework for Open Science-aware RRA, Tools and services, and Diamond publishing. These are illustrated in Figure 16 below. Additional information on each collaboration can be found in the dedicated section of the website “Collaborations”⁴¹ where details on specific joint activities are provided.

⁴¹ <https://graspos.eu/collaborations>

Figure 16 - Collaboration with external projects and initiatives

Below are highlights of these collaborations:

- OPUS Project: Joint coordination aims to avoid duplication and identify synergies, particularly in adapting the OPUS Research Assessment Framework for integration within GraspOS services.
- PathOS Project: Shared focus on measuring the impact of Open Science. GraspOS benefits from PathOS recommendations to better detect and track impact indicators through its tools and services.
- FAIRCORE4EOSC Project: Joint dissemination efforts and technical collaboration, particularly in adapting the RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) service for integration into GraspOS assessment workflows.
- SciLake Project: Shared efforts in developing interoperable knowledge graphs through thematic pilots. The alignment ensures consistency and richness of data to support robust and discipline-specific research assessment indicators.
- CoARA Initiative: Strategic alignment with policy developments on research assessment, especially as they relate to infrastructures, ensuring GraspOS is consistent with evolving best practices.
- EOSC-A C&E WG: Engagement within this group promotes shared visibility among INFRAEOSC projects and has led to joint outputs such as a policy brief.
- Barcelona DORI: Joint alignment on policy directions for infrastructures involved in research assessment.

- DIAMAS & CRAFT-OA: Collaboration focuses on policy alignment and the development of joint reports and recommendations concerning Diamond Open Access publishing.
- OSTRAILS: Collaboration revolves around data quality, FAIR principles, and the development of interoperable indicators for FAIRness, contributing to the robustness of assessment metrics.
- PFASwin: This partnership led to a lecture on responsible research assessment practices focused on the PFAS challenge in Serbia. It also includes the publication of recommendations to inform institutional policy updates, specifically regarding Open Science and recognition systems.

Through these collaborations, the project has not only benefitted from shared resources and expertise but also contributed to a growing ecosystem of mutually reinforcing initiatives in the field of research assessment and Open Science. A poster detailing these collaborations will be presented at the Final Conference of the project, on 12-13 November 2025.

5. Exploitation Plan

The present chapter describes the Final Exploitation Plan of the GraspOS project and outlines the concrete measures undertaken to ensure the long-term sustainability, adoption, and valorisation of the project outcomes. It builds on the initial strategy outlined in the Intermediate Exploitation Plan (D6.2) and integrates feedback received during project reviews, in particular regarding the need for more structured planning of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the definition of market-oriented pathways.

The objective is to provide a comprehensive and updated overview of how GraspOS results—tools, services, and frameworks—can be maintained, integrated, and exploited beyond the end of the project. The document also reflects on the broader policy and infrastructural contributions of GraspOS, including its alignment with emerging European frameworks for responsible research assessment and open science monitoring.

The plan has been informed by several supporting activities, such as the structured characterisation of the project's KERs, the involvement in the Horizon Results Booster programme, and the continuous engagement with stakeholders, including research institutions, funders, and policy actors. These efforts have resulted in the identification of new service opportunities (e.g., the Researcher Profile component), strengthened synergies with initiatives like CoARA, projects like OPUS, SciLake, and PathOS, and laid the foundations for future integration with EOSC infrastructure.

5.1 Methodology

The methodology adopted for the development of this Final Exploitation Plan builds upon the approach initiated in the Intermediate Exploitation Plan (D6.2) and was significantly enhanced through the support of the **Horizon Results Booster (HRB)** Go-to-Market module, which the project joined in early 2025. The objective was to strengthen the strategic exploitation of GraspOS results by identifying the most promising Key Exploitable Results (KERs), refining their value propositions, and aligning them with clear pathways for post-project sustainability and adoption.

The process was structured in four main phases:

1. Identification and Characterisation of KERs

A consolidated list of **KERs** was established through collaboration with Work Package leaders and technical partners. Each KER was then described using a structured **Characterisation Table** developed with guidance from the HRB coach. This included information on:

- The nature of the result (tool, service, framework)
- Target users and beneficiaries
- Value proposition
- Expected benefits and impact
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL) or Service Readiness Level (SRL)
- Intellectual property (IP) and access conditions
- Exploitation owner(s) and stakeholders
- Suggested adoption pathways and business models

This allowed the consortium to prioritise results with high sustainability and reuse potential, and to develop targeted strategies for each.

2. Value Proposition and Market Fit

With the support of the HRB experts, selected KERs underwent a structured value proposition refinement process. This included:

- Definition of the user problem (“job-to-be-done”) and needs
- Analysis of current practices and competing approaches
- Stakeholder mapping
- Validation of assumptions via engagement with early adopters
- Iterative refinement of positioning and key benefits

The HRB sessions also helped shape the strategic alignment of these KERs with emerging European initiatives in research assessment and open science (e.g., CoARA, OPUS).

3. Go-to-Market Strategy and Roadmap Development

Building on the outcomes of the value proposition work, the HRB coach supported the consortium in designing a **preliminary Go-to-Market roadmap**. This roadmap:

- Outlined the main use cases and entry points for stakeholders
- Identified enabling conditions for adoption (e.g., interoperability with existing systems)
- Suggested relevant business and sustainability models (e.g., subscription-based integration in OpenAIRE catalogue and EOSC)
- Provided a structure for communicating value to institutions, funders, and infrastructures

4. Alignment with Policy and Infrastructure Initiatives

The exploitation planning process was complemented by efforts to position GraspOS outcomes within broader **policy and infrastructural frameworks**, including:

- Contribution to the **CoARA Working Group on Open Infrastructures for RRA**
- Synergies with **OPUS, PathOS and SciLake**
- Preparations for integration into EOSC and OpenAIRE catalogue of services

This alignment ensures that exploitation strategies are not only market-oriented but also policy-relevant and community-driven.

5.2 Key Exploitable Results and Value Proposition

The GraspOS project has generated a portfolio of KERs that support the reform of research assessment practices in alignment with Open Science principles. These results include conceptual frameworks, digital services, and training resources designed to meet the needs of diverse stakeholders across institutional, national, and European levels.

Over the course of the project, the set of KERs has evolved through continuous engagement with stakeholders, pilot implementation feedback, and strategic input from the HRB. This process led to a refined KER strategy, which includes:

- the consolidation of the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) into the SCOPE+i Framework;

- the removal of the Community of Practice (CoP) from the KER list due to limited sustainability and ownership conditions;
- the addition of the Researcher Profile service as a new KER, based on strong demand and its high reuse potential.

To ensure structured and stakeholder-centred exploitation, each KER was analysed and developed according to the methodology described in Section 3. The following subsections present:

1. how the KERs were identified and characterised,
2. their value proposition and stakeholder fit,
3. the go-to-market strategy developed through HRB support,
4. and their alignment with broader policy and infrastructure initiatives.

5.2.1 Identification and Characterisation of KERs

At the proposal stage, GraspOS identified four initial Key Exploitable Results (KERs), which reflected both the technical and policy ambitions of the project:

- **KER1 – Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF):** a conceptual guide to operationalise responsible research assessment (RRA) with Open Science as a core value;
- **KER2 – GraspOS Infrastructure:** a technical backbone composed of modular, open services supporting research assessment workflows;
- **KER3 – Training Materials:** educational resources to build capacity for implementing OS-aware RRA approaches;
- **KER4 – Community of Practice (CoP):** a participatory space for institutions and individuals to co-develop practices and share experiences in research assessment.

As the project advanced, this list was critically reassessed based on internal reviews, feedback from pilots, engagement with external stakeholders, and strategic input from HRB programme. This led to a refined and more coherent set of KERs, reflecting actual uptake potential, maturity, and alignment with stakeholder demand.

Three key decisions were made as a result of this process:

1. **Consolidation and rebranding of KER1 into SCOPE+i**
The original framework (OSAF) was rebranded and integrated into the SCOPE+i Framework, combining conceptual resources (templates, guides, checklists) with digital infrastructure components. The updated name reflects alignment with the [SCOPE](#)

[methodology](#) developed by INORMS, while the “+i” signals the added value of infrastructure integration through GraspOS. This framework forms the conceptual and methodological basis for several GraspOS services.

2. **Removal of KER4 – Community of Practice (CoP)**

Although the CoP played an important role during the project in enabling knowledge exchange and stakeholder engagement, it was removed from the final list of KERs. The decision was based on the absence of a sustainable ownership structure and the limited potential for independent exploitation. Nonetheless, the CoP's contributions are documented in the impact narrative of the project, and its legacy will be supported through external partnerships with CoARA, DORA, and EOSC groups.

3. **Addition of a new KER – Researcher Profile**

The **Researcher Profile** emerged as a direct response to pilot feedback and policy trends (e.g. narrative CVs, recognition of Open Science contributions). This service enables structured, machine-readable, and interoperable representation of individual contributions to Open Science. It is technically aligned with the OpenAIRE Graph and other open infrastructures, reuses the framework provided by [OPUS for the researchers assessment](#) and the [Open Science Impact Indicators Handbook](#) by PathOS, and complements the Openness Profile. Given its reuse potential and high stakeholder interest, it was formally included as a new KER.

To reflect the ambition and layered nature of the project, GraspOS adopted a dual exploitation approach that recognises both the strategic and policy-oriented value of the SCOPE+i Framework (KER1) and the operational value of the supporting services (KER2–KER4). While the framework provides conceptual guidance and policy-aligned resources for responsible research assessment (RRA), the services demonstrate how such approaches could be supported in practice through open and interoperable infrastructure components.

Importantly, the project acknowledges that the full implementation of Open Science-aware research assessment practices lies beyond the scope of GraspOS, as it requires broader commitment and action from research institutions, funders, and policy makers. However, by contributing directly to the work of the CoARA Working Group on Open Infrastructures for RRA, and by developing tangible, reusable components aligned with those principles, GraspOS lays the groundwork for future systemic change.

Each result has been characterised to inform targeted adoption scenarios and sustainability strategies, supporting both the conceptual transition and its potential operationalisation across diverse contexts.

The table below provides an overview of the final set of KERs, including resources type (e.g. tools and framework, infrastructure, services, training), ownership, and exploitation status.

Table 12 – Final list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

KER ID	Title	Type	Status	Owner(s)	Main Target Stakeholders
KER1	SCOPE+i Framework	Framework + Tools	Updated	WP2/WP3	Policy makers, institutions
KER2	GraspOS Infrastructure	Infrastructure	Updated	WP3/WP4	Service providers, EOSC, funders
KER3	Training Materials	Learning Resources	Stable	WP6	Research managers, academia
KER4	Researcher Profile	New Service	New	WP3/WP4	Researchers, funders, EOSC

5.2.2 Value Proposition and Market Fit

The GraspOS exploitation strategy was grounded in a stakeholder-centred approach, aimed at ensuring that each Key Exploitable Result (KER) is aligned with actual needs, challenges, and expectations across the research ecosystem. To achieve this, the project applied the methodology provided by the Horizon Results Booster (HRB), making extensive use of the **Value Proposition Canvas**. This tool was employed to systematically capture stakeholder perspectives by mapping **customer jobs, pains, and gains** to corresponding features of each KER. Through this process, we defined the value proposition of each result across three main dimensions:

1. the problem or challenge addressed;
2. the benefits and opportunities generated for stakeholders; and
3. the relevance and alignment with broader RRA priorities.

Figure 17: Value Proposition Canvas

Building on this, the third dimension of the value proposition analysis focused on the **relevance and fit of each KER** within the broader research assessment landscape. To capture this, the project considered three primary stakeholder levels:

- **Institutional** (e.g., universities, research performing organisations): requiring flexible and transparent assessment tools that can be adapted to local disciplinary and organisational contexts.
- **National** (e.g., research funders, evaluation agencies): seeking reliable frameworks and tools to support reforms, harmonisation, and the integration of Open Science criteria.
- **European** (e.g., European Commission, CoARA, EOSC actors): emphasising alignment with policy objectives, interoperability, and the creation of a responsible assessment infrastructure.

For each level, GraspOS identified key goals and “wishes”—such as adaptability, interoperability, evidence-based guidance, and policy relevance—ensuring that each KER responds meaningfully to concrete challenges.

Value Proposition per KER

KER1 – SCOPE+i Framework

The SCOPE+i Framework builds upon the original Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF) introduced at the beginning of the project. While OSAF focused on defining guiding principles for Open Science-aware assessment, SCOPE+i integrates these foundations with actionable process resources and interoperable services, enabling both conceptual clarity and practical implementation support. The SCOPE+i Framework provides a policy-aligned and operational foundation for organisations seeking to transition toward RRA, with a particular emphasis on OS. Co-developed in collaboration with the CoARA Working Group on Open Infrastructures for RRA, the framework responds to the shared needs of both Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), who often struggle with rigid assessment practices, lack of transparency, and the challenge of recognising diverse research contributions.

The framework is composed of two core components:

1. Assessment process resources – A structured set of 16 templates, guides, and checklists that support institutions in designing and documenting their assessment activities. These resources are designed to be flexible and adaptable to different local contexts, and cover all phases of the assessment process, from readiness to evaluation and dissemination.
2. Assessment digital services – Tools that enable the collaborative collection, sharing, and registration of assessment protocols and Open Science contributions. These include the Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) and the Openness Profile, both part of the broader GraspOS infrastructure.

The value proposition of the SCOPE+i Framework lies in its ability to:

- Help institutions define their values, context, and purpose for assessment;
- Provide plug-and-play resources to guide a structured and transparent transition from principles to implementation;
- Facilitate collaborative and inclusive planning, involving multiple stakeholders;
- Ensure interoperability with existing infrastructures such as Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and repositories;
- Reduce complexity and enable reuse of assessment protocols, through tools like the Assessment Protocol Registry.

By integrating these elements into a coherent and extensible framework, SCOPE+i not only supports conceptual alignment with RRA principles but also provides the practical building blocks needed for systemic change. The resources and services developed have been tested

through pilots and aligned with broader European policy developments, reinforcing their relevance and readiness for uptake.

Table 13: Value Proposition Canvas for the SCOPE+i Framework

<p>Customer Segment: RPOs and RFOs Users: Evaluators, Evaluands, Infrastructure, Policy Makers</p>	<p>Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) are treated similarly when it comes to customer needs. Although they have distinct missions within the academic landscape—RPOs focusing on conducting research and RFOs on funding it—both depend on effective, fair, and forward-looking research assessment to achieve their goals. As a result, they face similar challenges in reforming entrenched assessment systems. In particular, they must contend with the inertia of traditional practices, such as overreliance on journal impact factors or narrow publication metrics, as well as deeply embedded assessment infrastructures.</p> <p>With this in mind, the SCOPE+i Framework was developed as a flexible, interoperable set of assessment resources and digital services. It supports both RPOs and RFOs in adopting more transparent, inclusive, and holistic evaluation approaches aligned with open science principles.</p>
<p>Customer Job</p>	<p>Transition to Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on Open Science</p> <p>Define values and context: Identify and document the organisation’s values, mission, and purpose of the assessment.</p> <p>Assess readiness: Conduct a self-assessment of the organisation’s maturity in relation to RRA and Open Science.</p> <p>Design the protocol: Develop an assessment protocol based on the documented values, context, and purpose.</p> <p>Implement the process:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assemble a peer review committee with an appropriate balance of qualitative and quantitative expertise. Perform the assessment according to the protocol <p>Review and improve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a self-evaluation of the assessment outcomes. Register and share the assessment protocol to ensure transparency and reusability.
<p>Pains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty in developing new assessment practices Resource consuming and complex processes Difficulties of incorporating new kinds of evidence (e.g. Open-Science practices) Lack of structured and reusable assessment process Entrenched assessment practices Embedded assessment infrastructures
<p>Gains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Services to help transition towards RRA, especially recognizing and rewarding open science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> accommodate a diverse range assessment content (beyond publications) interoperable with contemporary infrastructure, such as local CRISs and repositories Process resources to help reduce complexity Increase transparency and inclusivity of assessment process Easy discovery (and reuse) of new RRA and open science practices

<p>Products and Services</p>	<p>SCOPE+i Framework: The GraspOS project has developed tailored infrastructure that works together with the existing SCOPE framework, which is known as the SCOPE+i Framework. This assessment infrastructure consists of two main components: assessment process resources and digital services. The assessment process resources offer guidance for implementing key elements of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), while the assessment digital services enable collaborative collection and sharing of assessment plans and documentation throughout the entire assessment process.</p> <p>In this framework, assessment processes refer to the activities involved in planning and carrying out research assessments. Assessment services refer to digital services aligned with modern interoperability standards for research information systems.</p> <p>SCOPE+i Resources The process resources are focused on operationalizing the transition to RRA. This set of resources are provided in three formats; templates, guides, and checklists. The aim of the full set of sixteen process resources is to support the design and documentation of research assessment events, providing guidance toward operationalizing RRA principles while respecting the flexibility needed to implement in local contexts.</p> <p>SCOPE+i Services The two services are an Assessment Protocol Portfolio for use during the full assessment event and an Openness Profile – a portfolio for making visible contributions to OS. These services are part of the GraspOS Open Infrastructure and are technologically underpinned by the Research Activity Identifier, also known as RAiD. Adaptation of the RAiD for use in research assessment was developed in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.</p> <p>As part of the broader GraspOS infrastructure, the SCOPE+i services offer three key advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative and Inclusive – Open to all assessment participants. • Comprehensive Support – Accommodates all aspects of assessment planning, documentation, and final protocol development. • Interoperable and Extensible – Built on a robust metadata schema and API, enabling direct data transfer to downstream analytic services. Additionally, individual instances of these Assessment Protocol Portfolios and Openness Profiles can be hierarchically linked to each other. <p>Assessment Protocol Portfolio The SCOPE+i Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) supports the planning and documentation of research assessment by serving two key functions: it records the agreed-upon approach for a specific assessment event and provides a means to register the assessment protocol after the event concludes. It acts as a shared resource for conducting the assessment and documenting its outcomes.</p>
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	<p>An APP is a collaborative, multi-actor digital object that brings together essential information for assessment planning—such as a readiness self-assessment, values statement, and purpose statement—along with the assessment protocol that outlines the assessment approach.</p> <p>During the assessment, the portfolio is accessible ("locally open") to all participants involved in the event. It can also be made publicly available afterward, balancing transparency with the need for privacy during the process. This approach ensures consistency and clarity for both evaluators and those being assessed, while protecting sensitive information during the event.</p> <p>After the assessment concludes, the APP can be archived for historical reference. Additionally, the assessment protocol itself—separate from any privacy-related content—can be published in the Assessment Protocols Registry. This allows the broader community to learn from the protocol's design in relation to its local context and stated purpose.</p> <p>The Assessment Protocols Registry serves as a shared knowledge base to inform and inspire the design of future assessment events.</p>
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating online, collaborative collection of and sharing of assessment plans and agreed evidence • Searchable Community Resources and protocols • Researchers making visible their contributions to Open Science
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plug and Play Resources (digital, living documents) guiding a structured transition from RRA principles into practical solutions • Transparent and reusable assessment protocol • Interoperability with local infrastructure

KER2 – GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure

The GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure is a federated, modular, and open ecosystem designed to support Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) practices aligned with Open Science principles. It enables the discoverability, interoperability, and integration of diverse assessment tools, data sources, services, and indicators.

The infrastructure targets multiple stakeholder groups—researchers, research performing organisations (RPOs), funding agencies (RFOs), and bibliometricians—each with distinct but converging needs around transparency, accountability, and contextual evaluation of research activities.

For researchers, the infrastructure simplifies the creation and curation of academic profiles that include both quantitative and qualitative contributions, particularly those aligned with Open Science. It supports automatic data ingestion (e.g., from ORCID, OpenAIRE Graph), offers narrative and discipline-sensitive templates, and streamlines the visibility and reuse of research contributions beyond publications.

For RPOs, it reduces reliance on traditional metrics by enabling the development of data-driven, Open Science-aware assessment frameworks. Dashboards, indicators, and reusable protocol components allow for flexible yet standardised approaches across departments and disciplines.

For RFOs, the infrastructure offers tools to support consistent evaluation and monitoring of funded research. It includes automated tracking of project outputs, integration of Open Science indicators, and APIs for cross-programme analysis—facilitating more responsible, comparable, and evidence-based funding decisions.

For bibliometricians, GraspOS provides a transparent, interoperable environment for responsible impact analysis. It integrates open and harmonised metadata across publications, datasets, software, and projects, enabling reproducible workflows and alternative metrics beyond citations.

Across all use cases, the infrastructure delivers:

- EOSC integration for broader discoverability and sustainability;
- Standardised APIs for seamless integration with existing research information systems;
- Open-source components and transparent governance;
- Reduced administrative burden and increased cost-efficiency through automation and reuse;
- Support for reproducibility and benchmarking across disciplines.

By aligning policy aspirations with technical implementation, the GraspOS infrastructure fills a critical gap in the current RRA landscape, enabling stakeholders to adopt scalable, responsible, and Open Science-aligned assessment practices. To ensure clarity and impact, the Value Proposition results for KER2 are presented separately for each main stakeholder group—researchers, research performing organisations (RPOs), research funding organisations (RFOs), and bibliometricians—reflecting their specific needs and the tailored benefits that the infrastructure delivers to each of them.

Table 14: Value Proposition Canvas for KER-2 GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure.

<p>Customer Researchers (domain-agnostic) Users: researchers across disciplines and career stages</p>	<p>Segment: Researchers, regardless of their discipline, career stage, or institutional affiliation, face growing pressure to make their contributions visible, beyond traditional publication records. They are increasingly expected to demonstrate their impact across a broader range of dimensions, including Open Science practices, data sharing, societal engagement, and interdisciplinary collaboration. However, most existing academic profile tools focus on bibliometric outputs and offer limited flexibility or personalisation.</p> <p>In this context, researchers often struggle with fragmented systems, manual processes, and lack of interoperability. They must navigate multiple platforms to build and maintain their CVs, often with limited options for integrating qualitative narratives or Open Science contributions in a coherent, standardised format. This complexity makes it difficult for them to curate profiles that fully represent their research activity and values.</p> <p>The GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure addresses these challenges by offering a user-friendly, interoperable, and Open Science-oriented platform that allows researchers to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build and publish structured profiles, including narrative CVs, quantitative and qualitative indicators; • Integrate data from multiple sources (e.g., ORCID, OpenAIRE Graph);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight contributions to Open Science through dedicated sections and templates; • Customise their profile based on disciplinary needs and intended use (e.g., funding application, hiring, evaluation). <p>This enables a more inclusive and contextualised representation of research careers, aligned with emerging practices in responsible assessment and Open Science policy frameworks (e.g., CoARA, DORA).</p>
<p>Customer Job</p>	<p>Researchers are increasingly expected to document and communicate their contributions in ways that go beyond traditional publication lists. In this context, they must:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect and maintain a comprehensive track record of their research activities, including outputs beyond publications (e.g., datasets, software, societal impact); • Share their research progress with others, both manually and through dedicated platforms or automated systems; • Understand and apply qualitative and quantitative indicators to evaluate their own research performance, moving beyond citation metrics; • Curate structured, narrative-based academic profiles that reflect the diversity of their work; • Integrate Open Science principles—such as openness, collaboration, and transparency—into their research practice and professional record. <p>These needs reflect a shift toward more holistic and inclusive recognition of research contributions, requiring infrastructure that supports dynamic, researcher-centred representation.</p>
<p>Pains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The process is often time- and resource-intensive, especially when updating and maintaining data across systems; • It is difficult to track research activities beyond publications, due to the lack of integrated, automated tools and standardised infrastructures; • Researchers are forced to rely on multiple, disconnected platforms (e.g. for indicators, datasets, narrative content, updates), increasing cognitive and operational burden;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is limited guidance or tooling to support the calculation of research impact in a way that reflects Open Science principles, making it challenging to align profile content with evolving assessment practices.
<p>Gains</p>	<p>Researchers benefit from solutions that simplify the creation and dissemination of academic profiles while increasing the visibility and accessibility of their contributions. Desired outcomes include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to share tailored academic profiles adapted to different purposes—such as job applications, grant proposals, or institutional evaluations; • Access to a centralised platform where their diverse research contributions (e.g., publications, datasets, software, Open Science practices) can be compiled, managed, and discovered; • Enhanced visibility and recognition of their research activity, including outputs and efforts that are often overlooked by traditional metrics and fragmented systems.

<p>Products and Services</p>	<p>The GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure provides researchers with access to a set of interoperable, customisable, and Open Science-aligned tools and services that support the creation, curation, and sharing of academic profiles. Key components include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Federated Infrastructure: An open environment where researchers can access interoperable academic profile services integrated across institutions and platforms. ● Data Registry: A catalogue of metadata-rich datasets relevant for research assessment, ensuring discoverability and reuse in profile building and impact demonstration. ● Tools Catalogue: A curated collection of software tools supporting profile generation, narrative CV formatting, indicator selection, and evaluation use cases. ● Services Catalogue: A registry of remote services accessible via web interfaces and APIs, offering advanced functionalities such as indicator calculation, profile export, and EOSC-aligned integration. ● Data Interoperability and Access Layer (DIAL): A backend component ensuring data harmonisation across sources (e.g. ORCID, OpenAIRE Graph, institutional CRIS), following RDA standards to support seamless information flow. ● Infrastructure Front-End: A user-friendly interface (based on Docusaurus) that allows researchers to browse, select, and interact with the available components, without requiring technical expertise.
<p>Gain Creators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support for profile customisation: Researchers can generate academic and non-academic profiles in different formats, tailored to specific use cases such as job applications, project reporting, or institutional evaluations. ● Streamlined updating through automation: Integration with data sources such as OpenAIRE Graph and ORCID enables automatic ingestion and update of records, saving time and reducing manual effort. ● Access to complementary resources: The platform facilitates discovery and integration of previously untracked research

	contributions, including software, datasets, and Open Science activities, improving completeness and visibility.
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A user-friendly front-end, designed for seamless navigation and intuitive discovery of relevant tools, data, and services—lowering the technical entry barrier for researchers with limited time or resources. • Centralised access to a wide range of resources—including indicators, datasets, services, and templates—consolidated into a single, interoperable platform, reducing the need to switch between fragmented systems. • A powerful and inclusive academic profile environment, which supports the integration of both quantitative and qualitative contributions, enabling researchers to present their work in a more holistic and meaningful way.

<p>Customer Segment: Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)</p> <p>Users: policy makers at university level, research admins, and research supporting staff</p>	<p>RPOs—such as universities and research institutes—are under increasing pressure to evaluate research in a way that reflects Open Science principles. They must move beyond traditional metrics, integrate diverse contributions (e.g. datasets, software), and ensure transparency in assessment processes.</p>
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	<p>GraspOS supports RPOs with interoperable tools, standardised APIs, and reusable resources that enable responsible, efficient, and policy-aligned evaluation workflows across the institution.</p>
Customer Job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the performance of research activities and researchers in a responsible way that considers Open Science. • Collect and analyse research activity information from various internal and external sources. • Implement Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) methodologies aligned with Open Science, combining qualitative and quantitative indicators.
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional research metrics (e.g., journal impact factor) introduce biases and fail to recognise important aspects of research contributions. • The process is complex due to the lack of standardised Open Science-aware tools. • Difficulty integrating multiple data sources for comprehensive research evaluation. • High administrative burden in assessment and reporting processes.
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability between assessment systems and research information management infrastructures. • Greater transparency in research assessment through standardised, Open Science-aware methodologies. • Time and cost savings in implementing and maintaining research evaluation workflows.

Products and Services

- GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure that supports discovery and integration of **customisable data, tools, and services** for Open Science-aware assessment.
- EOSC-aligned platform for wide accessibility and interoperability.
- Metadata management via registries, catalogues, and APIs.

Gain Creators

- **Transparent assessment workflows** supported by open-source tooling.
- **Customised access to assessment resources** through a unified online platform.
- Supports responsible evaluation with reproducible, Open Science-aligned metrics and frameworks.

Pain Relievers

- Standardised APIs that enable **interoperability across diverse data sources** and facilitate metadata ingestion.
- EOSC integration ensures **alignment with European infrastructures**.
- Enhanced **transparency and traceability** in the assessment process.

Customer Segment: Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

Users: Programme officers, evaluation panels, policy makers, research strategists

Research Funding Organisations—whether public agencies, philanthropic bodies, or private foundations—play a central role in shaping research agendas and incentivising practices aligned with broader societal goals. In recent years, RFOs have come under increasing pressure to move beyond narrow, publication-based metrics and adopt **responsible, transparent, and Open Science-aware** approaches to evaluating funded research.

These organisations operate in a **high-stakes and resource-constrained environment**, where they must demonstrate the **impact, fairness, and accountability** of their funding decisions. Yet, many still rely on fragmented data sources and outdated evaluation models, which often fail to reflect the diversity of research contributions and the real-world effects of funded projects.

RFOs therefore need:

- **Reliable and standardised indicators** that combine quantitative and qualitative dimensions, including Open Science outputs;
- **Flexible yet consistent methodologies** for assessing projects across disciplines and funding schemes;
- **Tools for monitoring and benchmarking** the progress and impact of funded activities;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data infrastructures that allow real-time tracking, cross-project comparison, and aggregation of evidence. <p>The GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure supports RFOs by providing integrated services, harmonised data pipelines, and dashboards tailored to these needs. This enables them to shift toward policy-aligned, Open Science-compatible assessment strategies, while improving efficiency and transparency across the funding lifecycle.</p>
Customer Job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate funded research impact using both qualitative and quantitative indicators • Ensure transparency and accountability in research funding allocation • Implement responsible funding evaluation aligned with Open Science • Assess projects based on broader impact, not just bibliometrics • Monitor the progress and outputs of funded projects over time • Use insights from evaluation to inform future funding priorities and strategies
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in assessing the impact of research due to the lack of reliable Open Science indicators • Difficulty in benchmarking research outputs across diverse funding programmes • Challenges in integrating Open Science policies into funding strategies • Complex, time- and resource-consuming evaluation processes
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved ability to evaluate impact using mixed indicators • Transparent and consistent evaluation across funding calls • Real-time monitoring of project activities • Enhanced accountability and learning from policy implementation • Support for responsible and Open Science-aware funding allocation

Products and Services

- **GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure** that facilitates discoverability and reuse of data, tools, and services
- Catalogues of **assessment resources** (tools, templates, indicators)
- EOSC-integrated infrastructure for broader visibility and accessibility
- APIs and data access layers for cross-programme interoperability

Gain Creators

- Automates and streamlines **funding assessment workflows**
- Delivers structured methodologies for Open Science-aware evaluation
- Supports better **impact reporting**
- Provides **qualitative + quantitative indicators** tailored to funding agencies
- Improves visibility into funding outcomes through **data aggregation** across projects.

Pain Relievers

- Enables **automated tracking** of research activities across the lifecycle of funded projects
- Dashboards to monitor **uptake of Open Science practices**

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated tools to support transparent, reproducible assessment • Enhances benchmarking and comparability across programmes and disciplines • Reduces costs and complexity through reuse and open solutions
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<p>Customer Segment: Bibliometricians and Research Analysts</p> <p>Users: researchers and data analyst specialised in research on research, metascience, and research assessment</p>	<p>Bibliometricians and research analysts are responsible for evaluating research performance and impact using structured data and indicators. With growing attention to responsible metrics and Open Science practices, they are increasingly expected to move beyond citation-based analyses and incorporate diverse research outputs—such as datasets, software, and societal contributions—into their evaluations.</p> <p>However, they often face fragmented data sources, lack of standardised tools for Open Science-aware analysis, and challenges to reproducibility due to reliance on closed platforms and proprietary systems.</p> <p>The GraspOS infrastructure provides these users with access to open, harmonised, and linked data, reproducible APIs, and</p>
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	workflows that support comprehensive, transparent, and cost-efficient assessment practices across disciplines.
Customer Job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Find and use data, tools, services, and other resources for bibliometric and research assessment analysis Ensure that Open Science aspects relevant to the research under study are considered and measured Ensure the analysis includes a diverse range of research activities, not limited to publications
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional bibliometrics are dominated by citation-based metrics that ignore Open Science and other contribution types High diversity and inconsistency across bibliographic data sources used for analysis Lack of standardised tools to support Open Science-aware metrics Challenges to reproducibility, plus increased costs due to reliance on closed data sources and proprietary software
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunity to analyse diverse aspects of research beyond publications Access to transparent and reproducible workflows for bibliometric and research assessment analysis Greater time and cost efficiency through open, integrated infrastructures and tools

<p>Products and Services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GraspOS Federated Open Infrastructure supporting the discovery and access of data, tools, and services for Open Science-aware assessment • Integrated APIs and catalogues for data, software, and indicators • Research activity linking across publications, data, software, and projects
<p>Gain Creators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of Open Science-aware indicators into bibliometric workflows • Support for reproducible analysis via open APIs and data pipelines • Cross-disciplinary and scalable analysis through linked metadata and research outputs
<p>Pain Relievers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to open and harmonised data sources through a common API specification • User-friendly front-end for seamless discovery of relevant resources

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|--|---|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified metadata access and interoperability across data services |
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KER3 - Training Materials

The training dimension of GraspOS was initially articulated through a series of **webinars** and **hands-on training sessions** designed to accompany the development and deployment of services and tools across the project. Over time, however, this effort evolved into a more strategic and sustainable outcome: the development of a **dedicated course hosted on OpenPlato**, which serves as the main **Key Exploitable Result (KER3)** for capacity building. OpenPlato is a Moodle-based learning platform for Open Science training. It is a free, openly licensed e-learning hub focused on topics such as Open Science, FAIR data, and Research Data Management (RDM), developed and maintained by OpenAIRE. The platform offers a catalogue of courses and resources, supports both self-paced and live learning, and is enriched with structured metadata to ensure long-term discoverability and interoperability.

This OpenPlato course consolidates the knowledge and materials produced by the project's results, offering a structured and modular learning experience. Unlike standalone webinars, the course is specifically tailored to the needs of **target stakeholders identified in KER1 and KER2**—such as research managers, funders, analysts, and institutional administrators. It helps them understand how to integrate GraspOS tools, services, and principles into responsible research assessment practices.

Course Structure and Value

The OpenPlato course is built using Articulate and includes:

- **Curated learning pathways** that align with the roles and needs of RPOs, RFOs, and bibliometricians;
- **Updated, modular content** based on real-world training delivery and participant feedback;
- Embedded materials and demonstrations from live training sessions;
- A foundation in both conceptual frameworks (e.g., SCOPE+i) and technical components (e.g., OpenAIRE Graph APIs, BIP! Scholar, Metadata Validator).

This structure allows the course to act as a **centralised, re-usable knowledge base**, ensuring the longevity and sustainability of GraspOS's capacity-building mission.

From Events to Exploitable Knowledge

Throughout the project, GraspOS delivered targeted training sessions, thematic webinars, and training materials published on Zenodo and [OpenAIRE's YouTube channel](#), ensuring openness and long-term accessibility, as described above in the dedicated sections on Training.

While these activities supported wide dissemination and awareness-raising, it is the OpenPlato course that transforms them into a structured, sustainable, and stakeholder-ready training offer. This ensures that the investment in training becomes a strategic enabler for uptake, adoption, and replication of GraspOS's results across Europe and beyond.

Table 15 – Value Proposition Canvas for KER 3 - Training Material

<p>Customer Segment: Researchers, RPOs, and RFOs Users: all (open course)</p>	<p>These stakeholders require not only tools and frameworks but also training and guidance to apply them effectively in real contexts. The OpenPlato course enables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The stakeholders (Researchers and RPOs) understand how to integrate GraspOS developing tools, services and frameworks • Research managers to understand and implement SCOPE+i; • Funders to align evaluation strategies with Open Science principles
<p>Customer Job</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and implement research assessment procedures aligned with emerging principles of openness, transparency, and inclusivity; • Monitor and evaluate research performance using both quantitative and qualitative indicators;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the transition from traditional metrics to more responsible, context-sensitive evaluation frameworks; • Guide institutional or programme-level decisions based on evidence from Open Science-aware data sources and assessment tools; • Interpret policies and translate them into operational practices, particularly in response to CoARA, DORA, or funder mandates; • Build internal capacity and foster awareness across their organisations about responsible assessment practices and Open Science.
<p>Pains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited time and resources to engage in structured training opportunities • Difficulty translating policy guidelines (e.g., CoARA, DORA) into practical workflows • Fragmented access to relevant tools, data sources, and indicators • Lack of clear, contextualised examples for applying RRA and Open Science in real institutional settings • Uncertainty about how to interpret and implement qualitative indicators or narrative components • Overload of information without guidance on what is most relevant for their role • Insufficient internal capacity to train others or support change across departments • Limited awareness of existing open tools and infrastructures that could support their work
<p>Gains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical understanding of how to implement Open Science-aware assessment strategies • Clear orientation on tools, indicators, and frameworks relevant to their role • Access to curated, modular content tailored to institutional, funder, or analytical contexts • Increased confidence in engaging with emerging policy frameworks • Ability to train others or lead internal change processes based on what they've learned • Time-saving through consolidated and structured learning, instead of scattered materials • Greater capacity to align internal practices with national and European policy expectations • Enhanced readiness to participate in or lead assessment reform initiatives

Products and Services

The primary exploitable output of KER3 is the **GraspOS training course hosted on OpenPlato**, which consolidates, structures, and updates all training and webinar content produced during the project. It serves as a sustainable and centralised resource to support long-term capacity building in Open Science-aware research assessment.

Key products and services include:

- **GraspOS Training Course on OpenPlato**
A modular e-learning course developed using Articulate and hosted on OpenPlato. It offers structured learning paths tailored to different stakeholder roles, combining conceptual overviews with practical guidance and demonstrations.
- **Recorded Webinars and Training Sessions**
A curated set of webinar recordings and interactive training sessions delivered by subject-matter experts, covering tools and services such as BIP! Scholar, OpenAIRE Graph APIs, OPERAS Metrics, and narrative CVs.
- **Open Access to All Materials**
All resources—including slide decks, recordings, and hands-on materials—are published on Zenodo and YouTube, ensuring continued access beyond the end of the project.
- **Stakeholder-Oriented Content Paths**
Learning content is adapted for different target groups (e.g.

	<p>research managers, funders, bibliometricians), providing role-relevant guidance and use cases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical Implementation Resources Case examples, tool walkthroughs, and documentation help users understand how to integrate GraspOS tools and frameworks into real-world assessment contexts. <p>These services collectively provide a reusable and scalable knowledge base to support institutional change, policy implementation, and professional development in research assessment.</p>
<p>Gain Creators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enables users to build confidence in implementing Open Science-aware research assessment Facilitates professional development through structured, credible, and openly accessible training Equips institutions and funders with the knowledge needed to support policy alignment (e.g. CoARA, DORA) Improves internal capacity for reform by training key staff in assessment design and execution Supports interoperability and consistency in assessment practices through shared training standards Enhances stakeholder engagement by providing role-specific pathways that reflect real-world needs Promotes reuse and scalability across organisations, projects, and national contexts
<p>Pain Relievers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centralises scattered training materials into a single, accessible platform Translates complex concepts and policies into clear, practical guidance Provides reusable, ready-to-use content that reduces the need for institutions to develop internal training from scratch Offers on-demand access, removing barriers related to scheduling, location, or availability Adapts learning materials to specific stakeholder roles, avoiding generic or irrelevant training Reduces time spent searching for tools and guidance by consolidating relevant resources and examples Supports autonomous learning and knowledge transfer across teams

KER 4: Researcher Profile

MyResearchFolio is a new pilot service designed to support the shift toward more inclusive, Open Science-aligned, and researcher-centric research assessment. While its current Technology Readiness Level (TRL) remains low—as the service is still in the design phase and scheduled to enter pilot testing in autumn 2025—it responds directly to the needs and expectations expressed by several institutions involved in the GraspOS pilots.

The service builds on the foundations of the Researcher Profile prototype initially developed within GraspOS. MyResearchFolio retains the same vision and technical principles but expands its scope and repositions the profile as a coherent, standalone service, to be maintained and further developed within the OpenAIRE service catalogue. In this sense, the two are not separate outputs, but rather two stages of the same Key Exploitable Result, evolving from internal infrastructure testing to a federated, community-facing pilot.

In particular, many pilot stakeholders expressed a desire to focus not only on the assessment of research outputs, but also on the assessment of researchers as contributors, through richer, more contextualised representations of their work. MyResearchFolio emerges from this shared need, shaped collaboratively within the project as a response to this demand.

Though still under development, the service has been conceived to ensure interoperability with the infrastructure, indicators, and services developed in GraspOS, and is firmly grounded in the project's wider ecosystem of collaborations—with OPUS (evaluation frameworks), SciLake (graph-based infrastructures), and PathOS (policy pathways and behavioural insights).

Purpose and Positioning

MyResearchFolio aims to act as a testbed for alternative researcher evaluation formats, blending narrative CVs and Open Science indicators. Its added value lies in its flexibility, alignment with European policy developments, and its potential to empower institutions and funders to explore new assessment models in real-world settings.

By connecting to the OpenAIRE Graph and integrating indicators on FAIRness, openness, SDG alignment, and responsible data practices, MyResearchFolio aspires to offer a richer, context-aware researcher profile. It complements existing identity systems such as ORCID, allowing researchers to curate and present a more meaningful, policy-relevant view of their career advancements.

Key Characteristics

- **Researcher-focused:** Designed to reflect the needs of individuals, not just institutions or funders.
- **Narrative-driven:** Supports the creation of customisable narrative CVs aligned with Open Science and career diversity.

- **Data-enriched:** Integrates information from the OpenAIRE Graph, ORCID and potentially other trusted sources.
- **Interoperable:** Designed to exchange and align data with ORCID, CRIS systems, and national identifiers.
- **Collaboratively shaped:** The result of cross-project dialogue with OPUS, PathOS, and input from users.
- **Policy-aligned:** Developed in the context of the CoARA Agreement, the OI4RRA Working Group, and the Barcelona Declaration.

From Emerging Need to Design Pilot

While MyResearchFolio is not yet a production-ready service, it constitutes a high-potential outcome of GraspOS. It exemplifies the project's ability to detect, translate, and develop stakeholder needs into explorable, interoperable solutions, and lays the groundwork for future service development within OpenAIRE.

Its classification as a KER reflects its strategic relevance rather than technical maturity: a concrete expression of institutional and policy priorities emerging from the GraspOS community, and a clear candidate for follow-up development and integration.

Table 16: Value Proposition Canvas for the new KER4 on the Researcher Profile (branded as MyResearchFolio).

<p>Customer Segment: Researchers (domain-agnostic)</p>	<p>Researchers are increasingly expected to document, showcase, and evaluate their contributions beyond traditional publications. This includes not only datasets, software, and societal engagement, but also their alignment with Open Science principles such as openness, transparency,</p>

<p>Users: researchers across disciplines and career stages</p>	<p>and collaboration. As research assessment reforms take shape, particularly under the influence of the CoARA Agreement and similar initiatives, researchers are under growing pressure to make these diverse contributions visible in ways that are both structured and meaningful.</p> <p>However, existing academic profiling tools often fall short: they are publication-centric, inflexible, and lack interoperability. Researchers must navigate multiple disconnected platforms to maintain their CVs, manually input redundant information, and often have no space to contextualise their work through narratives or role descriptions. This results in an underrepresentation of their real impact and effort, particularly for early-career researchers and those working in interdisciplinary or community-engaged areas.</p> <p>MyResearchFolio responds to this need by offering a researcher-centred, Open Science-aligned profile service that supports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible and modular CVs (including Narrative CVs) • Integration with existing identifiers like ORCID • Automation of data ingestion from trusted sources (e.g. OpenAIRE Graph) • Templates that reflect domain-specific expectations and Open Science practices <p>In doing so, it empowers researchers to curate richer profiles that reflect the diversity, quality, and societal relevance of their work—supporting more equitable and responsible research assessment practices.</p>
<p>Customer Job</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create CVs and maintain them over time • Showcase contributions beyond publications (e.g. datasets, software, societal engagement) • Showcase Open Science practices and alignment • Produce and structure Narrative CVs • Demonstrate their societal contributions and broader impact • Present the quality and relevance of their work, beyond just output volume
<p>Pains</p>	<p>Existing academic profiling tools often fall short: they are publication-centric, inflexible, and lack interoperability. Researchers must navigate multiple disconnected platforms to maintain their CVs, manually input redundant information, and often have no space to contextualise their work through narratives or role descriptions. This results in an underrepresentation of their real impact and effort, particularly for early-career researchers and those working in interdisciplinary or community-engaged areas.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation based only on publication quantity, ignoring quality

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many contributions remain unacknowledged or invisible • Open Science efforts are overlooked in current CV tools • Lack of descriptive flexibility to explain role in specific contributions • Impact of contributions often unclear or missing • Limited flexibility and no domain-specific templates or structuring options
<p>Gains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase a wide range of contributions, including Open Science activities • Represent contributions in the most appropriate and personalised way • Include narrative descriptions and qualitative context (e.g. roles, effort) • Be evaluated on the basis of quality, relevance, and societal value • Benefit from automated data integration to simplify profile maintenance
<p>The diagram shows a central gift box icon. Three lines radiate from it: one to the top-left labeled 'Products & Services', one to the top-right labeled 'Gain Creators' (with a line graph icon), and one to the bottom-right labeled 'Pain Relievers' (with a pill icon). An arrow points from the gift box to the right.</p>	
<p>Products and Services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic and chronological representation of researcher contributions • Dedicated Open Science contribution page • Integration and sync with ORCID • Ability to add short descriptive texts to contributions

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative CV section (Royal Society 4-module format, and other RFOs/Learning Societies formats to be added) • Profile statistics (quantitative and qualitative indicators) • Data ingestion from OpenAIRE Graph and ORCID • Domain-specific templates and profile customisation
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified and flexible platform for showcasing diverse research outputs • Personalised, quality-oriented CVs combining narratives and metrics • Simplified representation of professional profile aligned with Open Science policies • Promotes holistic and responsible assessment aligned with CoARA and other frameworks
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables researchers to categorise and enrich contributions with descriptions and context • Allows adding new types of contributions, including societal or interdisciplinary work • Open Science practices are explicitly supported and made visible • Facilitates structured profiles adaptable to different disciplines or evaluation formats • Reduces fragmentation and time waste by integrating existing data (ORCID, OpenAIRE).

<p>Customer Segment: Researcher Evaluators in RPOs and RFOs</p> <p>Users: Members of evaluation committees, research managers, department heads, funders' scientific officers</p>	<p>As the research reform agenda advances, evaluators in RPOs and RFOs face mounting expectations to assess researchers in fair, transparent, and contextualised ways. This means going beyond traditional metrics and considering a broader set of contributions—such as open science practices, data/software outputs, community engagement, interdisciplinarity, and narrative CVs.</p>
<p>Customer Job</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess researchers for hiring, promotion, tenure, or funding allocation. • Compare candidates from different disciplines and institutions. • Evaluate a wide range of research contributions (not only publications). • Understand a researcher's impact within collaborative or interdisciplinary projects. • Ensure alignment with institutional/funder values (e.g., Open Science, societal impact). • Apply both qualitative and quantitative criteria in decision-making. • Document and justify assessment decisions transparently.
<p>Pains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher profiles often lack standardisation and comparability across cases. • Contributions to Open Science, teaching, mentoring, or societal engagement are hard to identify or assess. • Narrative CVs are inconsistently structured and difficult to use for comparative evaluations.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluators must manually retrieve information from fragmented systems (ORCID, CVs, institutional platforms). Limited time and resources to conduct holistic and fair evaluations. • Uncertainty in interpreting non-traditional indicators or narrative content.
<p>Gains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to structured, standardised researcher profiles combining narratives and indicators. • Improved visibility into diverse contributions, including datasets, software, reproducibility efforts, and engagement. • Clear descriptions of researcher roles and context in collaborative outputs. • More confident and fairer decision-making thanks to richer evidence. • Interoperability with institutional systems and familiar frameworks (e.g., ORCID, OpenAIRE Graph). • Streamlined evaluation process with reduced administrative burden.
<p>The diagram features a central gift icon. A diagonal line from the top-left corner of a square frame passes through the gift icon, with the text 'Products & Services' positioned above it. In the top-right corner of the square frame, there is an icon of a line graph with an upward arrow, labeled 'Gain Creators'. To the right of the gift icon, there is an icon of a pill, labeled 'Pain Relievers'. An arrow points horizontally from the gift icon towards the right side of the frame.</p>	
<p>Products and Services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MyResearchFolio: researcher-centric profile service combining narrative CVs and Open Science indicators. • Narrative templates: structured formats based on the Royal Society's four-module model. • Integration with ORCID and OpenAIRE Graph: auto-populated profiles with validated metadata.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Science indicators: inclusion of FAIRness, reproducibility, SDG alignment, and openness of outputs. • Customisable views: ability to filter and review profiles based on discipline, role, or purpose (e.g., hiring vs funding) • API-based infrastructure: enabling interoperability with institutional CRISs or evaluator dashboards.
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports RRA principles: enables context-rich, fair, and transparent assessment aligned with CoARA and DORA. • Inclusive evidence base: improves recognition of mentorship, community service, interdisciplinary work, etc. • Efficient comparative review: evaluators can browse, filter, and assess candidates with consistent criteria. • Enables defensible decisions: evidence is structured, reproducible, and aligned with assessment guidelines. • Reduces bias: narrative structure and OS indicators help move beyond simplistic metrics.
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised and structured profiles: make profiles easier to read and compare across candidates. • Embedded OS indicators: evaluators can immediately identify researchers' Open Science engagement. • Bidirectional ORCID sync: ensures information is up to date without burdening evaluators or researchers. • Narrative + indicators: allows evaluators to assess not just what was done, but how and why it matters. • Interoperability layer: reduces time spent switching between platforms and gathering fragmented data. • Profile snapshots: summarised overviews support fast initial screening and more informed shortlisting.

5.3 Go-to-Market Strategy and Roadmap Development

This section presents the Go-to-Market strategy for the four Key Exploitable Results (KERs) emerging from the GraspOS project, focusing on their development trajectories, adoption potential, and associated risks. The strategy has been informed by the analysis conducted through the Horizon Results Booster (HRB), including the completion of the KER characterisation tables for KER1 (SCOPE+i Framework) and KER2 (GraspOS Infrastructure for Institutions and Funders). A third table for KER3 (Training Material) is also included to support a consistent understanding of the portfolio. KER4 (Researcher Profile - MyResearchFolio) is currently at a lower Technology Readiness Level (TRL) but plays a critical cross-cutting role by offering a unifying interface for researcher representation and assessment, and reported in the Services Characterisation Table in (Annex 8).

The overall commercialisation and sustainability strategy builds on three pillars:

- **KER-specific exploitation trajectories**, guided by the stakeholder needs mapped in the characterisation exercises;
- **Cross-KER integration logic**, ensuring coherence between training, assessment frameworks, services, and researcher profiles;
- **Risk analysis and mitigation measures**, designed to ensure resilience in adoption and sustainability across diverse user segments (RPOs, RFOs, researchers, policy makers).

The roadmap included in this section synthesises short-, medium-, and long-term actions needed to prepare, pilot, and sustain these results beyond the project lifetime.

5.3.1 Characterisation Tables of Key Exploitable Results

Characterisation Tables are structured tools used to capture the exploitation potential of each Key Exploitable Result (KER). These tables summarise key dimensions such as:

- Target stakeholders and use scenarios,
- Unique value proposition and expected benefits,
- Maturity level (TRL/MRL) and IP considerations,
- Potential barriers and adoption pathways.

In GraspOS, the Characterisation Tables were instrumental in guiding the development of tailored exploitation strategies and supporting the roadmap and risk assessment phases.

This section includes tables for:

- **KER1 – SCOPE+i Framework**
- **KER2 – Federated Open Infrastructure**
- **KER3 – Training Material**

KER4 – MyResearchFolio is not presented as a standalone KER but is embedded within the service components of the infrastructure. Its design and objectives are reflected across multiple service-level characterisations, as it represents a cross-cutting response to user needs identified throughout the project.

While the main Characterisation Table of KER-2 describes the overall GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure, each of its key components—namely, the tools and services developed within the infrastructure—has also completed a dedicated Characterisation Table. These are provided in **Annex 8**, offering a detailed overview of their individual value propositions, use models, and exploitation paths.

Table 17. Characterisation Tables for KER 1, KER2, and KER 3.

KER1 – SCOPE+i Framework	
Description	<p>The SCOPE+i Framework is a structured, policy-aligned result of the GraspOS project that builds on the earlier Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF). It aims to support Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) in implementing Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), with particular attention to recognising diverse contributions and Open Science practices.</p> <p>The framework combines two core elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assessment process resources – including templates, guides, and checklists – to assist institutions in planning and documenting research assessments aligned with their values, context, and goals. ● Digital services – enabling the collaborative development, sharing, and registration of assessment protocols and researcher profiles. These services enhance transparency, reuse, and interoperability across institutional systems. <p>The SCOPE+i Framework is modular and adaptable, allowing institutions to implement RRA gradually and according to local needs. It is accessible via the GraspOS federated infrastructure and supported by video tutorials and case studies. All resources are openly available, and the digital services are integrated with the broader GraspOS ecosystem.</p>
Target market / End users	<p>The SCOPE+i Framework is aimed at organisations engaged in research assessment and funding allocation, primarily:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) – universities and research institutes seeking structured, fair, and Open Science-aware assessment

	<p>practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) – public and private funders requiring transparent and responsible evaluation frameworks. <p>End users include evaluators, evaluands, research support staff, and information system managers. Consultants may also act as facilitators for institutions with limited internal capacity to implement reform.</p> <p>The initial target market comprises the 700+ signatories of the CoARA Agreement, committed to improving research assessment practices. Market analysis will continue by mapping institutional needs, assessing RRA readiness, and exploring synergies with initiatives such as INORMS and EOSC nodes. This will support refinement of the go-to-market and sustainability strategy.</p>
<p>End-users needs / problem</p>	<p>Across Europe and beyond, RPOs and RFOs are navigating the shift towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), which requires tailoring evaluation practices to specific contexts—including institutional missions, disciplinary structures, and assessment purposes. This transition presents several recurring challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The process of designing new assessment protocols is resource-intensive and complex, especially in the absence of operational guidance. • Institutions face difficulties in capturing and validating evidence of Open Science practices and diverse research contributions. • There is a lack of structured, reusable processes that can be adapted to different institutional levels (individuals, groups, organisations). • RRA implementation is often a learning-by-doing process, requiring iteration and self-reflection. • The transition demands coordination among multiple stakeholders, including institutional leadership, evaluators, evaluands, and IT staff. <p>In this context, SCOPE+i aims to lower barriers to entry, offering clear process models and modular resources.</p> <p>Consultants and facilitators may also play a key role in supporting early-stage adopters. Their needs include access to customisable, easy-to-use materials, and training resources to help guide organisations through the implementation journey. Where institutions lack in-house capacity, these external experts become critical in scaling adoption.</p>
<p>Competitive advantages</p>	<p>The SCOPE+i Framework is among the first to tailor infrastructure specifically for the assessment process. The framework is designed to support the transition to Responsible Research Assessment, with a particular emphasis on contributions to Open Science (OS). By integrating process resources and digital services with the SCOPE framework, the SCOPE+i Framework combines the flexibility required to plan and conduct RRA in diverse assessment contexts with practical tools for managing the complexities of research assessment reform.</p> <p>Additionally, the SCOPE+i Framework is part of the GraspOS federated infrastructure. It will be integrated into the GraspOS service portfolio offered through the GraspOS federated infrastructure.</p> <p>Unlike proprietary or fragmented tools, GraspOS integrates a wide array of open data sources, services, and tools across a distributed infrastructure. For the user, this provides a wide range of plug-and-play resources offered and the fact that all services are digital.</p> <p>This ensures:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Interoperability through standardised APIs. · Scalability across diverse use cases, disciplines, and stakeholder types. · Sustainability, by enabling contribution and reuse by the broader research community.
Use model	<p>The SCOPE+i Framework will be made available through the GraspOS ecosystem (federated infrastructure + zenodo community).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Provision of digital resources: Templates, guides, and checklists to support institutions in research evaluation. · Deployment of digital services: the Assessment Protocol Portfolio and the Openness Profile. · Training and capacity-building workshops to ensure effective adoption and implementation by institutions. <p>In addition, the following potential opportunities for exploitation will be investigated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offering SCOPE+i as an EOSC service, especially when applying for future calls to join the EOSC nodes and the broader ecosystem. - The Interest of INORMS in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · adopting and/or authorising the SCOPE+i framework as support for implementing SCOPE. This could include either part or all of SCOPE+i · collaborating to further develop this new framework; · co-investing in evolving the final service model of specifically SCOPE/SCOPE+i consultants.
Early Adopters	<p>The first adopters of the SCOPE+i Framework will be research institutions and funding organizations that have signed the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) agreement. These early adopters are motivated to implement new research evaluation methodologies and provide critical feedback. Another possibility would be offering the services to expected emergence of EOSC nodes, whereby the SCOPE+i Framework will be available to EOSC users.</p>
Adopters' problems/needs	<p>Organisations aiming to adopt the SCOPE+i Framework—particularly RPOs and RFOs—face a range of structural and operational challenges that limit the uptake of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) approaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of clear, actionable methodologies for implementing qualitative and values-based evaluation; • Limited availability of reusable resources and protocols to guide and document assessment practices in a structured way; • Difficulties in achieving transparency and inclusivity, especially when multiple stakeholders (e.g., researchers, evaluators, policy staff) must collaborate in designing or applying assessment criteria; • Need for interoperability between emerging assessment tools and pre-existing research information systems (e.g., CRISs, repositories), to avoid duplication and streamline workflows;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty in aligning internal assessment policies with evolving external requirements (e.g., CoARA commitments, funder expectations).
<p>Alternative solution</p>	<p>In terms of conceptual resources and policy guidance, alternative solutions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), which provides high-level principles for improving research evaluation practices; • The CoARA National Chapters, which support local implementation of responsible assessment reforms across Europe. <p>However, these initiatives primarily offer normative guidance and policy frameworks—they do not provide the digital infrastructure, reusable resources, or operational tools necessary to implement RRA in a structured, scalable way. To the best of our knowledge, there are no directly comparable digital service frameworks currently available that integrate process resources with interoperable infrastructure as offered by SCOPE+i. That said, the project will continue to monitor the evolving competitive landscape, including efforts by other Horizon Europe projects (e.g. OPUS, SciLake, PathOS) and global initiatives aiming to support Open Science-aware research assessment. This is essential to refining the unique value proposition, anticipating potential synergies or overlaps, and informing the go-to-market strategy.</p>
<p>Unique Value Proposition (UVP)</p>	<p>The SCOPE+i Framework provides a structured, actionable, and interoperable solution to support institutions and funders in implementing Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with a strong focus on Open Science. It distinguishes itself by addressing real user needs—such as the lack of clear, reusable methodologies and the burden of fragmented, non-interoperable systems—through the following unique features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive Support: Covers all phases of the assessment lifecycle—from values definition and planning to documentation and post-evaluation—using both process resources and digital services. • Plug-and-Play Resources: Ready-to-use templates, guides, and checklists that facilitate adoption and local adaptation of RRA principles in a flexible, modular way. • Transparent and Reusable Protocols: Supports the creation and sharing of structured, interoperable, and Open Science-aware assessment protocols, combining qualitative and quantitative criteria. • Collaborative and Inclusive Design: Enables participation from all relevant stakeholders (evaluators, evaluands, research managers), encouraging co-creation and institutional learning. • Interoperability and Extensibility: Built on robust metadata standards (e.g. RAiD, RDA), allowing integration with CRIS, repositories, and other research information systems. <p>This UVP is designed to address the core challenges identified across customer segments—RPOs, RFOs, and facilitators/consultants—ensuring that the framework</p>

	is scalable, adaptable, and aligned with European policy priorities (e.g. CoARA, DORA). Its openness and modularity make it suitable for both early adopters and more mature organisations looking to consolidate or scale up their RRA practices.
Timing	<p>The SCOPE+i resources will be completed and published on Zenodo.</p> <p>By the end of the project, SCOPE+i services will demonstrate proof of concept, and the underlying technology, RAiD, will be in production. After the end of the project, the final tasks to make SCOPE+i services market-ready will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish RAiD service point and identify host organization - Conduct guided use of SCOPE+i services to develop real world use cases. - Update user guides based on the use cases. - Promote services
IP Strategy	<p>The IP background includes prior research assessment methodologies and digital infrastructure developed by consortium partners, ensuring compatibility with existing Open Science policies and standards.</p> <p>The foreground IP includes newly developed assessment processes, digital services, and structured templates/guides within the OSAF framework. Ownership and access rights are determined in accordance with the project's Consortium Agreement, ensuring open accessibility to early adopters and stakeholders.</p>

KER2 - GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure	
Description	<p>The GraspOS infrastructure integrates a wide variety of data sources, tools, services, indicators, and guidance/training materials. These components are made accessible through a user-friendly interface acting as gateway to the infrastructure informing the end-users about the contents and assisting them in identifying federated resources of interest while, thanks to its modular architecture, ensuring interoperability, transparency, and scalability. Key resources are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federated Catalogues of tools, designed in a way to facilitate the discoverability of the respective resources in the EOSC ecosystem, including next-generation metrics and indicators, data, templates, and guidance for research assessment • Monitoring and enrichment services that calculate and visualise both quantitative and qualitative indicators at researcher, institutional, and national levels. • Standardised APIs for seamless integration leveraging on Data Interoperability and Access Layer (DIAL) that harmonizes metadata from diverse sources. • Access to open, community-driven infrastructures such as the OpenAIRE Services and OpenCitations. • Supports a broad spectrum of use cases — from compiling narrative CVs and tracking OS adoption to benchmarking research funding outcomes <p>The infrastructure enables users to:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate research in a context-sensitive and evidence-based way, going beyond bibliometrics on publication, to include datasets, software, policy contributions, and collaborative practices. • Visualise and monitor the uptake of Open Science practices through dashboards and analytical services. • Support the design and implementation of transparent and inclusive evaluation protocols, tailored to different disciplines, institutions, or funding schemes. • Reduce the administrative burden and costs of evaluation workflows by using open tools and reusable components. <p>GraspOS responds to growing demands for responsible indicators and open evaluation ecosystems and serves as a key enabler for institutional reform in research assessment.</p>
<p>Target market / End users</p>	<p>The GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure serves a diverse and evolving market composed of stakeholders committed to transforming how research is evaluated. The infrastructure addresses the needs of four key customer segments, each facing specific pain points in their efforts to implement Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Researchers (domain-agnostic), who are under increasing pressure to demonstrate the impact and relevance of their work, not only through publications but also by engaging in Open Science practices. 2. Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) such as Universities, research centres, and institutes that increasingly need to implement fair, standardised, and policy-aligned research evaluation frameworks. 3. Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), funders — both public and private — seek robust, reproducible, and transparent methods to assess project proposals and measure funded outcomes. 4. Bibliometricians and Research Analysts, usually involved in research evaluation analysis hence requiring reliable, reproducible, and interoperable tools to assess impact. <p>In later stages, further segmentation and quantification of these customer groups will be essential to assess the sustainability of the use model. This will also support the design of an effective go-to-market strategy, particularly as the policy landscape—shaped by initiatives such as CoARA, DORA, and the Barcelona Declaration—increasingly mandates the adoption of Open Science-aware RRA procedures across Europe.</p>
<p>End-users needs / problem</p>	<p>Current research assessment systems are increasingly recognised as inadequate for capturing the full spectrum of research contributions and for supporting Open Science-aligned, qualitative evaluations. End users—those directly involved in performing or supporting research assessment—encounter significant operational, technical, and conceptual challenges.</p> <p>GraspOS identifies four key end-user groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers acting as evaluators, • Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), • Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), and

- Bibliometricians and research analysts.

These users are often expected to apply responsible, transparent, and inclusive assessment methods, but lack the appropriate infrastructure and guidance to do so efficiently.

Cross-cutting pain points:

- Time-consuming and resource-intensive workflows for collecting, reviewing, and interpreting diverse research contributions.
- Lack of standardised, Open Science-aware indicators and structured templates to guide evaluations in alignment with evolving policies (e.g., CoARA, FAIR).
- Fragmentation of data and tools across platforms (e.g., CRIS, ORCID, repositories), resulting in duplication of effort and inconsistencies in reporting.
- Overreliance on citation-based metrics, which fail to reflect the diversity of outputs such as datasets, software, or engagement activities.
- Limited guidance and methodological support for conducting evaluations that combine qualitative narratives with quantitative indicators.
- Absence of interoperable, customisable infrastructures that adapt to varying institutional, disciplinary, or funder contexts.

Specific challenges per user group:

Researchers (as evaluators):

- Limited tools to assess non-traditional research outputs and Open Science practices.
- No consolidated view of candidates' or collaborators' diverse contributions.
- Difficulty in preparing or reviewing narrative CVs due to lack of standardisation and automation.
- Lack of reference indicators or guidance for applying qualitative judgment consistently.

RPOs (e.g., universities, research institutes):

- Internal evaluations rely heavily on traditional metrics, missing Open Science contributions.
- High administrative burden when collecting and aligning data from multiple sources.
- Difficulty applying consistent evaluation criteria across departments or disciplines.
- Limited capacity to adopt qualitative approaches due to absence of structured tools.

RFOs (e.g., national or EU funders):

- Difficulty evaluating grantees on qualitative and Open Science dimensions in competitive calls.
- Challenges benchmarking across programmes due to heterogeneous data and manual reporting.
- Lack of dashboards or automated workflows that support consistent, policy-compliant evaluation processes.

	<p>Bibliometricians / Analysts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No tools designed specifically for Open Science-aware bibliometrics. • Difficulty accessing interoperable data for building reproducible, transparent analytics. • Challenges integrating non-publication outputs into impact assessments. • Heavy reliance on closed platforms with limited customisation.
<p>Competitive advantages</p>	<p>The GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure offers a strategic advantage by directly addressing a widespread challenge: how to implement Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) practices that include qualitative and Open Science indicators—without overburdening institutions or evaluators with fragmented and time-consuming processes.</p> <p>Compared to existing offerings, GraspOS distinguishes itself through the following key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated support for qualitative contributions Supports narrative CVs, datasets, software, and societal engagement—beyond traditional publication metrics. • Alignment with policy and reform agendas Designed in line with RRA principles and Open Science policy frameworks (e.g., CoARA, DORA, EOSC), enabling institutions and funders to demonstrate compliance and leadership. • Open and federated architecture Provides a modular infrastructure based on open standards and governance, ensuring transparency, adaptability, and community ownership. • Interoperability by design Ensures seamless integration with existing research information systems through standardised APIs and harmonised metadata models. • Ready-to-use templates and services Offers a practical toolkit—assessment resources, reusable templates, indicators, and digital services—allowing adopters to move from principle to implementation with minimal overhead. • Scalability and extensibility Built to support a wide range of use cases, institutional contexts, and stakeholder roles, from pilot experimentation to full institutional adoption.
<p>Use model</p>	<p>The GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure is designed as a modular, open, and publicly accessible ecosystem that supports responsible research assessment across a broad spectrum of users — from individual researchers to institutions and funders.</p> <p>The infrastructure operates according to four complementary usage modes:</p> <p>1. Core Open Services for Broad Access</p>

- The foundational components of GraspOS — including APIs, standard indicators, dashboards, and open catalogues — are made available as open-source services.
- These are accessible through a public gateway, free of charge, and aligned with EOSC interoperability standards to ensure wide integration and reuse.

2. Federated Governance and Service Provision

- GraspOS operates under a distributed governance framework, where partners (e.g., OpenAIRE, Athena RC, INRIA, OpenCitations, EGI, Operas, etc) host and maintain specific services.
- This federated model:
 - Leverages existing public mandates or national support to ensure continuity.
 - Enables contribution from new actors (e.g., other EOSC nodes, consortia).
 - Supports modular integration into different local or national contexts.

Note: A Memorandum of Understanding or other EOSC-aligned governance model is under discussion to guide sustainability and roadmap management post-project.

3. Advanced Customisation for Institutional Use

- GraspOS will offer tailored services to institutional partners, based on co-development and pilot activities conducted during the project. These include:
 - Custom dashboards and analytics layers.
 - CRIS system integration and synchronisation.
 - Adaptable user interfaces (e.g., for ministries, alliances).
- These services will be sustained through:
 - Institutional collaborations and in-kind support.
 - Participation in future EOSC or Horizon Europe calls.
 - Structured service agreements when needed (non-profit and transparent).

4. Sustainability-Oriented Collaboration Pathways

- The long-term vision of GraspOS is to function as a **public-good infrastructure**, embedded in the European Open Science landscape.
- Sustainability will be pursued via:
 - Contribution by institutions adopting the services.
 - Integration into EOSC Nodes or national/regional infrastructures.
 - Continued alignment with community-led initiatives like CoARA or national OS policies.

	<p>No commercial or for-profit model is currently foreseen. Instead, the infrastructure is designed to be adaptable to the needs of public-sector actors, encouraging contributions, reuse, and joint stewardship.</p>
<p>Early Adopters</p>	<p>The early adopters of the GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure will be stakeholders who are actively engaged in reforming research evaluation practices and already committed to implementing Open Science principles. These adopters are typically those who face the greatest challenges with current assessment systems and are seeking immediate, scalable, and policy-aligned solutions. While the core services of GraspOS will be open and accessible to all, early adopters are expected to engage at different levels, depending on their needs and capacities — ranging from pilot testing of open components to establishing institutional partnerships for custom implementations.</p> <p>Target Early Adopters</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> CoARA Signatories (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment), institutions (universities, funders, national evaluation bodies) already committed to moving beyond journal-based metrics and implementing responsible research assessment practices. EOSC-related Institutional Champions, members of the EOSC Association or affiliated EOSC-related projects that are driving the adoption of open infrastructures. Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) piloting Open Science dashboards and narrative CVs, institutions already experimenting with OpenAIRE MONITOR, OpenAIRE Graph and/or OpenAlex, or narrative CV formats (e.g., in NORWAY, Netherlands, Finland). National or Thematic Funders Exploring Reform (RFOs), funding bodies in countries with Open Science mandates (e.g., France, Ireland, Slovenia) or sectors like health, climate, and digital transition.
<p>Adopters' problems/needs</p>	<p>Organisations adopting the GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure—such as Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), and policy-makers—are expected to align with Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) and Open Science (OS) principles. However, this transition presents a number of structural, operational, and technical challenges:</p> <p>Common Cross-Adopter Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of operational tools to apply narrative CVs, qualitative methods, and Open Science indicators in real-case scenario assessment workflows. • Resource-intensive and fragmented processes: Assessment activities are typically manual, time-consuming, and require collecting data across multiple disconnected platforms. • Dependence on proprietary, metric-centric infrastructures: Existing systems emphasise citation-based metrics and lack support for assessing diverse research contributions. • Low interoperability: Absence of shared standards and APIs impedes integration of new tools with existing CRIS, HR, or funding systems.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty demonstrating alignment with Open Science policies such as CoARA or DORA in a reproducible and scalable way. <p>Specific Needs by Adopter Type</p> <p>RPOs (e.g., universities, research institutes):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for fair, transparent, and contextualised research evaluation across disciplines and departments. • Limited internal capacity to support customised indicators or alternative evaluation models. • Pressure to align with national OS policies and demonstrate reform at the institutional level. <p>RFOs (e.g., national and international funders):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of standardised and trusted indicators for evaluating Open Science practices across funding programmes. • Challenges in benchmarking grantee outputs and aligning evaluation practices with OS-related funding requirements. • Demand for reproducible and cost-efficient impact evaluation workflows. <p>Bibliometricians / Research Analysts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate tools for conducting Open Science-aware analysis (e.g., inclusion of datasets, software, and engagement metrics). • Limited access to reliable, open, and interoperable data sources for large-scale evaluation. • Lack of guidance and reproducibility in OS indicator design and implementation. <p>Researchers (as secondary adopters or hybrid user-adopters in smaller settings):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited support for building rich profiles that go beyond publication lists. • Difficulty curating and maintaining contributions across platforms (e.g., ORCID, institutional CRIS, grant reports). • Absence of integrated environments for aligning with OS expectations in career development and funding applications.
<p>Alternative solution</p>	<p>Until now, adopters seeking to implement Open Science-aligned research assessment have had to rely on a patchwork of partial solutions. These range from commercial platforms and institutional systems to policy frameworks and isolated open tools—none of which offer an integrated, end-to-end infrastructure for Responsible Research Assessment (RRA).</p> <p>Common alternatives included:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metric-focused analytics platforms offering strong citation data but limited support for non-traditional outputs (e.g., datasets, software, engagement). These solutions are often closed, expensive, and narrowly focused on publications. • Institutional CRIS and RIMS systems, useful for administrative reporting but lacking modules for qualitative indicators or narrative elements. Their integration into assessment workflows is typically manual and resource-intensive. • Spreadsheets and internal reporting tools, used to monitor Open Science practices or respond to policy mandates. While highly customised, these methods are unsustainable, non-automated, and lack reusability. • Policy declarations and manifestos that provide valuable guidance but no technical mechanisms to support implementation or monitor progress, leaving institutions to develop bespoke solutions. • Custom dashboards and national tools, often well-adapted to local needs but difficult to scale, compare, or integrate across institutions and systems. • Emerging open infrastructures supporting metadata, citations, and OS indicators. While open and community-driven, these typically focus on specific components and lack the interoperability, workflow integration, and user interface needed for institutional adoption. <p>Despite valuable contributions from EU-funded initiatives developing indicators, prototypes, and pilots, most remain fragmented and do not offer a unified operational platform.</p> <p>GraspOS fills this gap by providing a modular, interoperable, and production-ready infrastructure that combines data, tools, and services for real-world, policy-aligned research assessment. Its design responds directly to the need for integrated, scalable, and Open Science-aware solutions across institutions and funders.</p>
<p>Unique Value Proposition</p>	<p>GraspOS offers a practical response to the growing demand for more inclusive, transparent, and Open Science-aligned research assessment. It is built to serve the real needs of institutions, funders, researchers, and analysts—those who are struggling with manual, fragmented, or metric-centric evaluation systems that fail to recognise the diversity of modern research.</p> <p>By addressing key user pains such as high administrative burden, lack of suitable indicators, fragmented workflows, and limited support for qualitative contributions, GraspOS provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Research Performing Organisations (RPOs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A cost-effective way to conduct assessments that go beyond publications, integrating Open Science indicators and custom criteria.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced administrative workload through automated data collection and reusable evaluation protocols. ● For Research Funding Organisations (RFOs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tools to evaluate funded research with both qualitative and quantitative indicators aligned with policy objectives. ○ The ability to benchmark outcomes across programmes and improve accountability and learning from funding strategies. ● For Researchers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A unified platform to showcase contributions beyond traditional metrics, including datasets, software, engagement, and more. ○ Simplified self-assessment and portfolio building, with narrative CVs and Open Science dashboards designed for reusability. ● For Bibliometricians and Analysts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Transparent, reproducible access to open indicators and metadata across systems. ○ Support for developing custom metrics aligned with Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) and Open Science values. <p>GraspOS turns policy commitments into practice—bridging the gap between strategic ambitions (e.g., CoARA, DORA, EOSC) and operational reality. It enables responsible, contextualised assessment at both micro (individual, departmental) and macro (institutional, national) levels, helping the research ecosystem shift from rhetoric to implementation.</p>
<p>Competitors</p>	<p>The research assessment landscape includes a variety of tools, systems, and frameworks that partially address the evolving needs of institutions, funders, and researchers. These competitors can be grouped into five main categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1. Proprietary Research Analytics Platforms Commercially developed systems dominate the market with citation-based metrics and global adoption. They offer polished interfaces and extensive publication datasets but rely on closed infrastructures, prioritise legacy indicators, and provide limited support for Open Science outputs or qualitative contributions. Customisation is often costly, and integration with policy frameworks is minimal. ● 2. Institutional CRIS and RIMS Solutions These systems are primarily designed for internal data management and administrative reporting. While well-integrated into institutional workflows, they often lack native support for Open Science or Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) indicators, are difficult to customise, and

	<p>operate in siloed environments with limited interoperability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Policy Initiatives Without Operational Tools Declarations and frameworks such as DORA and CoARA have successfully raised awareness and mobilised support for reform, but they do not provide technical infrastructures to implement or monitor assessment practices. As a result, institutions are left to interpret and operationalise principles independently, leading to fragmented approaches. 4. Custom or National Dashboards Some institutions and funders have developed in-house dashboards or national-level monitoring systems tailored to specific needs. While effective for local reporting or compliance, these tools are often not interoperable, are limited in scope, and require substantial maintenance and technical investment to scale or adapt to broader contexts. 5. Open Data Services and Infrastructure Components Community-driven services for open metadata, citations, and Open Science indicators (e.g., those offered by public infrastructures) have significantly advanced transparency. However, when used in isolation, they lack integration with institutional workflows and are not designed to function as complete assessment infrastructures. Adoption requires substantial integration efforts and technical capacity.
<p>Timing</p>	<p>Currently at TRL 6, with its components tested through pilots and demonstration cases involving early institutional users, the infrastructure will reach full deployment and integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by the end of 2025, ensuring technical maturity, policy alignment, and long-term sustainability. From that point on, the infrastructure will be ready for broad adoption by research-performing organisations, funders, and other actors seeking Open Science-aware assessment solutions.</p> <p>Beyond 2025, the platform is expected to evolve continuously, incorporating feedback from users, alignment with CoARA and EOSC developments, and contributions from the wider community under an open-source governance model.</p>
<p>IP Strategy</p>	<p>The IP strategy for KER 2 is essential to support the openness, interoperability, and long-term sustainability of the GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure. It ensures that all technical components, metadata standards, and documentation remain accessible and reusable beyond the project's duration.</p> <p>Background IP</p> <p>The infrastructure builds on open-source software and services developed by consortium partners prior to GraspOS, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Components maintained by OpenAIRE, Athena RC, OpenCitations, INRIA, and others; Metadata infrastructures like the OpenAIRE Graph and its APIs;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software libraries released under permissive licenses (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0, EUPL) by partners such as UniBO and OPERAS. <p>All background components are provided under open licenses to guarantee compatibility and extensibility.</p> <p>Foreground IP Newly developed assets include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core components such as the Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL), federated catalogues and registries, and the user-facing GraspOS interface; • Assessment-focused services (e.g., researcher profiles, assessment protocols registry); • Updated semantic models, open APIs, and implementation guidance for OS-aware RRA. <p>These are released as open-source (e.g., MIT, Apache 2.0) and hosted in public repositories (GitHub, Zenodo) with full documentation and DOIs.</p> <p>IP Management and Governance Key measures include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking all software outputs with appropriate open-source licenses; • Collaborative maintenance via GitHub and open documentation practices; • A shared Data Management Plan to ensure compliant reuse of metadata; • Agreement among partners to avoid commercial restrictions (e.g., patents) in favour of maximising uptake through open standards; • Ongoing discussions to define a post-project governance model, potentially via a community-led or EOSC-affiliated structure, ensuring continued stewardship and openness. <p>This strategy safeguards the infrastructure's alignment with FAIR principles, while enabling long-term community-driven adoption and evolution.</p>
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KER 3- Training Material	
Description	<p>KER 3 consists of a modular, open-access training programme developed and hosted on the OpenPlato platform. It consolidates the knowledge, resources, and lessons learned throughout the GraspOS project into a structured capacity-building offer. Designed for a wide range of stakeholders—such as research managers, analysts, funders, and institutional administrators—the course integrates both conceptual frameworks (e.g., SCOPE+i) and practical tools (e.g.,</p>

	<p>OpenAIRE Graph APIs, BIP! Scholar, Metadata Validator). It offers guided learning pathways, embedded demonstrations from training events, and reusable materials to support the adoption of Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA) practices. The training materials aim to enable replication, scalability, and long-term impact beyond the project's lifetime.</p>
<p>Target market / End users</p>	<p>The training material targets key stakeholders involved in designing, implementing, or supporting research assessment practices. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Performing Organisations (RPOs): Research managers, department heads, and institutional assessment officers responsible for coordinating internal evaluations, designing CV formats, or aligning local practices with Open Science and RRA principles. • Research Funding Organisations (RFOs): Programme officers and evaluators seeking guidance on how to implement OS-aware assessment in funding calls and evaluation protocols. • Bibliometricians and Research Analysts: Professionals working on the development and interpretation of indicators, who need both technical and conceptual training to support the transition to responsible metrics. • Individual Researchers and Evaluators: Early adopters of Open Science-aligned practices, including those participating in committees or pilots exploring narrative CVs and alternative indicators. <p>The Training Material is particularly relevant for institutions and funders that are CoARA signatories or otherwise committed to research assessment reform. It serves both as an onboarding tool for newcomers and as a professional development resource for more advanced users.</p>
<p>End-users needs / problem</p>	<p>End users face a significant knowledge and skills gap in implementing Open Science-aware and Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) practices. While many institutions and funders endorse policy principles (e.g., CoARA, DORA), they often struggle with practical implementation. Specific challenges include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of training and guidance on how to operationalise policy frameworks in everyday evaluation workflows. • Limited understanding of alternative indicators, narrative CV formats, and Open Science metrics. • Fragmented access to trustworthy, up-to-date, and context-sensitive training materials tailored to different roles and organisational levels. • High reliance on traditional practices, with insufficient exposure to innovative approaches or international case studies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate internal capacity to train staff or evaluators, especially in small institutions or funding bodies with limited resources. <p>The training material developed in GraspOS responds to these challenges by offering structured, modular, and role-based training material that supports both conceptual understanding and practical adoption of RRA-aligned tools and services.</p>
<p>Competitive advantages</p>	<p>The GraspOS training material supports capacity building for Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) and Open Science practices through a modular and open-access learning resource. It offers several advantages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundation in project-wide expertise: The content draws on the tools, frameworks, and services developed within GraspOS, providing a coherent introduction to OS-aware RRA. • Interoperable and open: Developed in open formats, the material is suitable for reuse and adaptation across institutions and national contexts. • Stakeholder alignment: It contributes to creating a shared understanding of responsible research assessment principles among researchers, funders, and administrators. • Support for awareness and onboarding: The material helps lower entry barriers for organisations beginning to engage with Open Science-aligned assessment, serving as an initial stepping stone for deeper engagement
<p>Use model</p>	<p>The GraspOS training material is freely available and openly accessible, supporting community-driven capacity building in Responsible Research Assessment and Open Science. It is hosted and maintained on OpenPlato, a governance-based training infrastructure coordinated by OpenAIRE. This platform ensures long-term accessibility, standardised format, and integration with other OpenAIRE services. The material can be reused and adapted by institutions, funders, and research support professionals seeking to train internal staff or external stakeholders.</p>
<p>Early Adopters</p>	<p>The primary early adopters of the GraspOS training material are institutions and organisations engaged in the reform of research assessment practices, particularly those already involved in GraspOS pilot activities or members of the CoARA initiative. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) seeking internal capacity-building resources to train staff, evaluators, and researchers on Open Science-aware assessment principles. • Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) aiming to align internal evaluation procedures with emerging policy frameworks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research supports professionals and consultants who facilitate or advise on Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) implementation. <p>The initial uptake is expected from those who participated in co-design activities within GraspOS or showed interest in adopting the SCOPE+i framework and related services. These actors are motivated to experiment with new training formats to support institutional change and policy alignment.</p>
<p>Adopters' problems/needs</p>	<p>Organisations aiming to reform their research assessment processes often struggle with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of accessible, structured training resources to support internal change towards Open Science-aligned and Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). • Limited internal expertise on designing and implementing alternative evaluation methods (e.g., narrative CVs, Open Science indicators, portfolio-based assessments). • Fragmentation of knowledge, with training materials scattered across initiatives and lacking coherence with practical tools and infrastructures. • Insufficient awareness and understanding of how to translate policy principles (e.g., CoARA, DORA) into operational practices. <p>Adopters need modular, well-documented resources that help guide institutional actors—research managers, support staff, and evaluators—through the implementation process in a coherent, scalable, and policy-aligned way.</p>
<p>Alternative solution</p>	<p>While various training initiatives exist in the broader Open Science landscape — such as those developed by UNESCO, NASA, and initiatives like PEP-CV — these resources tend to be general, not tailored to the specific tools, services, and frameworks developed under GraspOS. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most Open Science courses are accessible and updated but lack alignment with the GraspOS infrastructure, services, and the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF). • No dedicated training currently exists on the practical implementation of CoARA or DORA recommendations or on integrating OS-aware assessment practices into institutional workflows. • Available training typically does not support structured enrolment or role-based customisation for different stakeholder groups (e.g., RPOs, RFOs, bibliometricians). • The GraspOS training material, supported through OpenPlato, consolidates webinar content addressing multiple target audiences, such as researchers (e.g., BIP! Scholar), institutions and funders (e.g., OpenAIRE Monitor), and analysts (e.g., OpenAIRE Graph, OpenCitations). • Unlike generic Open Science training, the GraspOS course is embedded in a governed infrastructure (OpenPlato) that enables continuous updates,

	<p>modular reuse, and potential integration into EOSC for broader visibility and sustainability.</p>
<p>Unique Value Proposition</p>	<p>The GraspOS training materials offer a unique entry point for capacity building on Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA), going beyond general Open Science education by focusing on the tools, services, and workflows developed within the GraspOS infrastructure and the Open Science Assessment Framework (OSAF).</p> <p>Unlike other Open Science training resources, the GraspOS materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are embedded in a governed infrastructure (OpenPlato), enabling modular reuse, long-term sustainability, and potential EOSC integration. • Address multiple stakeholder needs (researchers, funders, institutions, analysts) through dedicated webinars and hands-on demonstrations. • Provide applied guidance on tools such as BIP! Scholar, OpenAIRE Monitor, and the OpenAIRE Graph, which are not covered in mainstream training. • Support the operationalisation of OS-aware assessment principles (e.g., PEP-CV, narrative profiles, policy indicators), bridging the gap between high-level policy and real institutional workflows. <p>By focusing on implementation and alignment with the GraspOS infrastructure, these training materials fill a critical gap in current capacity-building efforts for research assessment reform.</p>
<p>Timing</p>	<p>The Training Material will be completed by the end of the project and released in a course in Open Plato</p>
<p>IP Strategy</p>	<p>The training materials developed under GraspOS will be openly licensed under Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY), ensuring that all authors and contributors are clearly acknowledged and credited across all formats and platforms. This licensing model promotes maximum reuse, transparency, and visibility while aligning with the Open Science principles underpinning the project.</p> <p>All content will be made publicly accessible through platforms such as Zenodo and OpenPlato, accompanied by metadata and contributor information. This guarantees traceability and compliance with FAIR principles and encourages adaptation and localisation by future users and adopters</p>

5.3.2 Exploitation Roadmap

This section outlines the strategic steps planned to ensure the sustainability, uptake, and further development of the GraspOS Key Exploitable Results (KERs) beyond the project's lifetime. The roadmap includes actions to refine services, engage stakeholders, secure alignment with relevant policy frameworks (e.g., EOSC, CoARA), and explore funding and governance models. Each KER follows a tailored path based on its maturity level, user needs, and adoption potential, supported by a shared vision of responsible, Open Science-aligned research assessment.

While KERs 1 and 2 are addressed through specific exploitation activities and service refinement plans, KER 3 – Training Material is considered an integrated component of the infrastructure, supporting user onboarding, capacity building, and long-term engagement. Its roadmap is therefore embedded across the adoption strategies of the core services and aligned with the sustainability efforts of the federated infrastructure as a whole.

Table 18 Exploitation Roadmaps per KERs

Exploitation Roadmap for KER 1- SCOPE + i Framework	
Actions	<p>In the 3–6 months following the conclusion of the GraspOS project, the following actions should be taken to ensure the uptake, sustainability, and exploitation of the GraspOS SCOPE+i Framework:</p> <p>SCOPE+i Assessment Resources</p> <p>As these resources will be published in the GraspOS catalogue and made accessible through the GraspOS repository on Zenodo, the following operational activities are required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a process to enable community contributions • Define a review and acceptance procedure for submitted contributions • Establish a governance framework to ensure fair and inclusive participation • Provide access to a training material <p>SCOPE+i Assessment Services</p> <p>The assessment services will demonstrate a pilot proof of concept using the SURF-RAiD demo platform. The following activities are necessary to transition to a production-ready service within the GraspOS federated infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deploy a hosted RAiD service point (provided by SURF) • Migrate services to the GraspOS federated infrastructure • Set up help desk support and provide comprehensive technical documentation <p>Dissemination and Adoption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide guided use pilots for early adopters

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document and disseminate use cases <p>Update user guides based on the use cases.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote services • Engage with CoARA and EOSC stakeholders
Roles	<p>CWTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the transition to a production-ready service • Recruit pilot partners for guided use pilots; support the pilots and document/disseminate outcomes • Strategically position services by engaging with related initiatives <p>ATHENA RC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the integration of the production service into the federated infrastructure • Facilitate processes for community contributions, including review and acceptance procedures • Develop and implement a governance framework to ensure fair and inclusive participation <p>Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCOPE+i Assessment Resources: Incorporate feedback from early adopters and publish updated versions as needed <p>All of the partners will support Outreach & Engagement activities with CoARA, EOSC, and other stakeholders.</p>
Costs	<p>The RAiD service in Europe is delivered by the RAiD Registration Agency at SURF in the Netherlands. However, SURF has not yet established a service fee structure for international users.</p>
Revenues	<p>The RAiD service is governed by an ISO standard (ISO 23527:2022). This standard allows service fees for cost recovery.</p>

Exploitation Roadmap for KER 2 - GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure

Actions	<p>In the 3–6 months following the conclusion of the GraspOS project, the following actions are planned to ensure the uptake, sustainability, and exploitation of the GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure, divided into five phases:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Operational Consolidation of the Infrastructure Timeline: Within 3 months <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final release of all core components: catalogues, APIs, interoperability layer, user interface, with open-source code where applicable • Transition from pilot environments to publicly accessible services • Launch of helpdesk support and technical documentation for new users, integrated to the training material and knowledge base in Open Plato Stakeholder Engagement and Onboarding of Adopters Timeline: Within 3-6 months
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding of early adopters (e.g., CoARA signatories, EOSC-aligned institutions and initiatives). • Delivery of use-case-specific training sessions and onboarding toolkits (both for technical and policy actors). • Collection of letters of intent (LoIs) or Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) from early adopters. <p>3. Finalisation of the Business and Sustainability Model Timeline: Begin within 3 months</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate the service model (e.g., freemium model, institutional service tiers, API-based services). • Define potential revenue streams and cost recovery strategy. • Explore funding opportunities via EOSC Nodes, EOSC-A Task Forces, and national Open Science frameworks. <p>4. Governance and Legal Framework Timeline: Begin within 3 months, formalise by month 6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a multi-partner governance model, involving both service providers and institutional supporters of the infrastructure. • Two options under discussion: i. MoU-based light structure for shared commitment; ii. Legal entity or EOSC Node participation for deeper integration and sustainability. • Assign roles for maintenance, updates, and roadmap coordination (technical, policy, community). <p>5. Dissemination and Positioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of a communication campaign targeting research institutions, funders, and policy actors. • Engage in key policy events and Open Science and research assessment fora to present the infrastructure and its uptake across the early adopters. • Publication of white papers, policy briefs, and success stories based on project pilots.
<p>Roles</p>	<p>1. OpenAIRE AMKE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for the exploitation roadmap. • Coordinates the long-term exploitation strategy, sustainability planning, and stakeholder engagement (particularly RPOs and RFOs). • Oversees integration with EOSC and ensures alignment with policy frameworks such as CoARA and national Open Science plans. • Leads dissemination activities, training delivery, and first-line support infrastructure (e.g., helpdesk). <p>2. ATHENA RC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical lead for the GraspOS architecture and back-end infrastructure. • Maintains and evolves the Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL), APIs, and metadata flows. <p>Supports scaling, interoperability, and onboarding of technical adopters through integration guidance and documentation.</p> <p>3. CNR-ISTI</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for semantic interoperability and metadata quality assurance • Contributes to the governance model for federated resources and registries. • Supports the maintenance and evolution of shared metadata standards and integration with linked open data sources. <p>4. CWTS (Leiden University)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributes methodological expertise on responsible research assessment and the design of indicator frameworks. • Supports the development and validation of qualitative and quantitative indicators in line with Open Science principles. • Co-develops training and awareness materials for institutions and funders adopting new evaluation approaches. <p>5. University of Bologna (UniBO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses on the integration and responsible use of citation-related data and indicators within the infrastructure. • Contributes to the identification and implementation of scientometric methods consistent with Open Science-aware assessment. • Supports the development of guidance and documentation for transparent citation practices where applicable. <p>OPERAS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engages with stakeholders from the social sciences and humanities (SSH) to ensure inclusive infrastructure design. • Contributes to the enrichment of the services and tools catalogue with SSH-relevant resources and use cases. • Leads multilingual dissemination and tailored engagement within SSH communities. <p>6. INRIA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides software development support and contributes to the governance of open-source components. • Participates in defining post-project sustainability pathways for the infrastructure. • Supports outreach in the French national and francophone Open Science landscape. <p>7. Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports alignment with national-level Open Science strategies and assessment policies. • Provides legal and policy input on data governance, service agreements, and national adoption models. • Facilitates outreach and integration within Nordic and CoARA-related policy communities. <p>8. EGI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advises on sustainability and integration models for federated services in EOSC. • Supports onboarding of the infrastructure in EOSC Exchange or EOSC Core environments. • Contributes to long-term service management planning and alignment with broader European e-infrastructure strategies.
<p>Milestones</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final public release of the infrastructure Core components (catalogues, APIs, front-end) are released in the production version with documentation. (Target: Month 3) • Launch of governance and maintenance group Agreement on post-project roles and responsibilities for sustaining the infrastructure. (Target: Month 4) • Onboarding of first external institutional adopters At least two institutions outside the consortium start using the infrastructure. (Target: Month 5) • Delivery of initial training sessions and materials At least two public training events delivered; publication of training resources. (Target: Month 4) • Publication of service access and licensing terms Finalisation and publication of terms of use, licensing model, and access policy. (Target: Month 6) • Integration roadmap submitted to EOSC Exchange Submission of the infrastructure for onboarding as an EOSC service. (Target: Month 6)
<p>Costs</p>	<p>Estimated Investment for Post-Project Exploitation (Months 1-6)</p> <p>To ensure the continuity, operational readiness, and adoption of the GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure after the project ends, we estimate that a minimum investment of €200,000–€250,000 over the first six months will be required. This estimation is based on actual personnel and operational costs incurred during the final phases of the project (Periods 5–6), and is proportionate to the activities foreseen in the exploitation roadmap.</p> <p>This investment would cover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final release and maintenance of core technical components • Coordination of the governance group and onboarding of institutional adopters

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of training events and support material • Operational costs for helpdesk, documentation, and outreach • Legal and administrative preparation of MoUs and terms of use <p>These costs are expected to be covered through in-kind contributions from partners and/or external funding sources. The estimated effort corresponds to approximately 6-8 full-time person-months, distributed across 2-3 key partners. The actual distribution of effort will depend on the governance model and exploitation route agreed upon at the end of the project.</p>
<p>Revenues</p>	<p>As all partners involved in the exploitation of GraspOS are non-profit organisations, the revenue model is designed to ensure cost recovery and long-term sustainability, rather than profit generation.</p> <p>Revenues will be generated through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service-level agreements with institutional adopters • Annual subscriptions to hosted services and APIs • Customised support and training packages • Participation in EOSC-related or national Open Science funding schemes <p>Assuming a conservative uptake scenario within the first year post-project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-5 research institutions adopting standard services • 1-2 networks or alliances • 1 national-level initiative • Several training sessions <p>The total potential revenue could range between €20,000 and €50,000 in the first year, increasing progressively with scaling and integration into EOSC or national infrastructures. This revenue estimation remains indicative and will be refined based on the governance model and exploitation pathway agreed among partners.</p>
<p>Other sources of coverage</p>	<p>In the short term, the operation and scaling of the GraspOS infrastructure will rely on in-kind contributions from key partners, particularly for coordination, technical maintenance, and initial support to adopters.</p> <p>To ensure long-term sustainability, the consortium will explore targeted funding schemes aligned with the non-profit, open, and public-service nature of the infrastructure. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC-related mechanisms, such as the EOSC Federation or EOSC Nodes support lines • National Open Science programmes available in participating countries

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional co-funding by early adopters and research alliances • European programmes supporting research infrastructures and digital services, such as Horizon Europe (e.g., Reforming R&I, INFRA) <p>These schemes typically support interoperable digital services, cross-border collaboration, and research assessment reform — all of which are central to the GraspOS exploitation strategy.</p>
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5.3.3 Risk Management and Business Model Mapping

As part of the exploitation support activities carried out in collaboration with the HRB, dedicated Risk Maps and Lean Canvas models were developed for the two core Key Exploitable Results of the GraspOS project:

- **KER 1 – SCOPE+i, previously named OSAF (Open Science Assessment Framework)**
- **KER 2 – GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure.**

While KER 3 – Training Material is a valuable component of the overall infrastructure, it is not a standalone service and does not currently follow an autonomous uptake or commercialisation path. For this reason, it was not the focus of dedicated risk and business model mapping exercises during the booster programme. Its sustainability is instead embedded in the broader strategy for KER 1 and KER 2, which it supports by enabling user capacity building and adoption.

The HRB exploitation support made use of two complementary tools: Risk Maps and the Lean Canvas model. Risk Maps were applied to systematically identify and categorise potential threats to exploitation, including technological, organisational, financial, and adoption-related risks. For each risk, the likelihood and potential impact were assessed in order to define appropriate mitigation measures. The Lean Canvas model was then used to structure the business logic of the two core KERs, capturing key elements such as target users, value proposition, channels, cost structures, and revenue streams. Together, these tools supported the identification of critical assumptions, potential obstacles to uptake, and the strategic positioning of the solutions within the evolving landscape of Responsible Research Assessment and Open Science policy reform. The exercise also contributed to refining the exploitation pathways of these high-priority, service-oriented results by linking risks with concrete actions for sustainability. The complete HRB report has been submitted on a confidential basis and can be provided upon request. The present section outlines the main outcomes of the analysis. In the following table we report a simplified version of the main risks identified for KER1 and KER2 and proposed mitigation strategies.

Table 19. Risk Analysis and Mitigation Intervention

Risk category	Description	Future interventions (mitigation)
Partnership & Governance	Lack of long-term partner commitment; insufficient human resources; divergent priorities.	Establish clear governance models (MoUs, agreements); assign dedicated staff; maintain continuous dialogue with stakeholders.
Technological	Integration challenges with external systems; need for scalability and interoperability.	Invest in API development; ensure EOSC integration; adopt open standards; iterative testing with pilot partners.
Market Adoption &	Institutions/funders not ready to adopt RRA tools; slow uptake due to timing of reforms.	Provide guided pilots with early adopters; communicate benefits through demonstrators; align with CoARA and national initiatives.
Financial & Sustainability	Limited funding beyond project lifetime; need for viable long-term business models.	Explore mixed funding models (EU projects, institutional contributions, freemium options); embed services in EOSC sustainability plans.
Legal & Ethical	Data protection and ethical concerns in the use of assessment data.	Ensure GDPR compliance; transparent data governance policies; clear terms of use for all stakeholders.

The risk analysis conducted for KER1 (SCOPE+i) and KER2 (GraspOS Research Assessment Infrastructure) indicates that the main challenges to exploitation are linked to governance, sustainability, adoption timing, and stakeholder trust. Both results are designed to facilitate the transition to more responsible and OS-aligned RRA practices. This transition requires not only robust infrastructure but also cultural change, regulatory alignment, and institutional engagement.

From a governance perspective, risks include the potential lack of long-term partner commitment, insufficient human resources, or divergent institutional priorities. These factors could affect the consolidation of the infrastructure and its capacity to operate beyond the project's duration. Mitigation strategies defined in this area include the establishment of clear governance models through Memoranda of Understanding and formal agreements, the allocation of dedicated staff to exploitation activities, and the maintenance of structured and continuous dialogue with key stakeholders.

Technological risks mainly concern the scalability and interoperability of services. Although the infrastructure has been designed with a modular and federated approach, integration with external systems and infrastructures (such as CRIS systems, data repositories, and EOSC services) remains essential. To address this, the project partners foresee iterative testing with pilot institutions, the development of open APIs, and compliance with recognised standards. Embedding GraspOS within EOSC and other trusted infrastructures is also expected to increase technical reliability and long-term viability.

Market and adoption risks reflect the uneven pace of reforms in Responsible Research Assessment across countries and institutions. In some contexts, readiness to adopt new practices may be limited, and uptake could take longer than anticipated. The mitigation measures in this category focus on the organisation of guided pilots with early adopters, the provision of demonstrators that communicate benefits clearly, and alignment with relevant policy initiatives such as CoARA and national Open Science strategies. These actions are intended to accelerate adoption and ensure that the infrastructure responds to the priorities of different stakeholder groups.

Financial and sustainability risks represent another critical area. Without secure and diversified funding sources beyond the project lifetime, there is a risk that the services will not be maintained. GraspOS has identified the need to explore mixed funding models that combine public support from EU projects, institutional contributions, and potential freemium approaches. Furthermore, integration into EOSC sustainability frameworks is considered essential to provide continuity and long-term support for the infrastructure.

Legal and ethical risks, particularly related to data protection, are also relevant for exploitation. Assessment processes involve sensitive information, and it is important to ensure compliance with GDPR and other applicable regulations. Mitigation measures in this area include the adoption of transparent governance rules, clear terms of use for all stakeholders, and explicit procedures to ensure accountability and ethical data management.

Therefore, the risk analysis demonstrates that the exploitation of GraspOS results requires a comprehensive strategy that combines technical robustness with governance, financial sustainability, legal compliance, and stakeholder adoption. The interventions identified provide a clear framework to anticipate and manage potential obstacles. The resulting exploitation pathway is structured to ensure that the outcomes of GraspOS can evolve from

pilot implementations with early adopters towards broader integration into institutional practices and European policy frameworks.

5.4 Alignment with Policy, Infrastructure, and Sustainability Strategies

The exploitation strategy of GraspOS has been developed in close alignment with major European policy frameworks and research infrastructure initiatives. This ensures that the project's outcomes are not only technologically sound and community-driven, but also positioned for systemic impact in the evolving ecosystem of Open Science and research assessment reform.

From its inception, GraspOS has embedded its strategic planning within the broader objectives of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), and other initiatives that aim to reform research evaluation practices across Europe. Rather than opting for a purely technical approach, the project has adopted a value-driven framework that prioritises transparency, inclusivity, and the long-term sustainability of its outputs. This alignment has shaped the technical design, governance proposals, and stakeholder engagement activities of the project.

By proactively engaging with actors such as the CoARA Working Group "Towards an Open Infrastructures for RRA" (OI4RRA), GraspOS has contributed to shaping the policy discourse around open infrastructures and assessment reform. It has ensured that its tools and services are not developed in isolation, but are instead interoperable with existing infrastructures, sensitive to institutional constraints, and designed to respond to policy needs that include Open Science in research assessment.

This integrated approach enables GraspOS to bridge the gap between vision and implementation, ensuring its outcomes are not only usable but also meaningful in advancing responsible and Open Science-aware research assessment across Europe.

5.4.1. Strategic Policy Anchoring

A distinctive feature of GraspOS is its dual role as both an infrastructure development project and a policy-shaping initiative in the European landscape for RRA. From the outset, GraspOS has taken an active position within CoARA, contributing substantially to the Working Group OI4RRA. This group brought together experts from infrastructures, funders, research institutions, and Open Science advocates to co-develop a shared vision for the technical,

organisational, and governance requirements of infrastructures that support reform in research assessment.

The GraspOS team has co-authored and co-led the development of three key policy documents emerging from this Working Group:

- Manola, N., Tzouganatou, A., Kuchma, I., & CoARA WG on OI4RRA. (2025). **Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Principles and Framework**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487403>
- Manola, N., Vergoulis, T., Tzouganatou, A., & CoARA WG on OI4RRA. (2025). **Conceptual Architecture for the Implementation of a Responsible Research Assessment Framework Built on Open Infrastructures**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487415>
- Manola, N., Tzouganatou, A., Vergoulis, T., & CoARA WG on OI4RRA. (2025). **Policy Briefs: Transitioning from Closed Proprietary Systems to Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment, for Research-Performing & Research-Funding Organizations**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15490704>

These publications provide both a strategic orientation and an operational blueprint for infrastructures intended to enable transparent, inclusive, and OS-aligned RRA practices. They collectively argue that infrastructures should not be neutral pipes or passive enablers. Instead, they must be actively governed, openly developed, and aligned with the values of the reform movement. This includes adherence to FAIR and CARE principles, public accountability, interoperability with diverse systems, and the capacity to reflect multiple forms of contributions beyond publications—including datasets, software, community engagement, and societal impact.

GraspOS has directly translated these principles into its technical and governance architecture. For instance, the *“Conceptual Architecture for the Implementation of a Responsible Research Assessment Framework Built on Open Infrastructures”* outlines foundational infrastructure properties—such as openness, modularity, interoperability, and co-governance—that GraspOS has embodied in the design of its federated infrastructure model. The *Policy Brief* document, meanwhile, advocates for infrastructures that not only support but also catalyse change, serving as scaffolding for institutions and funders to shift towards more holistic and responsible evaluation practices. This is precisely the role that GraspOS plays through its integration with the SCOPE+i Framework and services like the Openness Profile, the Assessment Protocol Registry, and the Assessment Portfolio.

Moreover, the OI4RRA CoARA WG documents provided a critical assessment of current gaps in the landscape, such as fragmentation, over-reliance on commercial providers, lack of sustainability planning, and the difficulty of achieving cross-institutional comparability. GraspOS responds to these by offering an **open, production-ready, and policy-aligned**

infrastructure that not only addresses current technical needs but is also built for adaptability and scalability across national and disciplinary boundaries.

This deep entanglement with policy work ensures that the exploitation roadmap for GraspOS is not only market-aware but also normatively grounded. The project's results are positioned to become trusted components within the evolving ecosystem of OS infrastructures and RRA implementation pathways in Europe. Additionally, by participating in strategic dialogue with actors from other initiatives (e.g., OPUS, PathOS, SciLake) and co-developing conceptual frameworks that feed into EOSC and CoARA strategies, GraspOS has ensured that its outputs are not developed in isolation but are fully embedded in **coordinated European efforts to reshape research evaluation**.

Ultimately, this policy anchoring positions GraspOS not just as a service provider, but as a reference model for open, ethical, and community-driven infrastructure design. It demonstrates that **responsible infrastructure** is not merely a technical construct, but a governance and policy artefact in its own right—capable of shaping how knowledge is valued, assessed.

5.4.2 Sustainability, Governance, and EOSC Integration

Sustainability

GraspOS's sustainability strategy aligns with the ESFRI report on Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, the EOSC Sustainability Guidelines, and the CoARA WG OI4RRA. These emphasise maintaining the research infrastructure's operation and relevance over time. This includes securing adequate framework conditions, ensuring that Research Infrastructures (RIs) stay at the forefront of science, and maintaining a robust training and education program. Harmonising and integrating data services across RIs, encouraging RIs to become innovation hubs, and demonstrating the societal and economic benefits of RIs are also crucial aspects of sustainability.

GraspOS has developed an exploitation plan to leverage the project's outcomes and propel its objectives forward. The primary aim of GraspOS is to establish a tailored federated infrastructure, serving as a dataspace specifically designed for measuring Open Science indicators within the realm of RRA. The exploitation plan is strategically structured into two distinct but complementary strands, ensuring the successful use of the project's results.

Technical Exploitation Plan: Interoperability and Integration in EOSC

The technical exploitation plan of GraspOS focuses on ensuring the interoperability of its tools and services for RRA while aiming for seamless integration within the EOSC. GraspOS recognises the importance of collaboration with infrastructure and service providers,

including OpenAIRE, OPERAS, and EGI, who share a vested interest in exploiting the services and tools developed throughout the project. To maximise the uptake and impact of the project's outcomes, these partners, along with their extensive networks of over 100 organisations, will play a central role in the operational infrastructure, facilitating broad impact and exploitation.

A key objective of GraspOS is the full integration of its infrastructure into the EOSC through the establishment of an open research assessment dataspace. This integration will ensure the interoperability of GraspOS with diverse CRIS and national providers, enabling seamless data exchange and analysis. By embracing interoperability, GraspOS aims to eliminate silos and promote the harmonisation of research assessment practices across different systems and stakeholders.

In addition, the project will actively collaborate with relevant standardisation bodies and research infrastructures to establish and promote the adoption of open metrics and evaluation practices. By aligning with existing standards and frameworks, GraspOS seeks to facilitate the integration and interoperability of its tools and metrics with other research evaluation systems. This collaborative approach ensures that GraspOS can effectively contribute to the broader research ecosystem and promote consistent and transparent evaluation practices.

By prioritising interoperability and integration within the EOSC, GraspOS not only enhances the value and usability of its tools and services but also fosters a more sustainable e-infrastructure for RRA. Through seamless data exchange, alignment with existing standards, and collaboration with key stakeholders (e.g., the internal Pilots, the CoP, other relevant EU-funded projects, and CoARA), GraspOS aims to make a significant contribution to the advancement of Open Science and the responsible evaluation of research within the European research landscape.

To ensure effective governance and sustainability of the GraspOS project, it is essential to align with the recommendations from the EOSC Financial Sustainability Task Force. The governance structure should include stakeholders representation from the research community, ensuring that EOSC serves researchers' needs. The long-term viability of the GraspOS tools and services will be ensured by the presence of RIs in the project such as OpenAIRE, OPERAS, and EGI who exploit the services, and foster the collaborations and interoperability to better serve the EOSC requirements and the research community expectations.

Tailoring Adoption and Implementation of Open Science Indicators

As part of the exploitation plan, GraspOS recognises the importance of tailoring the adoption and implementation of the Open Science indicators to ensure their effective use. This involves active engagement with various stakeholders and community-driven initiatives to foster ownership and participation in the evaluation process.

To achieve this, GraspOS has been collaborating closely with relevant initiatives for RRA such as CoARA and projects such as OPUS and PathOS. By leveraging the expertise and resources from these initiatives, GraspOS supported the dissemination and adoption of the services and tools developed for RRA. This collaboration had been instrumental in driving the uptake of assessment protocols and metrics within RPOs and RFOs.

GraspOS places a strong emphasis on community engagement and co-design. The project aims to actively involve communities in the co-creation of a dataspace that supports evaluation for individual researchers, research groups, institutions, and systemic stakeholders such as RFOs and policymakers. This participatory approach ensures that stakeholders have a sense of ownership in the evaluation process and that the developed tools align with their specific needs and priorities.

Furthermore, GraspOS prioritises the enhanced participation of relevant stakeholders in the development of indicators for openness profiles within the SCOPE+i Framework. By collaborating with these stakeholders, GraspOS ensures that the indicators accurately reflect the diverse requirements and priorities of the research community. Additionally, the project will continue to exploit the Key results (KERs) in pilot activities, evaluating various parameters across research disciplines, career stages, institutions, and systemic levels. This exploitation of the KER1, as well as the landscape analysis from WP5 and WP2, will generate valuable insights into the framework's effectiveness and contribute to its continuous improvement.

To foster community-based validation, GraspOS has been organising events where policy reports, key initiatives in RRA, pilot activities, best practices, lessons learned, training sessions, and the final report of GraspOS will be shared and discussed. These events serve as platforms for active participation and feedback from the research community, enhancing the project's impact and relevance.

Through tailoring the adoption and implementation of Open Science indicators, active community engagement, and validation processes, GraspOS ensures that its services and tools effectively meet the needs of stakeholders, promote open research practices, and contribute to the advancement of RRA within the research community.

Achieving Impacts Towards Exploitation

To achieve the described impacts towards the exploitation of the GraspOS project's outcomes, the methodology outlined above will be meticulously implemented. The structured approach provided by the Value Builder tool ensures that each KER is developed with a deep understanding of the specific needs and goals of the target stakeholder levels. By engaging stakeholders throughout the development process, the tools and services created will be relevant, practical, and user-friendly.

The pilot testing phase is crucial for validating the effectiveness of the tools in real-world settings. By collecting and incorporating feedback from a diverse range of research environments, the offerings can be refined to better meet the needs of different stakeholders. This iterative process helps create robust, scalable solutions that can be widely adopted across the research community.

The expansion and integration phase will focus on extending the reach of the tools and services, ensuring they are seamlessly integrated with existing research assessment systems and data infrastructures. This will enhance the interoperability and scalability of the solutions, making them accessible to a broader audience and increasing their impact.

Finally, the sustainability and impact monitoring phase will ensure that the tools and services remain relevant and effective over time. By establishing mechanisms for continuous updates and improvements, adaptation to evolving needs and technological advancements can be achieved. Regular monitoring of the long-term impact of the tools will provide valuable insights that can inform future developments and policy reforms, ensuring that the GraspOS project continues to contribute to the advancement of Open Science practices and research assessment.

In conclusion, the GraspOS project, through its structured methodology and alignment with the EOSC sustainability framework, aims to deliver impactful and sustainable solutions that promote Open Science practices across the research community. By ensuring comprehensive stakeholder engagement, rigorous validation, and continuous improvement, the project is committed to achieving significant advancements in research assessment practices and contributing to the broader objectives of the (EOSC).

Conclusions

The DECP has served as a strategic framework for ensuring the visibility, uptake, and sustainability of the GraspOS project outcomes. Throughout the duration of the project, we have implemented a coherent and evolving C&D strategy, aligned with its Open Science mission and the needs of its diverse stakeholders.

GraspOS has successfully built a strong online presence through its dedicated website, active social media channels, monthly newsletters, and a set of training and webinar sessions. The project's participation in and organisation of both internal and external events have further contributed to raising awareness and fostering dialogue around Open Science and RRA. Notably, collaborative efforts with related Horizon Europe projects and policy initiatives have strengthened the project's role in shaping a shared vision for reforming research assessment practices at various levels.

Monitoring data shows that KPIs across communication channels have not only been met but, in several cases, exceeded. This reflects the strong engagement of the project team and partners, as well as the relevance of the project's outputs to the broader research and policy communities.

In parallel, the project has defined a robust exploitation strategy to ensure that its Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are sustained and further developed beyond the project's lifetime. This includes pathways for integration into EOSC, uptake by institutional and national actors, and alignment with key policy frameworks such as CoARA. Exploitation planning was supported by Horizon Results Booster tools and stakeholder feedback from pilots and partners. These efforts will culminate in a tailored roadmap for scaling impact and securing long-term sustainability.

Looking forward, a particular focus in the final phase of the project, where consolidation and legacy-building will be essential, will be the GraspOS Final Conference "Opening Research Assessment", planned for 12-13 November 2025 in Pisa. This high-visibility event will serve as a milestone for the project's dissemination activities, showcasing key results, lessons learned, and forward-looking recommendations to the broader ecosystem of stakeholders.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS website traffic (M12-M31)

	Users	Unique users
M1		
M2		
M3		
M4		
M5		
M6		
M7		
M8		
M9		
M10		
M11		
M12	333	308
M13	425	388
M14	485	423
M15	635	574
M16	449	381
M17	617	555
M18	486	444
M19	492	459
M20	340	307
M21	317	277
M22	675	663
M23	476	434
M24	253	202
M25	487	426
M26	600	536

M27	556	480
M28	427	366
M29	792	695
M30	542	453
M31	591	496

Annex 2. List of articles published on the GraspOS website

List of articles published in the 'Latest updates' section of the website (M3-M31)
News and updates about GraspOS and external initiatives
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GraspOS kickoff meeting 2. NEW: Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment Community on Zenodo 3. GraspOS Landscape Survey on Reforming Research Assessment 4. Roadmap for Open Science approved by the Italian National Research Council 5. CoARA Working Group Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment announced 6. The University of Bologna and the CNR will lead the Italian National Chapter of CoARA 7. Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme Call Now Open: Join the Future of Open Science! 8. Roundup from the EOSC symposium 9. Findings from the GraspOS landscape survey 10. Key takeaways: GraspOS training BIP! Scholar 11. Key takeaways: GraspOS training on Indicators for institutions and the OpenAIRE Monitor 12. Open bibliographic references and the role of OpenCitations 13. Report from the GraspOS Pilot Workshops 14. SSH Pilot Consultation Workshops (call to participate) 15. Vote is open for EOSC Symposium Unconference proposals 16. European Commission Action Plan highlights the role of GraspOS in advancing the research assessment reform 17. Building Roadmaps for the GraspOS Pilots: identifying pathways for service inclusion 18. EOSC projects advancing the research assessment reform 19. EOSC projects enhancing scholarly data interoperability: a joint session at the EOSC Symposium 2024 20. GraspOS: A new approach to research assessment 21. Advancing Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: Progress from the CoARA Working Group OI4RRA 22. Exploring Research Assessment and Open Infrastructures

23. [Reframing Research Assessment: towards a comprehensive framework for Researcher Profiles](#)
24. [Operationalising the transition to Responsible Research Assessment with the Open Science Assessment Framework](#)
25. [WOOC 2025: Call for contribution and participation now open](#)
26. [Assessing Open Science: an overview of the Science Europe survey report](#)
27. [Strengthening the EOSC Federation: the EOSC Winter School 2025](#)
28. [Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment: the CoARA Working Group publishes its first report](#)
29. [Open Science and Research Assessment reform: key priorities in the next ERA Policy Agenda](#)
30. [First edition of the EOSC Federation Handbook now available](#)
31. [CoARA WG OI4RRA: A Conceptual Architecture for Responsible Research Assessment based on Open Infrastructures](#)
32. [Reframing Research Assessment with MyResearchFolio](#)

GraspOS Chats

1. [Thanasis Vergoulis](#)
2. [Giulia Malaguarnera](#)
3. [Ludo Waltman](#)
4. [Janne Pölönen](#)
5. [Francesca Di Donato](#)
6. [Silvio Peroni](#)
7. [Natalia Manola](#)
8. [Carol Delmazo](#)
9. [Chiara Di Giambattista](#)
10. [Zenia Xenou](#)
11. [Kumar Guha and Samuel Scalbert](#)
12. [Serafeim Chatzopoulos](#)

Inside stories from the Pilot studies

1. [Recognition and reward of Open Science practices in research assessment at the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University, Netherlands.](#)
2. [Assessing openness at National level in Finland](#)
3. [Assessment criteria for the Social Sciences and Humanities](#)
4. [Novel methods in responsible research assessment and Open Science evaluation at the University of Eastern Finland](#)
5. [Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment strategies at the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry \(UNIBE\)](#)
6. [Providing insights beyond mainstream research assessment objects in Computer Science](#)
7. [Open Science policy uptake and Responsible Research Assessment at INRAE](#)
8. [CNR, a reform in the making - analysing and supporting career progressions](#)
9. [Rethinking Research Assessment - a comprehensive Researcher profile for a broader and more personalised representation of researchers' contributions to science](#)

Connecting the Dots: Cross-project conversations

1. [EOSC Projects enhancing scholarly data interoperability](#)
2. [The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information – Openness of research information as a prerequisite for research assessment reform](#)
3. [Monitoring Open Science at university level for research assessment](#)
4. [Recognising and rewarding Open Science practices in research\(er\) assessment](#)

Annex 3. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS X account (M2-M31)

	Posts	Followers	Shares	Likes	Impressions	Engagements
M1						
M2	3		27	41	4642	194
M3	5		11	22	1317	98
M4	3	156	35	48	6349	283
M5	7	221	51	61	6807	260
M6	9	247	49	101	9293	415
M7	6	283	42	66	7719	294
M8	2	292	8	18	1312	100
M9	40	375	118	274	16226	1176
M10	16	406	79	120	9215	525
M11	7	423	41	72	6456	339
M12	8	490	25	40	4995	214
M13	10	491	36	78	5024	330
M14	9	524	56	86	8243	535
M15	5	539	18	25	4212	156
M16	8	580	38	60	5638	273
M17	12	623	32	75	4816	311
M18	4	677	10	15		
M19	10	795	33	58		
M20	3	813	1	5		
M21	3	856	7	14		
M22	6	874	40	50		
M23	6	713	24	29		

M24	2	664	9	10		
M25	7	672	32	38		
M26	5	670	14	304		
M27	6	673	14	31		
M28	5	675	10	16		
M29	8	673	11	14		
M30	3	680	11	9		
M31	7	692	10	35		

Annex 4. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS LinkedIn account (M2-M31)

	Posts	Group members	Impressions
M1			
M2	1	data not retrieved	data not available
M3	1	18	data not available
M4	1	30	data not available
M5	2	32	data not available
M6	1	39	data not available
M7	1	41	data not available
M8	1	48	data not available
M9	3	60	600
M10	4	67	2345
M11	4	72	2709
M12	3	90	917
M13	3	90	2441
M14	6	92	1950
M15	3	95	1505
M16	7	103	3020
M17	6	118	2328
M18	3	121	958
M19	4	130	2197
M20	4	132	1266

M21	3	132	1650
M22	6	140	2734
M23	6	153	2357
M24	4	157	1015
M25	5	177	2269
M26	5	191	9052
M27	5	203	5454
M28	6	211	3225
M29	8	228	4914
M30	3	243	3881
M31	7	257	3830

Annex 5. Monthly monitoring of GraspOS Mastodon account (M5-M31)

	Posts	Followers
M1		
M2		
M3		
M4		
M5	1	5
M6	4	21
M7	3	54
M8	2	68
M9	28	99
M10	11	132
M11	7	176
M12	6	180
M13	7	186
M14	8	194
M15	3	195
M16	5	203
M17	6	206

M18	2	209
M19	6	210
M20	4	214
M21	3	214
M22	5	222
M23	5	226
M24	2	229
M25	7	238
M26	5	241
M27	6	247
M28	6	248
M29	8	251
M30	3	263
M31	7	268

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Annex 6. Participation to external events (M2-M31)

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GrasPOS contact	Why ? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
2025														
23-26 September 2025	international event (external)	International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2025)	English	Research communities		Tampere	University of Tampere	https://tpdl2025.github.io/	presentation of 2 research papers	25-26 September 2025	Serafeim Chatzopoulos, Paris Koloveas	Presentation of 2 research papers: (1) From raw affiliations to organization identifiers (2) Can LLMs Predict Citation Intent? An Experimental Analysis of In-context Learning and Fine-tuning on Open LLMs	70	Coming soon
15-17 September 2025	international event (external)	Open Science FAIR 2025	English	Research communities		CERN, Geneva, Switzerland	OpenAIRE	https://www.opensciencefair.eu/	workshop		Thanasis Vergoulis & Angeliki Tzouganatou (also Mary)			
15-17 September 2025	international event (external)	Open Science FAIR 2025	English	Research communities		CERN, Geneva, Switzerland	OpenAIRE	https://www.opensciencefair.eu/	workshop		Thanasis Vergoulis & Stefania Amodeo (also Mary)			
3-5 September 2025	international event (external)	STI ENID 2025	English	Research communities		Bristol	University of Bristol	https://www.stienid2025.org/						
21-22 August 2025	national/local event (external)	Research Service Days 2025	Finnish	Research communities		Tampere	University of Tampere	https://events.tuni.fi/rsd2025-en/	poster	21-22 August, 2025	Anni Tarkiainen, Heikki Laitinen, Katri Rintamäki	Title: Hybrid indicator for assessing the societal interaction of the university	300 persons	Coming soon
21-22 August 2025	national/local event (external)	Research Service Days 2025	Finnish	Research communities		Tampere	University of Tampere	https://events.tuni.fi/rsd2025-en/	special session	21-22 August, 2025	Maria Pietilä, Anni Tarkiainen, Heikki Laitinen, Katri Rintamäki	Title: Open Science as Part of Researcher Evaluation	25 persons	Coming soon
30 June-2 July 2025	international event (external)	Metascience 2025	English	Research communities		London	Center for Open Science and Research on Research Institute	https://metascience.info/						
26-27 June 2025	organisation meeting	2025 Coordination meeting of EOOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe	English	Other	EOOSC ecosystem		EOOSC Association							
15 June 2025	organisation meeting	EOOSC OA5 General meeting	English	Other	EOOSC ecosystem		EOOSC Association							
30 May 2025	organisation meeting	GrasPOS Plenary Meeting	English	Other	GrasPOS Consortium	Bologna	GrasPOS / UNIBO	https://graspos.eu/	GrasPOS Plenary Meeting	30 May 2025. From 9:15 - 16:30 CEST	Thanasis Vergoulis, Lottie Provost (for reporting)	Third plenary meeting of the project. Discussion on project results, next steps, and Exploitation.	30	https://zenodo.org/records/15599833

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional Info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
28-29 May 2025	international event (organised by my organisation)	Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC)	English	Research communities		Bologna	OpenCitations and Barcelona DORI	https://workshop-oc.github.io/						
28-29 May 2025	international event (external)	Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC)	English	Research communities		Bologna	OpenCitations and Barcelona DORI	https://workshop-oc.github.io/	Making Research Software Count:SOFTWARE - A Tool for Recognizing Software in Scholarly Publications	29 May 2025	Samuel Scalber	Presentation of a Tool to Recognise Software in Scholarly Publications	20	https://zenodo.org/records/15601663
27 May 2025	national/local event (organised by my organisation)	Internal Seminar at UEF School of Computing	Finnish	Research communities		Kuopio	University of Eastern Finland	N/A	Presentation	27 May 2025	Anni Tarkiainen	One of several presentations. Objective: presentation of project output: developing quantitative data based indicators for the societal impact of open science	20	/
6-8 May 2025	international event (external)	INORMS Congress	English	Specific end user communities	RPOs, Research support	Madrid, Spain	EARMA and INORMS	https://earma.org/conference/	Researcher Profiles	7-8/05/2025	Giulia Malaguarnera, Zenia Xenou, Lottie Provost, Thanasis Vergoulis	The aim was collect feedback and desires from the Research Admin and Supporting Staff for the requirements on Researcher Profiles services	2200	https://zenodo.org/records/15421941
29 April 2025	virtual event (organised by my organisation)	Introducing the new OpenAIRE Graph API	English	Other	Librarians, Research Admins, Research Institutions, Researchers, Funders, Computer & Data Scientists, Developers	online	OpenAIRE	https://www.openaire.eu/eventdetail/1427/introducing-the-new-openaire-graph-api-enhanced-functionalities-and-real-world-applications	Presentation of new OpenAIRE Graph API	29 April 2025	Thanasis Vergoulis (speaker)	Designed to support bibliometric analyses, research discovery, and Open Science monitoring, the new API offers streamlined access to OpenAIRE's rich research data ecosystem.	73	https://zenodo.org/records/15308796
24 March 2025, 12-13 CET	national/local event (organised by my organisation)	EOSC Finnish Forum webinar about GraspOS benefits for Finnish organisations	English	Research communities		online	CSC, UEF, TSV, EOSC Finnish Forum	https://avointiede.fi/en/events/grasp-os-benefits-finnish-organisations	Introduction to GraspOS, Pilot work related to Research.fi (OpenCitations and Openness)	24 March 2025	liris Liinamaa, Laura Himanen, Joonas Nikkanen, Katri Rintamäki,	- make Finnish stakeholders aware of GraspOS benefits for Finnish Organisations - raise awareness about GraspOS among the Finnish stakeholders	36	https://zenodo.org/records/15267458

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
20-23 January 2025	international event (external)	EOSC Winter School 2025	English	Other	EOSC community, Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC Projects	Seville, Spain	EOSC Association, EOSC Focus project	https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2025/	/	21-22 January 2025	Thanasis Vergoulis, Leonidas Pispiringas, Josefine Nordling, Clifford Tatum	The objective was to raise awareness of European-funded RRA projects and initiatives, and to highlight their relevance to EOSC priorities (MAR pillars). This involved engagement with the Opportunity Area 6 (OA6) working group. Together with OA6 participants, we developed an RRA activity agenda, which has since been adopted.	110	/
2024														
10-11 December 2024	international event (external)	3rd Open Science Symposium in Greece	English	Research communities		Athens, Greece	Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI)	https://www.hellenicopenscience.gr/en/events	GraspOS Enabling the reform towards Responsible Research Assessment	10 December 2024, 17:30	Maria Makaronidou (m.makaronidou@athenarc.gr)	- Update on new Open Science developments in Eur - Update on the operation of the EPAE consortium a - Consultation with the political leadership in order t - Strengthening of skills of new researchers and mar	100	https://zenodo.org/records/14608597
4-6 December 2024	international event (external)	REvaluation Conference	English	Research communities		Vienna, Austria	Reval	https://www.revaluation2024.eu/	Reframing Research Assessment: Towards a comprehensive framework for Researcher Profiles	4 December 2024, 10:30 AM	Lottie Provost, Zenia Xenou	Presentation of the Researcher Profile under development in GraspOS	100	https://zenodo.org/records/14531056
20-22 November 2024	international event (external)	NWB2024 - Nordic Workshop on Bibliometrics and Research Policy	English	Research communities		Reykjavik	University of Iceland	https://nwb2024.hi.is/	Developing a Hybrid Indicator Model for Responsible Research Assessment and Open Science Evaluation (poster)	21 November 2024	Heikki Laitinen, Anni Tarkiainen, Katrin Rintamäki	To tell about GraspOS pilot study and its novel indicator model to make visible societal and open science activities of universities	100	https://zenodo.org/records/14045124
18 November 2024	international event (external)	BEAMING Open Science Clustering event	English	Research communities	researchers, research	Novi Sad, Serbia	University of Novi Sad	https://beamingproject.eu/news/	GraspOS Pilot Activities (panel 2)	18 November 2024, 12.30	Slađana Savić, Ana Đorđević	Presentation of activities related to Open Science realized in Serbia within the framework of the project GraspOS	85	https://zenodo.org/records/14359016
14 November 2024	international event (external)	International Conference Rethinking Research Assessment	English	Research communities	RFOs, RPOs, research	Bucharest, Romania	UEFISCDI	https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/rethinking-research-assessment-conference-0	Enacting change - Research Assessment Practices	14 November 2024	Clifford Tatum	promote GraspOS, OSAF, and the UEFISCDI pilot	100	https://zenodo.org/records/14203202

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
5 November 2024	national/local event (external)	National Open Science day	Serbian	Research communities	researchers, research	Belgrade, Serbia	University of Belgrade	http://www.open.ac.rs/index.php/dan-otvorene-nauke-v	Project, network and initiative - GraspOS	5 November 2024, 13.00	Ana Đorđević	Presentation of activities related to Open Science realized in Serbia within the framework of the project GraspOS	125	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169993
21-23 October 2024	international event (external)	ESOC Symposium 2024	English	EU institutions	service and data providers, researchers, research support staff, policymakers	Berlin, Germany	EOSC Association + EC	https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/#programme	EOSC collaborative frontiers to achieve interoperability and enhance scholarly data	22 October 2024, 11.30	Andrea Mannocci Thanasis and Giulia	alignment with EOSC on services and data interoperability	85	https://zenodo.org/records/14290081
21-23 October 2024	international event (external)	EOSC Symposium 2024	English	Other	service and data providers, researchers, research support staff, policymakers	Berlin, Germany	EOSC Association + EC	https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/#programme	Poster: Redesigning an open infrastructure according to the FAIR principles		Silvio Peroni	Presentation of how the OpenCitations infrastructure complies with FAIR principles	85	N/A
8 October 2024	national/local event (external)	FAIR Impact National Roadshow Romania - Collaborative FAIR Data Practices & Tools	English	Research communities	Research & Academic community in Romania	Online	UEFISCDI - Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding, from Romania.	https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-national-roadshow-romania	Open Science and FAIR Support a national level through UEFISCDI projects	8 October 2024, 10.00	Alina Irimia	Mention of the UEFISCDI pilot in GraspOS and its contribution to UEFISCDI's support for OS.	117	https://zenodo.org/records/13928018
23-24 September 2024	international event (external)	Paris Conference on Open Research	English	Research communities	Policy makers, service and data providers, funders	Paris, France	Sorbonne University and Barcelona Declaration	https://barcelona-declaration.org/conference_2024_paris/	Harmonizing the Barcelona Declaration and CoARA Efforts: Advancing Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment	23.09.2024	Thanasis Vergoulis	CoARA WG on OI4RRA	100	https://zenodo.org/records/13900059

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why ? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
18-20 September 2024	international event (external)	STI conference	English	Research communities	OS, responsible research assessment	Berlin	Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Humboldt-Universität, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies, European Network of Indicator Designers	https://sti2024.org	In search of open science-aware academic career assessments (special session)	20 September 2024	Clifford Tatum, Francesca Di Donato, Janne Polonen	share GraspOS progress & insights	20	https://zenodo.org/records/13981270
12 September 2024	international event (external)	Pubmet2024	English	Industry	Business partners, Publishers	Zadar	University of Zadar	https://pubmet2024.unizd.hr/#	Panel session 2: "Integrity and ethics in research assessment"	12 September 2024, 16:30-18:00	Fotis Mystakopoulos	Overall presentation and involvement of Open Infrastructures in the context of Research Assessment. Specifically mentioned the OS-Aware perspective of RA, using as examples the OpenAIRE Graphs, Open Citations, OPERAS Metrics and PRISM. It was important to demonstrate that by being open and transparent we enhance and support integrity in RA.	60	https://zenodo.org/records/14609139
13 September 2024	international event (external)	Pubmet2024	English	Research communities	Developers, RPOs	Zadar	University of Zadar	https://pubmet2024.unizd.hr/#	"Leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph for Transparent and Responsible Research Assessment", in the session 3 Diverse perspectives on research assessment	13 September 2024, 9:30-11:00	Maja Dolinar (OpenAIRE), supported by Giulia Malaguarnera	Our presentation emphasised the value of open infrastructures like the OpenAIRE Graph, which aggregates and enriches metadata from a variety of trusted sources. This infrastructure allows for a more nuanced assessment of research activities beyond traditional bibliometric indicators, incorporating outputs like data, software, and methods. We highlighted OpenAIRE's role in providing tools for monitoring open science practices and how these can be used by institutions to track research impact, funding collaborations, and the openness of research outputs. The audience showed particular interest in how the OpenAIRE MONITOR service helps organizations measure adherence to open science and research integrity practices, aligning with reforms suggested by frameworks like DORA and CoARA.	70	https://zenodo.org/records/13948106

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
2-6 September 2024	international event (external)	European Summer School in Scientometrics	English	Specific end user communities	Responsible metrics	Vienna	University of Vienna	https://esss.info/	Lowara New Assessment Systems and the Role of Indicators Therein: Where We Are and Where We Are Going / Responsible Metrics	6 September 2024, 10:45-11:15 AM CEST	Janne Polonen	Dissemination of GraspOS landscape survey results	60	https://zenodo.org/records/13711346
4 July 2024	international event (external)	LIBER Conférence	English	Specific end user communities	Librarians; institutions	Cyprus University of Technology	LIBER	https://liberconference.eu/programme/parallel-session-6/	Research libraries at the forefront: empowering Open Science decision making	4 July 2024	Giulla Malaguarnera	The objective was to inform the librarians in the data they provide for research assessment purposes	80	https://zenodo.org/records/12705255
20-21 June 2024	organisation meeting	2024 Coordination meeting EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe	English	Other	EOSC community; INFRAEOSC projects	Brussels, Belgium	EOSC Association				Clifford Tatum, Francesca Di Donato		N/A	
11-13 June 2024	international event (external)	PIDfest conference	english	Research communities	PIDs and open research information community	Prague	Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) & National Library of Technology, Prague, Czech Republic, (NTK)	https://www.pidfest.org/	présentation, leveraging PIDs for Open Science aware RRA	12 June 2024, 11.00 CEST	Clifford Tatum	short presentation on leveraging PIDs for RRA	40	https://zenodo.org/records/12515152
3 June 2024	organisation meeting	Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement WG, monthly meeting	English	Other	EOSC Community; EOSC Association, INFRAEOSC Projects		EOSC Association		National stakeholder engagement in GraspOS	3 June 2024, 13.00 CEST	Lottie Provost	Short presentation of national stakeholder engagement in GraspOS showcasing the 9 pilots	21	https://zenodo.org/records/11482696
2-5 June 2024	international event (external)	WCRI 2024	English	Research communities	Researchers	Megaron Athens International Conference Centre (MAICC)	National Technical University of Athens and National Kapodistrian University of Athens	https://wcri2024.org/	Easing the burden of creating and managing narrative CVs in academia	4 June 2024, 11.00 CEST	Thanasis Vergoulis, Serafeim Chatzopoulos	Poster showcasing the limitations of traditional academic profile, presenting narrative CVs as an alternative, and how they can be supported by the BIP! Scholar's academic profiles.	30	https://zenodo.org/records/11196985
20 May 2024	national/local event (organised by my organisation)	"Reliability, Transparency and Reproducibility" and research assessment	English	Research communities	Researchers	University of Bologna	UNIBO	https://eventi.unibo.it/fundamentals-of-research/reliability-transparency-and-reproducibility	There was no specific contribution, but GraspOS was mentioned in connection with the theme of the event		Silvio Peroni	The event will focus on the ingredients of research methodology, and the ongoing debate around reproducibility of results, also mentioning the role of the GraspOS project.	85	N/A

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why ? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
16 May 2024	organisation meeting	UNIBE pilot activities promotion	Serbian	Research communities	Researchers	University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry	University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry	https://chem.bg.ac.rs/akuiet/biblioteka/index.html	Open Science and GraspOS at the Faculty of Chemistry, special session	16 May 2024 at 10 CEST	Ana Đorđević, Slađana Savić, Aleksa Savić, Mihajlo Kuljić	Presentation of the project's ongoing work on the pilots, the OSAF and the infrastructure at the Faculty.	50	https://zenodo.org/records/11564976
15-17 May 2024	international event (external)	CRIS2024 Conference	English	National authorities	research information management professional, researchers	TU Wien	EuroCRIS	https://cris2024.eurocris.org	Title: Research.fi's researcher profiles supporting the recognition of diversity in research	15 May 2024 at 11:30 CEST	Laura Himanen & Josefine Nordling	Presentation on the project's ongoing work, specifically on the piloting plan of CSC (research.fi) in regard to the Openness Profile being developed in WP2	50	https://dspacecris.eurocris.org/handle/11366/2539
06 May 2024	national/local event (external)	Open Science Communities at UC 2024	Portuguese	Research communities	Researchers	University of Coimbra	University of Coimbra	Open Science Communities at UC 2024	"Reforma da avaliação da investigação: perceções e desafios no âmbito do projeto GraspOS" ("Reform of research evaluation: perceptions and challenges in the context of the GraspOS project") - Invited lecturer	06/05/24 - 10h30 (CEST); 30 minutes for GraspOS	Carol Delmazo	The presentation focused on explaining the main goals of the project and the specific challenges and main discussions going on in the SSH Pilot. It contributed to raising awareness about GraspOS in Portugal.	40	https://zenodo.org/records/11175504
24-26 April 2024	International event (external)	OPERAS Conference	English	Research communities	Publishers, Researchers, Research Infrastructures, Libraries, Funding Agencies, Policy Makers (from an SSH perspective)	University of Zadar	OPERAS Plus	https://operas.eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/	Contextualising Research Assessment for Social Sciences and Humanities: Insights and Challenges from the GraspOS Project Pilot (Presentation)	25/4/2024 - Day 2, Session 4, 14:30 to 16:00 CEST	Fotis	The session will focus on bringing together a discussion on the CoARA efforts which is why it includes presentations on the Multilingualism WG and the Peer-review, as well as a presentation by the Head of Programme for CoARA. The presentation by OPERAS will focus on the context of Responsible Research Assessment in the SSH. The outcomes of this session is a reinforced summary of the challenges the SSH thematic area is facing. GraspOS has a particular interest in finding solutions with its infrastructures for SSH scholars as well.	40	https://zenodo.org/records/11071150

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
25 April 2024	international event (external)	International Scientific Conference: Scientific and Publishing Integrity in Biomedicine	English	Research communities	Researchers	Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje	MAME	https://viadotra68.blogspot.com/2024/04/10.html	Scientific Integrity at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry, in the context of responsible research assessment	25 April 2024 at 13:15 CEST	Ana Dordevic	Reference to Pilot F activities	125	https://zenodo.org/records/11184766
10 April 2024	organisation meeting	EOSC-CoARA workshop	English	Other	EOSC Association, INFRAEOSC projects, CoARA	online			Advancing Research Assessment with a Focus on Open Science	10 April 2024	Clifford Tatum, Francesca Di Donato	Presentation of the project's ongoing work on the pilots, the OSAF, the infrastructure and the community of practice in the EOSC and CoARA workshop	40	https://zenodo.org/records/10965617
14 March 2024	virtual event (external)	OpenAIRE Webinars	Greek	Other	Various stakeholders from Greece & Cyprus interested in Open Science		OpenAIRE		Title: "Advancing Research Assessment with a Focus on Open Science" Type: Webinar	14 March 2024	Thanasis Vergoulis	General presentation of the project to a wide audience of people in Greece & Cyprus interested in Open Science.	50	https://zenodo.org/records/10819526
8 March 2024	virtual event (external)	Workshop Open Science and Education	English	Research communities	communities of scholars from all academic spheres, as well as students, IT trainers or human resources departments	Hybrid (Politehnica University of Timisoara+online)	Politehnica University of Timisoara	https://elearning.uptr.ro/ro/event/open-education-week-workshop-2024/#	National strategic framework for Open Science	8 March 2024	Alina Irimia	Short presentation of GraspOS project	420	
21 February 2024	virtual event (external)	Aurora Open Science Training - Discover and Enhance Collaboration	English	Research communities	PhD candidates, Postdocs, Research Staff	online	VU Amsterdam	https://vu-nl.libcal.com/calendar/universitylibrary/discover-and-enhance-collaboration?fh	Discover and Enhance Collaboration	21 February 2024 at 11 CET	Giulia Malaguarnera	Training for researchers in creating a research profile in BIPIScholar	25	https://zenodo.org/records/10688661
20 February 2024	virtual event (external)	Experiences in Implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science – Online Workshop for National Commissions to Share Good Practices	English	Research communities	UNESCO National Commissions	online (closed meeting)	German and the Netherlands National Commissions for UNESCO and the UNESCO Secretariat	N/A	The White Paper of the Transition to Open Science (2023 2030)	20 February 2024, 14.30 CET	Alina irimia	Short presentation of GraspOS project as part of UEFISCDI's effort to implement/ test Open science practices at national level	30	N/A

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why ? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
29 January - 1 February 2024	organisation meeting	EOSC Winter School 2024	English	Other	Chairs of EOSC-A taskforces, INFRAEOSC projects, members of the WG on C&E in Horizon Europe	Thessaloniki, Greece	EOSC Association	https://eosc.eu/eosc-fcus-project/winter-school-2024/	"GraspOS project" presentation at O5 on Research Curricula, Skills, Training and Rewards	30 January 2024 (afternoon session)	Leonidas Psiringas will represent GraspOS	Inform the EOSC community about the infrastructure for OS on development in GraspOS	20	https://zenodo.org/records/10807919
2023														
23 November 2023	international event (external)	EuroCRIS strategic meeting	English	National authorities	Research information systems managers, decision makers	Pamplona, Spain	euroCRIS	https://meeting.eurocris.org/	The analysis of the available software infrastructures for supporting research assessment reform	23 November, 9:40-10:00 am CET	Dragan Ivanovic	Presentation of D2.1	50	https://zenodo.org/records/10807919
10 November 2023	national/local event (external)	Krecon2023, Annual Knowledge, Research, Education Conference	English	National authorities	RFOs and RPOs	Prague, Czech Republic	National Library of Technology	https://krecon.cz/event/6/	Panel Discussion: The Future of Research(er) Assessment	10 November, 2023	Clifford Tatum	Introduced OSAF, as context for remarks on the future of research(er) assessment	85	N/A
26-27 October 2023	international event (external)	Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2023	English	Research communities		Bologna, Italy	OpnCitations (University of Bologna)	https://workshop-oc.github.io/	title: BIP! Services: Demonstrating the Potential of Open Scholarly Data in Research Assessment	27 October 2023	Thanasis Vergoulis		100	https://zenodo.org/records/10046470
23-25 October 2023	national/local event (external)	GenOA Week "Community over commercialisation"	Italian	Research communities	RPOs	Genova, Italy (Hybrid)	Università di Genova, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, CNR, e Associazione Italiana Biblioteche - Sezione Liguria	https://openscience.unige.it/genOAweek2023	Engaging with research communities to advance research assessment: the case of GraspOS	23 October 2023	Lottie Provost	presentation of the project's objectives, pilot activities, CoP and CoARA WG OI4ARRA	200	https://zenodo.org/records/10036386

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
23-25 October 2023	international event (external)	19th European Computer Science Summit "Informatics: Shaping the Future"	English	Research communities	summit for the leadership of the Informatics research community in Europe	Edinburgh, Scotland	Informatics Europe	https://www.informatics-europe.org/ecss/home.html#:~:text=ECSS%202023%20will%20be%20held,informatics%3A%20Shaping%20the%20Future%22	1h30 session on evaluation in Informatics	25 October 2023,	Laurent Romary	presentation of Pilot G	100	https://zenodo.org/records/10048099
20 October 2023	organisation meeting	RAID advisory group meeting	English	Other		Salzburg, Austria	RAID		Overview of GraspOS	20 October 2023	Clifford Tatum	present the project and the OSAF, the Open and Federated Research Assessment Infrastructure and the pilots		https://zenodo.org/records/10374861
10 October 2023	virtual event (external)	FAIR-IMPACT Roadshow in Serbia	English	Research communities	Researchers Rectors & Decision makers	Serbian institution will facilitate, but it is a virtual event	University of Belgrade University of Novi Sad OpenAIRE NOAD in Serbia / OS Community in Serbia	https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roads-hows/open-science-and-research-data-management-policies-serbia	Assess the status of OS practices and regulations in Serbia, leveraging on some current initiatives. Showcase FAIR-IMPACT opportunities. Debate around challenges still to be addressed by the research community there by inviting researchers	October 10th, 11am CEST	Dragan Ivanovic	Presentation of the WP2 landscape analyzes	50	https://zenodo.org/records/10101845
27-29 September 2023	international event (external)	STI 2023. 27th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators, 2023	English	Research communities		Leiden, Netherlands	CWTS	https://www.sti2023.org/	special session "Implement evaluation reform"	28 September 2023, 14.30-15.45 CEST	Janne Polonen, Francesca Di Donato		350	https://zenodo.org/records/8422634
20-22 September 2023	international event (external)	EOSC Symposium 2023 "EOSC contributions to Research Assessment"	English	Other	EOSC ecosystem	Madrid, Spain	EOSC Future project	https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/	EOSC contributions to Research Assessment"	21 September 2023, 12.00-13.00 CEST	Giulia Malaguarnera		70	https://zenodo.org/records/10001016

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
5 September 2023	international event (external)	OAI13 - A case study: OpenCitation	English	Research communities		online	CERN; University of Geneva	https://oai.events.oai13.org/	A case study: OpenCitations, an open science infrastructure seeking long-term sustainability	5 September 2023, 16:30-17 CEST	Chiara Di Giambattista			https://zenodo.org/record/8389945
28 August 2023	national/local event (external)	"GraspOS - monimuotoisuutta tutkimuksen arviointiin"	Finnish/suomi	National authorities	Higher Education administration, ministry	Tampere, Finland	Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture	https://okm.fi/tapahtumat/2023-08-28/korkeakoulujen-kota-seminari	Presentation "GraspOS - diversifying research assessment"	28 August 2023, 13.30-13.45 EEST	Laura Himanen	Presentation on how the pilot work with research.fi aims at enabling the consideration of open science in research assessments.	70	https://zenodo.org/records/10101485
5 July 2023	international event (external)	Communication of Science and Literature in the multiverse	English	Research communities	Researchers and citizens	Aegina, Greece	Hellenic Open University	https://www.stgs.fau.de/7th-international-workshop-communication-of-science-and-literature-in-the-multiverse/	Ana Djordjevic participates in the lecture "Communication in the Multiverse of a Library" and will also present GraspOS Pilot F activities.	5 July 2023, 11.50-12.10 EEST	Ana Djordjevic	Presentation of open science in Serbia and Pilot F activities	30	https://zenodo.org/record/8180518
2 July 2023	international event (external)	Tutorial "Transitioning towards Open Scientometrics with Open Science Graphs" at ISSI conference 2023	English	Research communities	scientists, research managers, authorities and information professionals	Bloomington, Indiana, USA	Indiana University	https://cns-iu.github.io/workshops/2023-07-02_issi/#about	Tutorial scientific knowledge graphs for open research assessment workflows		Thanasis Vergoullis, Andrea Mannocci			https://zenodo.org/record/8194556
19-23 June 2023	international event (external)	EGI Conference	English	Research communities	international scientific communities, computing and service providers, European projects, security experts, community managers, and policy makers	Poznan, Poland	EGI	https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2023/	Poster presentation (mentioning GraspOS)		Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenCitations)			https://zenodo.org/record/8116350

Date	Events	Name of the event	Language	Target	Target additional info	Venue	Main organiser	Website	Title + Type of participation	Day and time of contribution	GraspOS contact	Why? Description of the objective(s)	Outreach	Link to the presentation/slides
15-16 June 2023	organisation meeting	2023 Coordination meeting EOSC-related projects	English	Other	EOSC ecosystem	Brussels, Belgium	EOSC Association		presentation GraspOS (10 mins)		Thanasis Vergoulis, Clifford Tatum			
7 June 2023	organisation meeting	ACM Publication Board Meeting	English	Specific end user communities	Publishers	San Francisco, US	ACM				Natalia Manola	Presentation of CS Open Science profile	15	
5 June 2023	national/local event (external)	ITAEOESC-2023 Italian Tripartite Assembly for the EOSC National event		Other	EOSC ecosystem	Rome, Italy	EOSC Association	https://eosc.eu/events/national-tripartite-event-italy	Poster to present GraspOS pilots D and G		Francesca Di Donato, Lottie Provost			https://zenodo.org/record/8099022
28 May - 1 June 2023	international event (external)	Extended Semantic Web Conference 2023	English	Research communities		Hersonissos, Greece	https://2023.eswc-conferences.org/organising-committee/	https://2023.eswc-conferences.org/	GraspOS/Sci Lake contribution: 1 min presentation and participation to the interactives Posters and demos session		Thanasis Vergoulis, Serafeim Chatzopoulos			https://zenodo.org/record/7984968#Z1HdarexBzPY
31 May - 1 June 2023	organisation meeting	Spring 2023 euroCRIS Membership meeting	English	National authorities		Brussels, Belgium		https://eurocris.org/eurocris-events	Presentation		Laura Himanen	Responsible research assessment principles for research information management (Preliminary results of the initial analysis on Pilot A)	50	https://meeting.eurocris.org/CS-C2.pdf
21-22 March 2023	virtual event (external)	Open Science Retreat - Reform on Research Assessment in the context of Open Science	English	Research communities		online	The ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	https://openscienceretreat.zbw.eu/		21 March 2023 13-15 PM and 22 March 2023 13-15 PM	Francesca di Donato, Ana Đorđević		30	https://openscienceretreat.zbw.eu/review/
15 March 2023	virtual event (external)	Indicators for Open Research	English	Research communities		online	UK Reproducibility Network	https://www.ukrn.org/event/or-indicators-mar23/	presentation		Janne Pölonen	presentation of GraspOS project		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752573
24-25 February 2023	international event (external)	MCAA Annual Conference 2023 - Parallel session: "Translating research assessment into practice"	English	Research communities	Beneficiaries of MSCA	Cordoba, Spain (hybrid)	Marie Curie Alumni Association	https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/conference-2023	invitation to a Panel Discussion on Research Assessment	25 February 2023 11-12 AM	Giulia Malaguarnera	dissemination and awareness about the goal of the project	80	https://next.brella.io/events/mcaa/schedule/480742

Annex 7. CSC Pilot Story

Recognising Open Science in a National CRIS

CSC – IT Center for Science is leading a piloting activity to recognise Open Science contributions in research assessment. Focusing on the national research information service Research.fi, this pilot explores how a national CRIS (Current Research Information System) can support more responsible and open-science aware evaluation practices.

Research.fi is a service offered by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture that collects and disseminates information on research conducted in Finland. Currently, Research.fi contains information on the Finnish research system, publications by Finnish organisations, projects funded by public and private research funders, information on researchers operating in Finland and their research activities, and statistical information on the development of research resources and impact.

THE CHALLENGE

Open Science is a cornerstone of the evolving European research landscape, but integrating Open Science into research assessment practices remains complex. Research information management plays a crucial role in research assessment, yet existing assessment frameworks often overlook discipline-specific and sectoral differences, and tend to underrepresent the wide range of research activities that underpin science.

Responsible research assessment principles emphasise the importance of recognising diversity in research activities and practices, as well as prioritising qualitative assessment, and avoiding

inappropriate use of metrics and indicators. Unfortunately, the documents guiding the reform on research assessment (i.e. Agreement on reforming research assessment, DORA, Metric Tide, Leiden Manifesto) offer very little guidance on how to collect new types of information to support the assessment of diverse activities and practices, even less on how to utilise new types of information in assessments. Hence, a lot of development work needs to be done to define what these new types of activities and practices could be, how can information on these new types of activities and practices be collected in a reliable way, and finally, how can new types of

information be stored and used in a meaningful way. To tackle this challenge, it is essential to find ways of highlighting competence and real effort, looking beyond standard metrics on open access publications, and without adding to researchers' administrative burden.

OBJECTIVES

This Pilot operated in the wider context of research information management, with the general objective to answer questions such as which aspects of Open Science should be shown on a national, organisational, sectoral or individual level and why. On a more specific level, the aims were to adopt and adapt the Openness Profile to the Research.fi service, to enrich its metadata and support the improvement of indicators and metrics, and to co-shape APIs of the Open Research Assessment Infrastructure.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The pilot was led by Laura Himanen at CSC, with support from Iliris Ruoho and Maari Alanko. It included collaboration with the Research.fi Steering Group, which brings together representatives of Finnish research-performing, funding, and supporting organisations, by collecting their views and experiences regarding their needs for more Open Science-aware evaluation.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The concept of Openness Profile gained a lot of interest during the piloting, especially from researchers who are active in advancing Open Science and who would like to be credited for it. The question is how to highlight competence and real effort, looking beyond standard metrics on open access publications, and without adding to researchers' administrative

burden.

On a theoretical level, the pilot contributed to widening researchers' and funders' understanding of Open Science as a merit, helping to distinguish between what constitutes true merit and what is merely compliance with external requirements. It also contributed to highlighting that simply opening an output should not be the focus; rather, it is essential to find ways to recognise and respect capabilities and competencies in Open Science.

The pilot further helped realise that recognition of Open Science practices is highly context-dependent, and reflects the level of maturity of Finnish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) in regard to Open Science. As a consequence, service providers like Research.fi need to continue to dig deeper into new data sources to be able to support a more diverse idea of what should be included in an Openness profile.

On a technical level, the pilot tested the coverage and reliability of OpenCitations' data in reference to the publication data of a national-level research information system. While the integration of services like OpenCitations is still under discussion, the pilot has improved technical readiness and policy understanding. The Research.fi data model has been developed and enriched with relations, which will allow for more diverse information to be added to the Research.fi database in the future and inform broader European initiatives to include Open Science contributions in research assessment.

In summary, both piloted services have underlined the need to reflect on the purpose of collecting and disseminating research information, and on the potential outcomes and uses of such information in

Annex 8 Characterisation Table per Services (Extension of KER 2)

KER 2 - GraspOS services & Tools Characterisation Table for KER

Athena Research Center (ARC)

Responsible: Serafeim Chatzopoulos schatz@athenarc.gr

BIP! CITATION CLASSIFIER

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Researchers and research evaluators often consider citation-based impact indicators to measure scientific impact, but many citations, especially from Computer Science conferences and workshops, are not reported in common citation data sources like Crossref or OpenCitations. Additionally, citation intent (why a paper is cited) is often missing, which limits a deeper understanding of the research impact.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Customers have relied on general citation metrics that do not account for citation intent. Some platforms, such as Scite, provide citation intent classification but are either proprietary or not fully integrated into workflows like the BIP! ecosystem.
Unique Selling Point (USP) - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifies missing citations: Extracts citations not reported by major data sources, specifically for publications without DOIs (e.g., from the Digital Bibliography & Library Project (DBLP) for Computer Science conferences). 2. Text analysis-based extraction: Uses advanced text analysis techniques to derive citation information directly from manuscripts. 3. Citation intent annotation: Offers automated intent-based annotation for

Topic	Description	Your input
		citations, supporting a deeper understanding of citation purpose.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The BIP! Citation Classifier extends citation data by identifying missing citations from conference and workshop articles (common for several Computer Science workshops and conferences) that lack DOIs. It collects relevant data from DBLP and uses text analysis techniques to extract citation information directly from the full text of the manuscripts. Additionally, It uses large language models (LLMs) to assign citation intents (background, method, results comparison) to each reference in a publication, enabling more nuanced impact analysis.
"Market" Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Researchers and bibliometricians analyzing citation trends and intent. Platforms aggregating research metrics.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers and bibliometricians in Computer Science who require accurate and complete citation data for their research. • Research impact platforms and tools that need comprehensive citation information.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include platforms like Scite (proprietary), and Semantic Scholar (open). Scite offers a well-established framework but is proprietary and not fully open for integration. Semantic Scholar provides APIs and open access but does not include papers without DOIs, which are a key focus of the BIP! NDR (NoDoiRefs) Dataset. The BIP! Classifier stands out by being open, integrated, and specifically designed for

Topic	Description	Your input
		citation intent classification within the BIP! ecosystem.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The tool can be deployed as a software library to retrieve and annotate citation data from a set of manuscripts.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The tool is under development in its early stages, and will be released and continue to be developed in the context of Graspos.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! NDR WORKFLOW

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	The creation and maintenance of datasets like BIP! NDR requires a systematic and automated approach. Without a dedicated workflow, the process of extracting, cleaning, and updating citation data is time-consuming, error-prone, and difficult to scale.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Customers have relied on manual or semi-automated processes to extract and clean citation data from open-access papers. These methods are labor-intensive, prone to inconsistencies, and lack the scalability required to process large datasets.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	The BIP! NDR Workflow is an open-source software solution that automates the process of extracting, cleaning, and updating citation data from open-access computer science papers without DOIs. It ensures consistency, scalability, and reproducibility, enabling researchers and institutions to maintain and expand the BIP! NDR Dataset efficiently. Its modular design allows for easy customization and integration into existing workflows.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The BIP! NDR Workflow is an open-source software tool designed to automate the creation and maintenance of the BIP! NDR Dataset. It includes modules for extracting citation data from open-access papers, cleaning and normalizing the data, and updating the dataset. The workflow is implemented in Python and is available on GitHub for use and further development by the community.

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	The target market includes: 1. Researchers and bibliometricians who need to create or maintain citation datasets, 2. Institutions and organizations interested in developing tools for bibliometric analysis, 3. Developers and data scientists working on citation analysis tools.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Researchers and developers in computer science who need to automate the creation and maintenance of citation datasets for bibliometric studies.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include general-purpose data extraction and cleaning tools, as well as proprietary bibliometric software. While these tools may offer flexibility and advanced features, they are not tailored to the specific needs of extracting and processing citation data from papers without DOIs. The BIP! NDR Workflow is specialized for this purpose and is open-source, making it accessible and customizable.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The workflow is made available as an open-source software project on GitHub. Users can download, customize, and integrate it into their own workflows. It is also distributed through Zenodo for easy access and citation.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The workflow is already available on GitHub and Zenodo as of its publication date, and will receive several updates until the end of the project.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! RANKER

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	BIP! Ranker addresses the need for a scalable, easily expandable, and customizable library to compute citation-based impact indicators. Traditional systems are either proprietary or offer limited configurability, in terms of the range of indicators that they support.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Not aware of other libraries offering the same functionality. Yet, traditional citation metrics can be retrieved from various scholarly databases such as Scopus/Web of Science, OpenAlex etc.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	BIP! Ranker is an open-source, easily expandable library that computes a variety of citation-based indicators on top of a given citation network. It is carefully designed to handle large-scale citation datasets efficiently, using a distributed paradigm. It is also easy to be integrated into existing analysis workflows, making it versatile for various use cases.

Topic	Description	Your input
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	BIP! Ranker is a distributed open-source library for computing a wide range of citation-based impact indicators for publications. BIP! Ranker is a powerful tool for bibliometric analysis since it computes diverse impact indicators (such as influence, popularity, and impulse), offering flexibility, scalability, and transparency.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Researchers and software engineers developing bibliometric methods. Policymakers and funding bodies using citation analysis to drive decisions.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Researchers and software engineers that want to compute a wide range of impact indicators on top of a given citation network. Additionally, it can be of use for communities advocating for transparency in bibliometric analysis.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Established tools that offer citation metrics (e.g., Scopus), or other platforms focusing on capturing the social media attention of publications (e.g., Altmetric).
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	BIP! Ranker is an open source software library that users can integrate into their workflows. It can be deployed locally or on distributed environments for large-scale analysis.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Service already in production phase, used to compute citation-based impact indicators for BIP! DB.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! SCHOLAR INDICATORS CALCULATOR

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	The current tools for assessing research impact primarily focus on traditional citation indicators, such as citation counts and h-index, which provide limited perspectives of a researcher's true impact. Researchers, and institutions lack tools to compute, explore, and showcase diverse dimensions of impact.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Traditionally, customers have relied on citation-based tools (like Google scholar, Scopus) that focus on simple, yet popular citation-based indicators. Additionally, researchers often extract insights from raw citation data to compile reports, which is time consuming and can be inconsistent.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative</i>	BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator goes beyond simple metrics to assess research impact, by providing a multi-dimensional impact view of research outputs. In particular, it offers advanced citation-based impact indicators capturing diverse aspects of

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	impact such as popularity, influence and impulse.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator is a software library that aggregates diverse citation-based impact indicators on the researcher level.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Software engineers that want to compute researcher-level indicators.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Software engineers
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Unknown; not aware of an open-source library that aggregated impact indicators for researchers.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	This library is already available on production through BIP! Scholar.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The library is In production phase with frequent updates to be delivered until the end of the project.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! DB

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	The growth rate of the number of published scientific articles is constantly increasing. At the same time, many of them are of low impact and may contain research of questionable quality. Consequently, identifying the most valuable articles for a given topic has become a tedious task.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Commercial platforms like Scopus, Web of Science, and Dimensions that offer citation metrics and analytics. Such databases typically have expensive subscription fees especially for their premium features.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her</i>	BIP! DB is based on citation network analysis and offers five useful impact indicators, which capture three distinct aspects of scientific impact. These indicators can be used by various applications in the field of scholarly data

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	management (e.g., scholarly search engines, researcher profiles etc).
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	BIP! DB is an multi-disciplinary open dataset that contains various citation-based impact indicators, calculated for more than 200M scientific products.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Platforms that allow exploration and provide insights for scholarly content.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Individual researchers or software engineers that want to extract and visualise/provide insights for scholarly data.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Altmetric, Dimensions, Scopus/Web of Science
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	BIP! DB is a dataset already available through BIP! Services and OpenAIRE Graph.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The database is currently available for use (and download through Zenodo), with ongoing updates until the end of the project.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! NDR

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Many scientific papers, particularly those from computer science conferences and workshops, lack DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers). As a result, their citations are not included in established citation datasets like OpenCitations and Crossref, limiting the scope of citation analysis and bibliometric studies. This creates a gap in understanding the impact of these papers and their contributions to the scientific community.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Customers have relied on datasets like Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) in the past, which provided substantial coverage of citation data, including papers without DOIs. However, with the discontinuation of MAG, there is currently no comprehensive solution addressing this issue.

Topic	Description	Your input
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	BIP! NDR provides a unique dataset that includes citations from open-access conference and workshop papers in computer science that lack DOIs. This dataset fills the gap left by the discontinuation of MAG and complements existing citation datasets by focusing on a previously neglected subset of research outputs. It enables more comprehensive citation analysis and bibliometric studies, particularly for researchers and institutions in computer science.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	BIP! NDR is a dataset that includes citations extracted from open-access conference and workshop papers in computer science that do not have DOIs. It provides researchers and institutions with a resource to analyze the impact of these papers, which are often excluded from traditional citation datasets.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	The target market includes: 1. Researchers and bibliometricians conducting citation analysis and impact studies in computer science, 2. Institutions and organizations interested in evaluating the impact of research outputs without missing potentially important works that are omitted by established sources.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Researchers and bibliometricians in computer science who rely on citation data for their studies and analyses.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include established citation datasets like OpenCitations and Crossref. Their strength lies in their comprehensive coverage of papers with DOIs and their mature infrastructure.

Topic	Description	Your input
		However, they do not include citations from papers without DOIs, which is the unique focus of BIP! NDR.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The dataset has been made available as an open-access resource through Zenodo and will be integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph and BIP! Services.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The dataset is already available on Zenodo as of its publication date, and will receive regular updates until the end of the project.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Owned by ARC

BIP! SCHOLAR

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate</i>	Researchers struggle to showcase the academic (and societal) impact of their research due to (over-)reliance on publication lists accompanied by traditional impact indicators (e.g., the h-index).

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Researchers manually compile CVs, which is a time-consuming task, and prone to inconsistencies. On top of that, these reports often lack context around citation impact and they have limited space to present narratives or any qualitative insights.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	BIP! Scholar assists researchers to showcase multiple aspects of their impact by combining advanced citation-based impact (quantitative) indicators with components offering a qualitative overview. Its key features can be summarised as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Innovative citation-based impact indicators that showcase research impact from different perspectives. ● Integration of narrative CVs to assist researchers in writing a structured description of their contributions and achievements. ● Customizability by offering several profile templates, allowing users to tailor profiles for specific audiences. ● Present research impact in an intuitive way, making it easier to communicate it to broader audiences.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	BIP! Scholar is a product designed to create detailed profiles for researchers, showcasing both quantitative and qualitative information of their research. It streamlines the process of creating a researcher profile following the latest guidelines for responsible research assessment.

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Individual researchers (including early-career, senior, and interdisciplinary researchers).
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Individual researchers.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Google Scholar, Scopus, Altmetric, Aminer. Well-known and established approaches that primarily are based on quantitative indicators but do not consider qualitative elements and broader societal contributions.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	BIP! Scholar is a service that is already available to users via the BIP! Services platform.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Service is already in production phase, with frequent updates (based on feature requests) to be planned until the end of the project.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Owned by ARC; includes existing expertise in citation analysis resulting in citation-based impact indicators, and software development.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	All novel components, including impact indicator visualisations, as well as components for supporting qualitative aspects are owned by ARC.

OPERAS

Responsible: Fotis Mystakopoulos fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org;

OPERAS METRICS

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Monitoring Open Access books. While there are alternatives, this is a free option and customisable. Potential users are publishers of open access books as well as libraries and individual researchers. Understanding how an Open Access book performs, not just via citations but also through alternative metrics is crucial to realise its impact.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	They rely on closed/proprietary databases to do the monitoring for them. It takes away the power from individuals to know about the impact of their OA Books. Less opportunities compared to the diverse metrics included in OPERAS Metrics
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	Currently, Provides independence and opportunities to track performance of OA books across multiple platforms, and it's all in one solution. USPs include: All in one solution: You can source data from many platforms and display them in one widget, so that simplifies where and how to gather data on usage and impact. The innovation is that you can see which platforms deliver which metrics to ensure understanding

Topic	Description	Your input
		<p>on where your users access the resource.</p> <p>It applies open science principles, and the database that supports these activities is open and accessible via APIS and crucially, for the customer it costs less to install this solution and is far more sustainable</p> <p>By installing OPERAS Metrics, Funders can better know how research they are funding is translated into readership and reach across many research communities. And they can also be better informed on which research receives attention to better evaluate their funding priorities.</p>
Description	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>OPERAS Metrics offers a database of usage and impact information of published Open Access books. Designed with the nuanced needs of Social Sciences and Humanities in mind, this service consolidates diverse data sources into a single, transparent interface. Metrics is not only displayed for the publisher's website, but also aggregated with those of other sites where a book is available.</p>
"Market" Target market	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>OPERAS Metrics is designed to serve and support the following target markets:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Publishers: using Metrics they understand where and how their books are read. As such they know if their books are used in specific regions, and by how many people. Books take a lot of time to accumulate citations, and alternative metrics can draw a clear picture of the attention it receives. 2) Libraries: libraries can use the data from altmetrics to

Topic	Description	Your input
		<p>understand usage of certain books to better curate their collections.</p> <p>3) Researchers: Individual researchers could showcase the reach and impact of their work.</p>
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Private and Institutional (e.g. University) publishers have adopted the OPERAS metrics as they already have Open Access books in their catalogues and they are now able to monitor performance of OA Books.
"Market" Competitors	- <i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some competitors include key services in the book publishing area: • Book Citation Index (Web of Science) • PlumX • Altmetrics (Digital Science) • OpenAlex <p>They are more established with more rich data and citation counts. The weaknesses are that are subscription services with a lot of opaque practices on how they gather and manage data which does not help with transparency. More specifically, the Book Citation Index, as a commercial database, indexes legacy publishers, prioritising English Language creating an issue for books in non-english language.</p>
Go to Market - Use model	Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement,	<p>Comprehensive Data Collection: usage metrics collected from various sources, providing a clear picture of open access book impact.</p> <p>Centrally-Managed Database: metrics on open access books stored in a central database that can be accessed by anyone.</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
	contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.	<p>Open Source and Community-Driven: based on open-source principles, offering an alternative to proprietary usage metrics services and emphasising community involvement.</p> <p>Transparent Processing: individual metrics comes with explanations of the data source and collection methods.</p> <p>Designed for SSH Disciplines: tailored to better serve the SSH domain, often underrepresented in metric systems.</p> <p>Widget: metrics can be visually displayed via any site, facilitating real-time interaction and analysis.</p> <p>Flexible Hosting Options: option for publishers to host the service themselves, with dedicated support.</p>
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	OPERAS Metrics is already TRL9 and available for use.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Background is the code available in Github. Code includes in Translation service and widget for displaying data.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Foreground is the data and API scripts produced as part of the project.

PRISM

Topic	<i>Description</i>	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Articulating the peer review process for a diverse list of publishers, open access books and across many disciplines is a massive challenge. PRISM provides a standardised route for all publishers and open access books to transparently display their peer review process.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	We believe there is no solution such as this at the moment for indexing platforms to possibly demonstrate Peer Review practices. Publishers often describe what the peer review process may be associated with their publishing practices but not necessarily in a visible way as the PRISM offers.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	PRISM provides a standardisation of Peer Review practices, contributing to the transparency of the quality assurance process for each book. How a book is peer reviewed matters in terms of assessment of each quality and value, and therefore, this transparent tool provides all publishers, not only the ones that have prestige and legacy, but also smaller publishers, to demonstrate their good practices.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM) gives publishers the opportunity to display information about their peer review procedures in a standardised way as part of the book's metadata in the Directory of Open Access Books. PRISM contributes to building trust in Open Access book publishing by improving transparency around the quality assurance process.

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	PRISM fills a specific gap in the quality assurance process for Open Access Books. The primary target is that of publishers. Publishers can adopt PRISM when indexing their books in DOAB, and as such showcase the quality assurance process of their output. Ultimately, librarians, researchers and discovery platforms, as well as repositories can benefit from PRISM metadata as they can help individuals assess the quality of books, and also platforms can display information of books that have adopted PRISM.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Publishers that are part of the Directory of Open Access Books.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Not to our knowledge. No similar tools for books exist.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	Controlled Vocabulary: standardised set of terms to describe the peer review processes, promoting consistency, clarity, transparency and trust. Title-Level Detail: provision of specific information about the peer review practices applied to each Open Access book, directly on the DOAB platform. Catalogue-Level Overview: ability to apply across a publisher's entire catalogue, showcasing the peer review processes that their titles undergo. API Integration: accessibility to PRISM data through the DOAB API, allowing for inclusion in library databases and search tools.

Topic	Description	Your input
		Widget: possibility for publishers to use the widget on their webpages to show PRISM records about their catalogues or titles.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	PRISM is already TRL9 and available for use.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Code for PRISM Widget available in Github. Option to display PRISM information to a website.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Data and API Scripts produced as part of the project.

OpenAIRE

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OPENAIRE IIS TEXT MINING MODULES

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Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Information Inference Service (IIS) is a flexible data processing system for handling big data based on Apache Hadoop technologies. Its main goal is to provide data/text mining functionality. It allows metadata extraction from PDF documents, performing documents classification, finding references between different kinds of research products, projects and organisations.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Running individual tools to address each specific aspect of information inference

Topic	Description	Your input
		without having a coherent system organised with predefined workflows responsible for different aspects of inference mining.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	Taking advantage of a distributed, multi-node and scalable computational cluster to perform big data analysis involving Text Data Mining algorithms focusing on a specific inference mining tasks. The source code is open source, available under Apache 2.0 licence and publicly available on GitHub .
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	IIS is a service, developed and maintained by ICM, encapsulating various mining modules including TDM modules based on the MadIS framework, an extensible relational database system, developed by ARC.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Researchers, content providers, funders, and policy makers
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	The product is already available on the market.
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are</i>	Unknown.

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	IIS is meant to be installed within the hadoop ecosystem and fed with the data coming from external sources. It is based on oozie workflows split into importing, processing and exporting component groups from which importing and exporting workflows need to be aligned with a given customer needs to populate the data and to obtain the mining outcome.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Already in use in a production environment as a part of OpenAIRE.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Knowledge Graph - Information Inference System (IIS) and its text-mining components were developed by OpenAIRE, ARC, and ICM prior to the project, under the Apache 2.0 license. The Background has been made available for use in the project in accordance with the terms agreed in the Consortium Agreement. Further details can be found at https://github.com/openaire/iis .
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	Not applicable

OPENAIRE OBSERVATORY

Giulia Malaguarnera and Ioanna Grypari

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Understanding and monitoring the global adoption and impact of Open Science practices remains a significant challenge for institutions, funders, and policymakers. The lack of standardized metrics and transparent methodologies often makes it difficult to assess the progress of Open Science initiatives effectively.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Many organizations rely on fragmented, manual approaches to track Open Science adoption, such as isolated surveys, limited bibliometric analyses, or proprietary tools. These methods fail to provide a comprehensive, standardized, and regularly updated overview of Open Science practices.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	The Open Science Observatory offers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized Metrics: Based on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, enabling consistent tracking of Open Science adoption. • Global Insights: Aggregates and harmonizes data from trusted sources worldwide to provide a comprehensive view. • Customizable Dashboards: Tailored views for institutions, countries, and thematic areas. • Open Science Alignment: Integrates with OpenAIRE's ecosystem, ensuring transparency and interoperability.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation,</i>	The Open Science Observatory is a platform designed to provide stakeholders with actionable insights into the adoption and impact of Open

Topic	Description	Your input
	<p><i>publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>Science practices globally. Leveraging data from the OpenAIRE Graph and other trusted sources, the Observatory offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FAIR-compliant metrics to monitor the progression of Open Science initiatives. ● Visualizations of Open Science trends across countries, disciplines, and funding programs. ● Indicators measuring Open Access compliance, FAIR data principles, and policy alignment. <p>The Observatory's methodology ensures that the data and metrics adhere to standardized, open practices, enabling stakeholders to rely on accurate, transparent, and actionable insights.</p> <p>Assess</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policy Tracking: Monitor the implementation of Open Science policies at national and institutional levels. ● Global Comparisons: Benchmark countries and regions based on Open Science adoption metrics. ● Impact Metrics: Evaluate the societal, academic, and economic impacts of Open Science practices. ● Dynamic Updates: Regularly updated data ensures stakeholders have access to the latest trends and insights.
<p>"Market" Target market</p>	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>The Open Science Observatory serves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National and regional policymakers. ● Research institutions and universities. ● Funders and international organizations. ● Open Science advocates and communities.

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	<p>Early adopters include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National governments tracking the implementation of Open Science mandates. • Institutions aligning their research practices with Open Science principles. • Funding bodies who require detailed metrics to assess policy compliance and impact.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include static bibliometric tools and proprietary platforms that lack the transparency, open methodology, and FAIR alignment offered by the Open Science Observatory. By integrating global data and providing regularly updated, customizable insights, the Observatory uniquely addresses gaps in traditional solutions.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The Open Science Observatory is available as an open-access platform. It is integrated with the OpenAIRE ecosystem, ensuring seamless use alongside other OpenAIRE tools like the OpenAIRE Graph and OpenAIRE MONITOR.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The Open Science Observatory is an operational platform with ongoing updates and feature enhancements. New metrics and visualizations are periodically introduced to address evolving stakeholder needs.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	The intellectual property (IP) background is based on OpenAIRE's established methodologies and data aggregation processes, ensuring adherence to open

Topic	Description	Your input
		science principles and collaborative agreements.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground IP encompasses the Observatory's methodologies, metrics, and visualization tools, developed to align with open-access principles and foster interoperability and transparency.

OPENAIRE CONNECT

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Research communities and institutions face significant challenges in assessing the impact and quality of research outputs. One of these difficulties is that there is a lack of aggregation between different registries, repositories, and data sources. This fragmentation hampers the ability to generate meaningful insights and assess research impact effectively.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Many research initiatives have attempted to address this issue by building common repositories, journals, or data sources. However, these efforts are often time-consuming and constrained by the limitations of commercial proprietary solutions, which frequently lack interoperability and fail to align with open science principles.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your</i>	OpenAIRE CONNECT addresses these shortcomings by serving as a gateway to discover and link numerous research outputs—including publications, data, software, and more. It groups them

Topic	Description	Your input
	<p><i>user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i></p>	<p>based on filters such as thematic areas, countries, or specific initiatives. By aggregating selected data sources from the OpenAIRE Graph, OpenAIRE CONNECT provides a streamlined approach for uniting diverse data repositories. Additionally, it can deliver basic statistics or integrate with the OpenAIRE Monitor for deeper analysis and regularly updated statistics (approximately every month in sync with the OpenAIRE Graph updates).</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>OpenAIRE CONNECT is a comprehensive platform designed to support research communities in discovering, linking, and assessing research outputs. It provides tools for tracking, analyzing, and reporting research impact using open-access data. By integrating seamlessly with institutional repositories and leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph, the platform ensures broad applicability and ease of use. Its ability to filter data based on thematic areas, geographic regions, or specific initiatives makes it a uniquely versatile tool for research assessment.</p>
<p>"Market" - Target market</p>	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>The target market for OpenAIRE CONNECT includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and universities. • Research Infrastructures • Individual researchers and collaborative research networks.
<p>"Market" - Early Adopters</p>	<p><i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i></p>	<p>The early adopters for OpenAIRE CONNECT are including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open science advocates and communities. • Universities and institutions seeking to align with open-access mandates.

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research groups in need of transparent and efficient assessment tools.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include proprietary research assessment tools and traditional bibliometric services (e.g., Scopus, Web of Science). While these competitors offer well-established metrics, they lack the openness, interoperability, and alignment with open science principles that define OpenAIRE CONNECT. This distinction represents a significant competitive advantage.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	OpenAIRE CONNECT is a well established service, used by Research Infrastructures, Universities Network, Researchers with thematic interest.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	OpenAIRE CONNECT is a ready service with a subscription model present in the OpenAIRE Catalogue.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	The intellectual property (IP) background includes foundational work and expertise from OpenAIRE's prior initiatives, adhering to agreements outlined in the Consortium Agreement.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground IP includes any enhancements and developments made specifically for the CONNECT platform, ensuring compliance with the terms established in Annex I of the Consortium Agreement.

OPENAIRE GRAPH

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<p><i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i></p>	<p>Research communities and institutions often face challenges in accessing and leveraging interconnected, comprehensive data sources for research assessment. The lack of unified, open, and structured research graphs makes it difficult to derive meaningful insights, perform benchmarks, or track research activities effectively in the open science landscape.</p>
Alternative solution	<p><i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i></p>	<p>Currently, researchers and institutions rely on fragmented or proprietary datasets, often requiring significant manual effort to integrate and analyze. These approaches are time-consuming, lack interoperability, and are frequently constrained by licensing issues. As a result, obtaining a holistic view of research outputs remains a challenge.</p>
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<p><i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i></p>	<p>The OpenAIRE Graph provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation and Interoperability: A unified gateway to discover and link diverse research outputs (publications, datasets, software, and more) through thematic, geographic, or initiative-based filters. • Enriched Insights: Embedded classifications such as Fields of Science (FOS) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), alongside advanced indicators like BipFinder and costs data from OpenAPC. • Open Access: Freely accessible through REST APIs and Zenodo for integration into custom environments, enabling enhanced metrics, benchmarks, and analyses.

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration in OpenAIRE Monitor, which leverages the OpenAIRE Graph Data to create customised dashboards with statistics and analysis monthly updated • The OpenAIRE Graph is already the backbone database in EOSC EU Node.
Description	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>The OpenAIRE Graph (formerly known as the OpenAIRE Research Graph) is one of the largest open scholarly record collections worldwide, key in fostering Open Science and establishing its practices in daily research activities. Conceived as a public and transparent good, populated out of data sources trusted by scientists, the Graph aims to bring discovery, monitoring, and assessment of science back into the hands of the scientific community. Imagine a vast collection of research products all linked together, contextualized, and openly available. Over the years, OpenAIRE has gathered this valuable record, resulting in a massive collection of metadata and links between scientific products, such as articles, datasets, software, and other research products, and entities like organizations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and data sources.</p>
"Market" Target market	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>The OpenAIRE Graph serves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and universities. • Research funders and policymakers. • Data analysts, bibliometricians, scientometricians. • Individual researchers and collaborative research networks.

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Early adopters for the OpenAIRE Graph include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutions and organizations that align with open science principles. • Research groups requiring advanced metrics for thematic and regional analyses. • Analysts and researchers (bibliometrics/scientometrics) seeking comprehensive data for benchmarking and reporting.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include commercial bibliometric tools and traditional research graphs, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Dimensions. While these tools are robust, they are often proprietary and lack the openness and interoperability of the OpenAIRE Graph. The OpenAIRE Graph's emphasis on open science and seamless integration sets it apart as a leading solution.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The OpenAIRE Graph is made available as an open-access service via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST APIs and Zenodo for data retrieval and integration. • OpenAIRE MONITOR for customizable dashboard creation. • Google Cloud (used for training purposes) for expanded accessibility.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The OpenAIRE Graph is an operational service, continuously updated and maintained, with enhancements made available periodically. New access points (e.g., public dataset on Google Cloud) are expected soon.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already</i>	The intellectual property (IP) background draws from OpenAIRE's extensive experience and prior initiatives,

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	ensuring adherence to open science principles and established agreements.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground IP encompasses all enhancements and innovations developed specifically for the OpenAIRE Graph, complying with collaborative agreements and advancing open-access research.

OPENAIRE MONITOR

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Institutions, funders, and researchers struggle to monitor and assess the broad range of research activities and their impact in alignment with Open Science principles. Traditional tools often lack customization, transparency, and the ability to provide timely indicators tailored to the needs of specific stakeholders.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Current monitoring solutions for research assessment often rely on static and proprietary tools that offer limited flexibility. These tools typically fail to align with open science requirements, making it challenging to track diverse research activities and their impacts effectively.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the</i>	OpenAIRE MONITOR provides: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customizable Dashboards: Tailored to specific stakeholders, offering dynamic indicators and analytics. • Real-Time Insights: Powered by the OpenAIRE Graph, it delivers timely and accurate data updates for informed decision-making.

Topic	Description	Your input
	<p><i>KER from the competition / current solutions?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration Support: Facilitates collaboration among stakeholders by offering shared, open-access monitoring solutions. • Open Science Alignment: Fully integrated with open science data and principles, ensuring interoperability and transparency.
<p>Description</p>	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>OpenAIRE MONITOR is a customisable, collaborative, and open platform designed to assist stakeholders in monitoring research activities and their alignment with Open Science principles. Built on the OpenAIRE Graph, MONITOR offers real-time, detailed insights into research outputs, impact metrics, and compliance with Open Access policies. It enables stakeholders to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track research activities at organizational, national, and thematic levels. • Monitor Open Access compliance and funding allocations. • Generate reports for decision-making and strategic planning. <p>MONITOR leverages advanced analytics to present data in a user-friendly, dashboard-based interface. It integrates seamlessly with the OpenAIRE Graph, ensuring timely updates and comprehensive coverage of the research lifecycle.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailored Dashboards: Create customized views to track key performance indicators (KPIs) relevant to organizational goals. • Impact Analysis: Evaluate the societal, economic, and academic impact of research activities through advanced metrics.

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Compliance: Monitor compliance with Open Access and Open Science mandates using data derived from the OpenAIRE Graph. • Collaborative Insights: Enable stakeholders to share dashboards and insights, fostering a collaborative approach to monitoring.
"Market" Target market -	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	The OpenAIRE MONITOR serves: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and universities. • Research funders and policymakers. • Collaborative research infrastructures. • Organizations and initiatives seeking Open Science alignment.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Early adopters include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutions and organizations advocating Open Science. • Funders and policymakers requiring real-time data to inform decisions. • Collaborative research networks seeking shared monitoring tools.
"Market" Competitors -	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Competitors include proprietary monitoring tools and static dashboards offered by traditional research analytics providers. While these tools offer basic functionalities, they lack the real-time, customizable, and collaborative capabilities provided by OpenAIRE MONITOR. Additionally, many competitors do not align with Open Science principles, limiting their interoperability and transparency.
Go to Market - Use model -	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a</i>	OpenAIRE MONITOR is available as an open-access service. Its dashboards can be customized by stakeholders to meet specific needs, and the platform

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	integrates seamlessly with institutional systems and the OpenAIRE Graph.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	OpenAIRE MONITOR is an operational service, continuously updated with the latest data from the OpenAIRE Graph. Enhancements and new features are released periodically based on user feedback.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	The intellectual property (IP) background draws on OpenAIRE's expertise and prior initiatives, ensuring compliance with collaborative agreements and alignment with Open Science principles.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground IP includes innovations and enhancements made specifically for OpenAIRE MONITOR, developed in compliance with open-access agreements and OpenAIRE's commitment to transparency and interoperability.

OPENAIRE RESEARCHER PROFILE

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<p><i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i></p>	<p>Traditional researcher profiles primarily rely on publication lists and quantitative impact metrics that are too parochial and unidimensional to accurately reflect a researcher's career contributions, not just to academia, but also to the wider society.</p> <p>They are therefore doing a disservice to the users – the researchers themselves – by depriving them of the opportunity to showcase the full range of their capabilities and achievements in the best light possible.</p>
Alternative solution	<p><i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i></p>	<p>Primarily through uploading traditional CVs (researcher profiles) to online platforms; narrative CVs are sometimes also used to showcase the qualitative perspective of a researcher's activities, but this is not common practice</p>
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<p><i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i></p>	<p>The researcher profile module within GraspOS combines a modern assessment methodology (incl. quantitative indicators/ metrics and qualitative perspectives) with an interactive UI and visuals to provide a more holistic view of a researcher's career and achievements. Key features of the service include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of all activities/achievements in an interactive timeline • Customizable profiles depending on FoS • Open science activities as defined by UNESCO • Integration of societal and economical contributions • Multiple types of research outputs beyond publication lists • Role description to accompany every activity

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of a Narrative CV (as defined by the Royal Society)
Description	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>The researcher profile will be a product, a framework where researchers can describe various activities. Our approach consists in combining qualitative and quantitative information into a new tool whose design closely follows current policy recommendations and guidelines promoting a responsible approach to research assessment</p>
"Market" Target market	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>First phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual researchers Assessments experts <p>Second phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutions <p>Third phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National-level adoption
"Market" - Early Adopters	<p><i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i></p>	Individual researchers
"Market" Competitors	<p><i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i></p>	<p>Online service tools (e.g., AMiner, Google Scholar, Semantic Scholar) that are used to index, search and mine scientific databases to automatically extract researcher profiles could potentially be perceived as competitors. The strengths of these services lie primarily in their established, mature operational status and the breadth of quantitative indicators they use to assess research impact. However, they do not take into account important elements of a researcher's profile such as qualitative perspectives and societal contributions.</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The service will become available to users through the OpenAIRE services platform. During the first phase of the rollout, researcher data will be integrated into the profile from ORCID and the OpenAIRE Graph; in later stages, interfacing with additional data sources will be accommodated and researchers will also be able to insert information themselves
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Rollout of the service is expected by the end of 2025
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	OpenAIRE TBD
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	TBD

OPENAIRE USAGE COUNTS

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Understanding and analyzing the usage of research outputs is a critical challenge for institutions, publishers, and researchers. Traditional approaches to usage statistics are often inconsistent, proprietary, or not aligned with Open Science principles, making it difficult to track and compare usage effectively.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Existing systems for usage metrics are typically managed by individual publishers or repositories, resulting in fragmented and non-standardized data. Proprietary solutions often lack transparency and interoperability, making it challenging to achieve a comprehensive view of research usage across platforms.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	OpenAIRE Usage Counts provides: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized Metrics: Ensures consistent and transparent usage metrics across repositories and publishers. • Interoperability: Aligns with Open Science principles, enabling integration with other systems and datasets. • Global Coverage: Aggregates usage statistics from multiple trusted sources to provide a comprehensive view. • Open Access: Freely accessible and compliant with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple</i>	OpenAIRE Usage Counts is a service designed to provide standardized, transparent, and FAIR-compliant metrics for research output usage. By aggregating data from repositories,

Topic	Description	Your input
	<p><i>wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>publishers, and other trusted sources, Usage Counts enables stakeholders to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Track views, downloads, and other usage metrics across repositories. • Benchmark usage patterns across disciplines, regions, or institutions. • Analyze trends to understand the reach and impact of research outputs. <p>The service integrates seamlessly with OpenAIRE's ecosystem and adheres to COUNTER standards for consistent and reliable reporting.</p> <p>Assess</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage Tracking: Provides detailed metrics on the views and downloads of research outputs. • Benchmarking: Enables comparative analysis across repositories and publishers. • Trend Analysis: Offers insights into the reach and impact of research outputs over time. • Open Science Alignment: Ensures that metrics are FAIR-compliant and accessible for reuse.
<p>"Market" - Target market</p>	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>OpenAIRE Usage Counts serves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and universities. • Publishers and repository managers. • Policymakers and funders. • Individual researchers and collaborative research networks.
<p>"Market" - Early Adopters</p>	<p><i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i></p>	<p>Early adopters include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Access publishers and repositories. • Institutions seeking to align their metrics with Open Science principles.

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funders requiring standardized metrics to evaluate research impact.
"Market" Competitors	<p><i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i></p>	<p>Competitors include proprietary analytics and usage metric tools provided by individual publishers or platforms. These tools often lack standardization and interoperability, making OpenAIRE Usage Counts a superior alternative due to its openness, FAIR alignment, and integration with a broader ecosystem.</p>
Go to Market - Use model	<p><i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i></p>	<p>OpenAIRE Usage Counts is available as an open-access service, integrated with repositories and other platforms. It supports standardized reporting and provides APIs for seamless integration into existing workflows.</p>
Go to Market - Timing	<p><i>What is the time to market?</i></p>	<p>OpenAIRE Usage Counts is an operational service with continuous updates to ensure alignment with evolving standards and stakeholder needs.</p>
Go to Market - IPR Background	<p><i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i></p>	<p>The intellectual property (IP) background is based on OpenAIRE's expertise in managing and standardizing research metrics, ensuring compliance with collaborative agreements and open science principles.</p>
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<p><i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i></p>	<p>The foreground IP includes methodologies, standards, and tools developed specifically for OpenAIRE Usage Counts to enhance transparency, interoperability, and alignment with FAIR principles.</p>

UniBo/OpenCitations

SEMANTIC CITATION CLASSIFIER

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	<p>The Semantic Citation Classifier (SCC) is a software that performs the automatic annotation of in-text citations in academic papers provided in PDF.</p> <p>It addresses two orthogonal sub-problems: (i) automatic extraction of bibliographic references from PDF articles and (ii) identification of the citation intents, i.e. the underlying reason for which an author references one or more other research works within his/her paper.</p> <p>The idea behind SCC is to help users (researchers, academia, publishers, institutions...) with a tool that enables smarter and more informed literature reviews, funding decisions, and academic impact analyses. This tool also supports researchers in finding relevant literature for their works and experiments.</p>
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	<p>The two subproblems have already been addressed by researchers, mainly with machine learning and deep learning techniques.</p> <p>The best results were achieved by exploiting pretrained models, for instance by GROBID to extract references, or by SciCite to classify citation intents.</p>
Unique Selling Point USP -	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative</i>	The tool performs better than its competitors in both sub-tasks. In

Topic	Description	Your input
Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	<p>particular, it shows a higher accuracy wrt the pre-trained GROBID module for extracting references and it is the current state-of-the-art (SOTA) in the Citation Intent Classification task on the SciCite dataset (which is the currently most-used dataset for this task).</p> <p>The tool also identifies and considers the sections in which each citation appears, in order to improve the accuracy of the final classification. This is a distinctive trait in comparison to similar approaches.</p>
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	<p>Our tool is delivered to the users through both a web-based platform, and an API.</p> <p>The citation extraction module is derived from GROBID and re-trained on a manually annotated set of bibliographic references.</p> <p>The citation intent classifier is based on LLMs and the core is an Ensemble Model, which allows to classify citations by taking into consideration also section titles (extracted in the first phase of the analysis).</p>
"Market" Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	<p>The target market includes academia, publishing, and bibliometric analytics sectors, focusing on scholarly content evaluation and dissemination. Key customers are researchers seeking tools for efficient literature reviews, universities or publishers evaluating research impact or trying to enhance citation metadata, and bibliometric platforms refining citation-based metrics.</p>
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first.</i>	<p>The early adopters for our citation intent classifier (CIC) are academic researchers</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	in highly collaborative and citation-intensive fields like computer science, biology, or social sciences, who struggle with efficiently navigating and interpreting vast literature. They feel the problem due to the high volume of publications and their need to differentiate between foundational, methodological, and result-oriented citations for their own research.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Our competitors are mainly other models specifically developed for the tasks of extracting and classifying citations. We outperform the other available models for both subtasks.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	The tool is available as a web-based application, but also by means of an API that can be integrated in other systems.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Both the Web application and the API are available and online in beta version.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	The background is the code previously developed by UniBO and available at the starting time of the project, together with all past results on these research tasks.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground is the code and models developed during the project and available as open-source on GitHub and Zenodo.

OPENCITATIONS

Topic	Description	Your input
<p>Problem</p>	<p><i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i></p>	<p>The problem OpenCitations aims to address revolves around the open availability, accessibility, and reusability of bibliographic and citation data, which are crucial for scholarly communication, research metrics, and advancing Open Science.</p> <p>Currently, research assessment is affected by an overall lack of transparency of the methods in use, the scholarly community has to strive to put to commons data that cannot be copyrighted, such as citations.</p> <p>The open availability of bibliographic citation data is a crucial requirement for the bibliometrics and scientometrics domain for the creation of reproducible metrics for research assessment exercises.</p> <p>Since its foundation in 2010, OpenCitations has been established with this aim as a community-guided open infrastructure to provide access to global scholarly bibliographic and citation data for the benefit of the scholarly community as a whole.</p>
<p>Alternative solution</p>	<p><i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i></p>	<p>The scholarly community is striving to put into the commons scholarly data, including bibliographic citations, through initiatives and set of guidelines, such as the National Plan for Open Science, the Leiden Manifesto and DORA Declaration. The latest initiatives are the creation of the CoARA Working Group Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA), and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information.</p>
<p>Unique Selling Point USP -</p>	<p><i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution</i></p>	<p>USP: There are other open sources of scholarly bibliographic information and of reference lists from which citations</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
<p>Unique Value Proposition UVP</p>	<p><i>do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i></p>	<p>can be inferred, however, OpenCitations is unique among them in having numerous beneficial characteristics regarding its data, its governance and its technical apparatus. In particular</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides an enduring source of comprehensive high-quality scholarly bibliographic and citation metadata • enables integration with complementary sources of open scholarly information; • provides information, both in human-readable form and in interoperable machine-readable Linked Open Data formats; • is a disruptive and free alternative to proprietary citation services; • shares the values of Open Science; • its data is published under a Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Waiver, and may be freely reused for any purpose, including commercial purposes. • It provides open access to fundamental factual information, and also by charging nothing for such access or for related services. This means that OpenCitations' activities generate no income to sustain its operations. While this poses an obvious financial problem, it also provides our unique 'selling point' in terms of charitable and institutional stakeholder support. <p>UVP: At present, scholarly institutions are paying large sums for access to such information. Academia is thus likely to value highly the alternative free availability of such information, provided it is sufficiently accurate and comprehensive. It is the potential of OpenCitations for increasing its</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
		<p>coverage over the next five years, its ability to provide safe long-term preservation of such comprehensive provenance-enriched high-quality bibliographic and citation data, and its ability to maintain enduring access to such open data and thus guarantee the transparency and reproducibility of analyses based upon it, in a way that commercial organizations cannot guarantee, that constitutes the real value and uniqueness of OpenCitations.</p>
Description	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>OpenCitations is an independent not-for-profit infrastructure organization for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data by the use of Semantic Web (Linked Data) technologies. OpenCitations makes it possible to you to access bibliographic data with no cost, independently of your nationality, your wealth and the prestige of your institution.</p>
"Market" - Target market	<p><i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i></p>	<p>OpenCitations facilitates free access to scholarly information and indicators for scholars, academic administrators and librarians, research funders, tool and service developers, scholarly publishers interested in citation tracking.</p>
"Market" - Early Adopters	<p><i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i></p>	<p>OpenCitations early adopters are the scholars and tool and service developers who use OpenCitations regularly for research purposes and the development of data services, and the academic administrators and research funders for determination of academic performance and evaluation of grant targeting purposes.</p>
"Market" - Competitors	<p><i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are</i></p>	<p>OpenCitations main competitors are services which offer the access to bibliographic metadata and citation data</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
	<p><i>their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i></p>	<p>via commercial plans and fees (Scopus; Web of Science) and for free (Dimensions; Semantic Scholar; OpenAlex). All these competitors share the Academia and research organization as one of the targeted users. While Scopus and Web of Science offer different types of bibliographic metadata, including the abstracts, OpenCitations primary focus is on citation data, which are provided with a universal scope and provenance information (a unique characteristic of OpenCitations). As highlighted by Alberto Martín-Martín (University of Granada) in a 2021 analysis, the coverage of OpenCitations' main database, COCI, is approaching that of Scopus, Web of Science, but with the additional benefit that OpenCitations data are free and open - OpenCitations charges no fees for any of its services or accessing to any of its data. Moreover, all OpenCitations data is published under a Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Waiver that permits downloading and re-use of any nature, while among the competitors, just OpenAlex adopts a CC0 license for its data. OpenAlex data and Semantic Scholar data also are freely provided for any use, however, compared to OpenCitations, Semantic Scholar doesn't share information on its data usage metrics, while OpenAlex provides neither clear information on its citation coverage, nor on its integrations. OpenCitations is run by and for the Academic community, and not by a commercial company, thus ensuring that it is not at risk of arbitrary closure for commercial reasons.</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	OpenCitations service delivery involves its Datasets, which include the OpenCitations Index and the OpenCitations Meta. All the data in any of the OpenCitations Datasets can be retrieved by using an HTTP REST API. To query OpenCitations data visit: https://opencitations.net/querying
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	OpenCitations is TRL-8 and ready to use.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	The background is the code previously developed by UNIBO/OpenCitations and available at the starting time of the project, together with all past results on these research tasks.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	The foreground is the code and models developed during the project and available as open-source on GitHub and Zenodo.

INRIA

SOFTWARE-SYNC

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The app allows the synchronization between xml-tei and the JSON result of Softcite into one xml-tei file The users are the evaluator/evaluated and Institutions/laboratory for the software of their publications
Alternative solution	Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.	Mention of software by labs on a declarative basis so far.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open-access on Github Simple to install with basic Git/Python knowledge. Identifies mentions of softwares that the authors may have omitted in their declarative statements. Distinguishes 3 types of software mentions : created, used, shared, reflecting the various activities around software
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The SOFTWARE-Sync application processes sets of XML or PDF files generated by GROBID, alongside JSON result files from SOFTCITE, to produce either enhanced XML files or CSV files summarizing software mentions found.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	The users are the evaluator/evaluated and Institutions/laboratory for the software of their publications

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RPOs across different fields, and more specifically the Computer Science field, who need to assess research production.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not known so far
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Software-Sync is available on GitHub, with an explanation on how to install it. It can be used as a standalone process to retrieve software mentions from pdf full text academic papers.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2025
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The background is the code developed in the context of GraspOS in order to address the need to assess researcher production beyond publications.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The foreground is code developed and available on github together with instructions for autonomous installation and fine-tuning.

SOFTWARE-VIZ

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	This is a visualisation tool using the JSON from Softcite to create a web flask app. It was developed as a Proof of concept based on HAL open archive and designed to use HAL's metadata (in XML-tei). A universal version could be developed using SOFTWARE-Sync results only.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Mention of software by labs on a declarative basis so far.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-access on GitHub • Simple to install with basic Docker/Git/Python knowledge. • Shows software mentioned in publications that the authors may have omitted in their declarative statements. • Distinguishes 3 types of software mentions : created, used, shared, reflecting the various activities around software • Create a web app to monitor and display the software's mentions in a dataset.
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	SOFTWARE-Viz is responsible for visualizing the processed data. It takes the synchronized data from SOFTWARE-Sync and transforms it into visual outputs or dashboards.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	The users are the evaluator/evaluated and Institutions/laboratory for the software of their publications

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessors of the Computer Science field.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not known so far.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Software-Viz is available on GitHub, with an explanation on how to install it. It provides a UIX that enables to visualise software mentions, as well a citations from publications, and a timeline chart of software citations.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2025;
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The background is the code developed in the context of GraspOS in order to address the need to assess researcher production beyond publications, adding a visualisation module compliant with xml-tei format.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The foreground is code developed and available on github.

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) and Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)

ASSESSMENT PORTFOLIO REGISTRY

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Responsible research assessment is quite a complex process requiring clear assessment purpose, agreed values, objective criteria across a diversity of research of contributions in relation to dimensions such as open science and societal impacts. This content must then be collected for analysis in an assessment event, while respecting principles such as transparency and inclusivity.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	First is the Assessment Portfolio Registry. Assessment portfolios are minted from the registry service, which are then used to facilitate the collection of inputs for research assessment, serving both as an account of the agreed approach and associated evidence for a given assessment event and as a shared resource for conducting the assessment and documenting the outcomes.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	There will be UI and API for the service, meaning the service can be integrated into local research information platforms through the service API, or can be used through offered UI. The service enabling creation of an assessment portfolio as a collaborative, multi-actor digital object that brings together the key information about assessment planning (e.g., a readiness self-assessment, values statement, and a purpose statement), agreed content to be assessed, and the assessment protocol (that articulates the assessment approach).

Topic	Description	Your input
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	Assessment portfolio registry entries are collaborative digital tools that compile key information, evidence, and protocols for research assessment, supporting planning, execution, and documentation of outcomes. They serve as shared resources for managing the full assessment process, with potential implementation through adaptations of the RAiD service for an Assessment Portfolio Registry.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Research Performance Organization (RPO), Research Funding Organization (RFO)
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	Anticipating CoARA signatories
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	Unknown
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	RPO or RFO can use the service for creation of assessment portfolios.

Topic	Description	Your input
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Should be ready in 2025.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	

ASSESSMENT PROTOCOL REGISTRY

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	Enacting change in research assessment is difficult. Many stakeholders, often with varied interests, are needed to participate. This process often lacks transparency, both within the organisation within the community. There is uncertainty about making changes.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Assessment Protocol Registry. Assessment Protocols Registry is designed to register and publish assessment protocols after the completion of an assessment event. Register/publish/share assessment approaches, by registering the assessment protocol and associated planning in a digital repository.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits</i>	Publishing assessment protocols promotes transparency, reuse and mutual learning.

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	The Assessment Protocols Registry is designed to register and publish assessment protocols after the completion of an assessment event. These registered protocols would ideally include documentation of the values, purpose and contextual factors related to the assessment, as well as the data sources and indicators used in the assessment. Individual identities and specific evidence used in the assessment are not included. The registry of assessment portfolios will be implemented based on a Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) service point. Based on this implementation, each registered protocol will have a persistent identifier and a metadata record for documenting aspects of the assessment event and suitable for public consumption. Although a user interface is available for administering access and compiling content (useful for small tasks), this service will be ideally implemented on a local platform via API.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	Research Performance Organization (RPO) Research Funding Organization (RFO)
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel</i>	Anticipating CoARA signatories

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	
"Market" Competitors	<i>- Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	For our best knowledge there is no established and well-known registry of assessment protocols.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	RPO or RFO can use the service for registration of used assessment protocols
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Should be ready in 2025
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	

OPENNESS PROFILE REGISTRY

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your</i>	Contributions to open science are often excluded in research assessment events

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	and they are often hidden in researcher profiles and CVs.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	The exposure of OS activities as an independent information entity, which should enable a more diverse consideration of Open Science in research assessment.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	The main ambition of the Openness Profile is to enable exposure of OS activities as an independent information entity, leading to a more diverse consideration of Open Science in research and related assessment. The Openness Profile is an updatable display of an individual's Open Science activities. Representing contribution of a researcher/institution/group to open science in a machine readable way including evidence (related outputs, OS activities, etc.)
Description	<i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i>	It will be a registry of Openness profiles for researchers/institutions/groups. A profile will include metadata about open science contributions and linked outputs (evidence). Open Science contributions are accommodated through flexible inclusion of both quantitative data and qualitative narratives, enabling structured, evidence-based research assessment.
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Local or national Research information systems • Research Performance Organization (RPO)

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	The GraspOS pilots for implementing the Openness Profile vary significantly, with some focusing on technical integration into existing infrastructures, such as Research.fi (CSC pilot) and Brainmap (UEFISCDI pilot). Others plan to leverage RAiD technology, adapting it to highlight their employees' Open Science contributions.
"Market" Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	There are services enabling making researchers' profiles, but not clearly separate Open Science contributions (e.g. Google Scholar, OpenAIRE Researcher Profile, BIP!Scholar)
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	Researchers can use the service for registration of their Openness profile via UI of the service or via a local platform integrated with the registry (e.g. Research.fi).
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	Should be ready in 2025
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	

GRNET and EGI Foundation (EGI)

EOSC ACCOUNTING SERVICE

Topic	Description	Your input
Problem	<i>Describe the problem you are addressing (the problem your potential users have). Potential users are the people, companies, organisations, etc. that you expect will use the result (and generate an impact). They are your "Customers".</i>	The EOSC Accounting Service tackles the complex challenge of harvesting usage metrics across different projects, users, and resources, essential for organisations, research institutions, and service providers. Within this project, the service is targeted to capture open science-related impact metrics, oriented to infrastructures' usage statistics. Entities who may not be able to provide insights into these types of metrics are potential customers.
Alternative solution	<i>Describe how your "customer" has solved the problem so far.</i>	Customers may still be struggling to address this issue, either lacking a suitable solution or having developed their own, which often involves substantial investments in hardware and software development and maintenance.
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	<i>Describe the competitive advantages, the innovative aspects. What does your solution do better, what are the benefits considering what your user/customer wants, how does your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes the KER from the competition / current solutions?</i>	Competitive advantages and innovative aspects of the EOSC Accounting Service are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The service provides a centralized, ready-to-use solution that simplifies the collection, aggregation, and dissemination of usage metrics across multiple infrastructures and projects. This reduces costs and resource burdens for customers and allows them to focus on core activities rather than technical upkeep.

Topic	Description	Your input
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metrics can be determined by the Customers according to their needs. • The users are able to execute complex search queries to retrieve specific metrics, based on their requirements. • The REST API enables seamless input from diverse resources, providing a flexible and standardised way to capture metrics across varied infrastructures and projects, serving in an interoperability manner. • Secure access through authenticated clients ensures that sensitive data is protected, allowing only authorized users to view and manage accounting information.
<p>Description</p>	<p><i>Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e., product, service, process, standard, course, policy recommendation, publication, etc.). Use simple wording, avoid acronyms, make sure you explain how your UVP is delivered.</i></p>	<p>Our solution is an online platform that helps organizations, research institutions, and service providers to store, analyze, retrieve, and share metrics that have been previously designated and sent by the customer.</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
"Market" - Target market	<i>Describe the market in which your product/service will be used/can "compete", answering the following questions: - What is the target market? - Who are the customer segments?</i>	<p>The target market includes research institutions, universities, public research organizations, and service providers in general that manage or fund scientific resources and seek to understand, store, or optimize their usage. Customer segments within this market include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and universities, which need tools to track and report the use of shared resources and demonstrate the impact of their services. • Service providers and infrastructures (e.g., data centers, computational resources) that offer scientific tools or platforms, aiming to improve resource allocation and showcase value to their users and funders. • Project managers and administrators who require detailed metrics on project utilization and efficiency to make data-driven decisions on resource distribution.
"Market" - Early Adopters	<i>Early adopters are the "customers" you are willing to address first. They are usually the ones that feel the problem harder than all the others (they are not the project partners).</i>	<p>Early adopters for the EOSC Accounting for Services platform are likely to be large research institutions, universities, and national research infrastructures that manage multiple projects and significant resources but lack an integrated, scalable solution for tracking and analyzing usage metrics. These organizations feel the problem acutely, as they often handle high volumes of data and diverse user bases, making it challenging to gather and interpret metrics across various departments, services, and collaborations.</p>
"Market" - Competitors	<i>Who are your "competitors" (note: they are the ones offering "alternative solutions")? What are</i>	<p>Our main competitors are custom-built solutions and general data analytics platforms. Custom-built solutions</p>

Topic	Description	Your input
	<i>their strengths and weaknesses comparing to you?</i>	provide tailored functionalities but are costly and resource-intensive, requiring substantial investments in hardware, software development, and ongoing maintenance. In contrast, our platform is a ready-to-use, scalable solution that reduces costs and complexity. On the other hand, our solution may lack some advanced options offered by general analytics tools, whereas scaling for very large datasets or real-time data processing could present performance challenges in highly complex infrastructures.
Go to Market - Use model	<i>Explain what is your "use model", how the KER will be put in use (made available to "customers" to generate an impact). Examples of use models: manufacturing of a new product, provision of a service, direct industrial use, technology transfer, license agreement, contract research, publications, standards, etc. Note training is a service.</i>	Our "use model" is primarily based on the provision of a service. The EOSC Accounting for Services platform will be made available to customers through a subscription-based model, where organizations, research institutions, and service providers can register to and access the platform to collect, analyse, and report on their resource usage metrics.
Go to Market - Timing	<i>What is the time to market?</i>	The time to market involves customers defining the specific metrics they are interested in, then coordinating with the Accounting Service support to integrate these metrics' definitions into the platform. Once the metrics' definitions are integrated, customers can register their users in the system enabling them to start using the platform, meaning sending and retrieving the associated metrics.
Go to Market - IPR Background	<i>What is the Background (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement, in Annex I.</i>	Under the current IPR background, the Accounting Service maintained by GRNET is a robust platform designed to streamline metric harvesting, archiving, and exchange across diverse

Topic	Description	Your input
		infrastructures, providers, and projects.
Go to Market - IPR Foreground	<i>What is the Foreground (type/partner)? Provide information considering also what already agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i>	GRNET, as contributing expertise in EOSC Core, will extend the EOSC Accounting for Services core tool by adding support for a more complex type of metrics in it that may be used to capture open science-related impact metrics, oriented to infrastructures' usage statistics.

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